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XIX ciclo

University of Pavia
Department of Computer and System Science
Ph.D. Program in “Bioengineering and Bioinformatics”

ELECTROCARDIOGRAM SIGNAL AUTOMATIC ANALYSIS

Ph. D. Thesis
George Karraz

Ph.D. Tutor: Prof. G. Magenes
Ph.D. Coordinator: Prof. M. Stefanelli

2003-2006

To my father and my mother

Without you, I would definitely not be where I am today...

George.

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Gorge Karraz

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INTRODUCTION

Modern engineering offers sophisticated means for monitoring diagnosis and therapy of cardiac diseases, the most common cause of death in the western world. There has been a rapid expansion and an increased utilization of computerized electrocardiography in recent years. The number of different ECG computer programs has steadily increased. Each of these programs has basically two distinct parts, a measurement and an interpretation part. In the measurement part various algorithms are used for wave recognition, beat selection and parameter extraction. In the interpretation phase different criteria and classification schemes are applied on the computed measurements in order to reach diagnostic ECG statements. The result is an improved quality of life as well as an increased life expectancy for many individuals suffering from cardiac diseases.

Several approaches to investigating cardiac activity are today available, the 12-lead surface electrocardiogram (ECG) being by far the most widely used. The ECG provides a global description of the heart electrical activity and it has been found helpful in diagnosing a multitude of cardiac diseases, by considering rate and morphology of the ECG signal. The three lead vector cardiogram (VCG) also provides information of the electrical activity; being an orthogonal description, the VCG is useful for studying the electrical activity in the three spatial dimensions. The endocardial electrogram (EGM) is used to study local activity and it is used in implantable devices designed for cardiac rhythm management (CRM) where surface electrodes are inappropriate.

The recognition and analysis of the ECG signals is a very important task. This could be difficult because the size and form of these signals may change eventually and can be noised. Many tools, methods and algorithms from signal processing theory have been proposed, described and implemented in the literature. Greater part of them was developed under Matlab, using Signal processing and Wavelet Toolboxes.

This doctoral thesis contributes to the field of cardiology by presenting several algorithms for improved analysis and is to put forward solutions to certain problems encountered in the processing of ECG.

First chapter is theoretical and is focused on heart anatomy and physiology in order to describe the ECG signal origin and typical signal parameters in normal cases.

It concludes with the description of the manifestation of two types of pathologies recognizable by the signal: arrhythmia and ischemia.

Second chapter includes ECG theoretical study representing different examples of abnormal traces.

Third chapter discusses distortion factors in an ECG signal explaining different noise types overlapped upon the signal itself especially in the frequency domain.

Fourth chapter discusses the different pre-processing methods studied in the literature in order to filter the signal from the types of noises of the previous chapter. We tried to choose some methods to create a filtering system that can reduce the noise with the smallest lost in the signal.

In the fifth chapter we start with the first ECG pattern recognition passage, the QRS-detection. We discuss the performance of four different QRS-detection algorithms set up in literature and then we develop a new one.

We finish with a comparison between the several studied algorithms and the developed one.

In this study we took the data from the database 48 ECG traces MIT-BIH. This algorithm realized an improvement in the obtained outcomes comparing with the other studied ones. Such development is composed by two main phases: pre-filtering and thresholding.

Sixth chapter continues the previous subject and is about the automatic recognition of the other two ECG components: the P and T waves.

In this chapter, as in the fifth one, we study four different algorithms, already studied in literature, and then we develop a new one comparing the several algorithm outcomes in the EGC trace.

In seventh chapter we explain the neural networks theory we'll use later for the ECG signal classification. This chapter comprehends the study of forward and backward neural networks in different topologies in one and multi hidden layers. Moreover we studied some neural network training algorithms we used later in this thesis.

In eighth chapter we propose a new ECG filtering system going by the QRS detection algorithm and the back propagation method of a neural network.

In chapter nine we studied Heart Rate Variability (HRV) and ischemic episodes in long term ECG signal. Firstly we discussed the HRV parameters meaning both in time plane and in frequency plane using several methods proposed by literature to calculate these parameters; secondly we developed two new algorithms for premature cardiac beat classification and ischemic episodes automatic recognition, the first one uses the relative ratio between two consecutive points in the HRV time series. Where the second algorithm is based on the ST segment morphologic study because of its importance in such cases and the C-mean Fuzzy logic algorithm. Outcomes have been shown on two leads long term traces together with HRV parameters. We noted that, in some cases of cardiac arteries diseases (CAD), the rise of an ischemia can be perceived thanks to HRV parameters.

In chapter ten we create a new method to classify five different types of arrhythmia based on the use of neural networks with two hidden layers and trained by three different algorithms (Bayesian, Backpropagation, and Levenberg Marequardt). We noted that Baysian classifier has the best performance compared to the other developed ones.

CHAPTER 1

ANATOMY AND PHYSIOLOGY OF THE HEART

1.1 Location of the Heart

The heart is located in the chest between the lungs behind the sternum and above the diaphragm. It is surrounded by the pericardium. Its size is about that of fist and its weight is about 250-300 g. Its center is located about 1.5 cm to the left of the midsagittal plane. Above the heart there are the great vessels: superior and inferior vena cava, the pulmonary artery and vein, as well as the aorta. The aortic arch lies behind the heart. The esophagus and the spine lie further behind the heart. An over all view is given in Figure 1. 1 (Williams and Warwick, 1989).

Figure 1.1 location of the heart in the thorax. It is bounded by the diaphragm, lungs, esophagus, descending aorta, and sternum.

1.2 Anatomy of the Heart

Heart's walls are composed of a cardiac muscle called *myocardium*. It also has *striations* similar to skeletal muscle. It consists of four compartments: the *right* and *left* atria and *ventricles*. Heart is oriented so that the anterior aspect is the right ventricle and while the posterior aspect shows the left atrium (see Figure 1.2). The atria form one unit and the ventricles another one. This has special importance for the electrical function of the heart which will be discussed later. The left ventricle pumps blood to the systemic circulation, where the pressure is considerably higher than the pulmonary circulation one, which arises from the right ventricular outflow.

The cardiac muscle fibers are oriented spirally (see Figure 1.3) and are divided into four groups: two groups of fibers wind around the outside of both ventricles. Beneath these fibers a third group winds around both ventricles. Beneath these fibers a fourth group winds only around the left ventricle. The fact that cardiac muscle cells are oriented more tangentially than radially, and that the resistivity of the muscle is lower in the direction of the fiber has importance in electrocardiography.

The heart has four valves. Between the right atrium and ventricle lies the *tricuspid* valve, and between the left atrium and ventricle is the *mitral* valve. The *pulmonary* valve lies between right ventricle and pulmonary artery, while the *aortic* valve lies in the outflow tract of the left ventricle (controlling flow to the aorta).

The blood returns from the systemic circulation to the right atrium and from there it goes through the tricuspid valve to the right ventricle. It is ejected from the right ventricle through the pulmonary valve to the

lungs. Oxygenated blood returns from the lungs to the left atrium and from there through the mitral valve to the left ventricle. Finally blood is through the aortic valve to the aorta and the systemic circulation.

Figure 1. 2. The anatomy of the heart and associated vessels.

Figure 1. 3. Orientation of the cardiac muscle fibers.

1.3 Electric Activation of the Heart

1.3.1 Cardiac muscle cell

In the heart muscle cell, or *myocyte*, electric activation takes place by means of the same mechanism as in the nerve cell- that is, from the inflow of sodium ions across the cell membrane. The amplitude of the action potential is also similar being about 100 mV for both nerve and muscle. The cardiac muscle impulse duration is, however, two orders of magnitude longer than that in either nerve cell or skeletal muscle. A *plateau phase* follows cardiac depolarization, and thereafter repolarization takes place. As in the nerve cell, repolarization is a consequence of the outflow of potassium ions. The duration of the action impulse is about 300 ms, as shown in Figure 1. 4 (Netter, 1971).

Associated with the electric activation of cardiac muscle cell is its mechanical contraction, which occurs a little later. For the sake of comparison, Figure 1.5 illustrates the electric activity and mechanical contraction of frog sartorius muscle, frog cardiac muscle, and smooth muscle from the rat uterus (Ruch and Patton, 1982).

An important distinction between cardiac muscle from tissue and skeletal muscle is that in cardiac muscle, activation can propagate from on cell to another in any direction. As a result, the activation wavefronts are of rather complex shape. The only exception is the boundary between the atria and ventricles, which the activation wave normally cannot cross except along a special conduction system, since a nonconducting barrier of fibrous tissue is present.

1.3.2 The conduction system of the heart

Located in the right atrium at the superior vena cava there is the *sinus node* (*sinoatrial* or *SA node*) which consists of specialized muscle cells. The sinoatrial node in human beings is in the shape of crescent and is about 15mm long and 5mm wide (see Figure 1. 6). The SA nodal cells are self-excitatory, *pacemaker cells*. They generate an action potential at the rate of about 70 per minute. From the sinus node, propagates throughout the atria, but cannot propagate directly across the boundary between the atria and the ventricles.

The *atrioventricular node* (AV node) is located in the boundary between the atria and ventricles; it has an intrinsic frequency of about 50 pulses/min. However, if the AV node is triggered with a higher pulse frequency, it follows this higher frequency. In a normal heart, the AV node provides only conducting path from the atria to the ventricles. Thus, under normal conditions, the latter can be excited only by pulses that propagate through it.

Propagation from the AV node to the ventricles is provided by a specialized conduction system. Proximally this system is composed of a common bundle, called the *bundle of His* (named after German physician Wilhelm His, jr., 1863-1934). More distally, it separates into two *bundle branches* propagating along each side of the septum, constituting the *right* and *left bundle branches*. (The left bundle subsequently divides into an anterior and posterior branch). Even more distally the bundles ramify into *Purkinje fibres* (named after Jan Evangelista Purkinje (Czech, 1787-1869)). That diverge to the inner sides of the ventricular walls. Propagation along the conduction system takes place in relatively high speed conditions once it is within the ventricle region, but prior to this (through the AV node) the velocity is extremely slow.

From the inner side of the ventricular wall, many activation sites cause the formation of a wavefront which propagates through the ventricular mass toward the outer wall. This process results from cell-to-cell activation. After each ventricular muscles region has depolarized, repolarization occurs. Repolarization is not a propagating phenomenon, and because the action impulse duration is much shorter at the *epicardium* (the outer side of the cardiac muscle) than at the *endocardium* (the inner side of the cardiac muscle), the termination of activity appears as if it were propagating from the epicardium toward the endocardium.

Figure 1. 4. Electrophysiology of the cardiac muscle cell.

Figure 1. 5. Electric and mechanical activity in:
(A) frog sartorius muscle cell.
(B) frog cardiac muscle cell.
(C) rat uterus wall smooth muscle cell.

In each the upper curve shows the transmembrane voltage behaviour, whereas the lower one describes the mechanical contraction associated with it.

Figure 1. 6. The conduction system of the heart.

Figure 1. 7. The different waveforms for each of the specialized cells found in the heart are shown. The latency shown approximates that normally found in a healthy heart.

Because the intrinsic rate of the sinus node is the greatest, it sets the activation frequency of the all heart. If the connection from the atria to the AV node fails, the AV node adopts its intrinsic frequency. If the conduction system fails at the bundle of His, the ventricles will beat at the rate determined by their own region that has the highest intrinsic frequency. The electric events in the heart are summarized in table 1. 1. The action impulse waveforms observed in different specialized cardiac tissue are shown in Figure 1. 7. Note that the atrial repolarization occurs during the ventricular depolarization; therefore, it is not normally seen in the electrocardiogram.

A classical study of the propagation of excitation in human heart was made by Durrer and his co-workers (Durrer et al., 1970). They isolated the heart from a subject who had died because of various cerebral conditions and who had no previous history of cardiac diseases. The heart was removed within 30 min post mortem and perfused. As many as 870 electrodes were placed into the cardiac muscle, the electric activity was then recorded by a tap recorder and played back at a lower speed by the ECG writer, thus the effective paper speed was 960 mm/s, giving a time resolution better than 1 ms. Figure 1.8 is redrawn from these experimental data. The ventricles are shown with the anterior wall of the left and partly that the right ventricle opened.

The isochronic surface shows clearly that ventricular activation starts from the inner wall of the left ventricle and proceeds more tangentially.

1.4 The Genesis of the Electrocardiogram

1.4.1 Activation currents in cardiac tissue

Section 1. 3. 1 discussed cardiac electric events on an intracellular level. Such electric signals (as illustrate in Figures 1. 4, 1. 5, and 1. 7) may be recorded by microelectrode, which is inserted inside a cardiac muscle cell. However, the electrocardiogram (ECG) is a recording of the electric potential, generated by the heart electric activity, on the surface of the thorax. The ECG signal represents the extracellular electric behaviour of the cardiac muscle tissue. In this section I explain the ECG signal genesis via a highly idealized model. Figure (1. 9. A and B) show a segment of cardiac tissue through which propagating depolarization (A) and repolarization (B) wavefront planes are passing. In this illustration wavefronts move from right to left, it means that the time axis

points to the right. There are two important cardiac tissue properties that had been used to analyze the potential and current distribution associated with these propagating waves. First, cells are interconnected by low-resistance pathways (gap junction), as a result in the intracellular space of one cell pass freely into the following cell. Second, the space between cells is very restrictive (accounting for less than 25% of the total volume).

Table 1. I. Electric events in the heart

Location in the heart	Event	Time [ms]	ECG	Conduction velocity [m/s]	Intrinsic frequency [1/min]
SA node	Impulse generated	0		0.05	
Right atrium	Depolarization	5	P	0.8-1.0	
Left atrium,	Depolarization	85	P	0.8-1.0	
AV node	Arrival of impulse	50	P-Q		70-80
AV node	Departure of impulse	125		0.02-0.05	
bundle of His	Impulse	130	interval	1.0-1.5	
bundle	Activated	145		1.0-1.5	
branches	Activated	150		3.0-3.5	
Purkinje fibers	Activated	175		0.3 (axial)	
Endocardium Septum	Depolarization	190		-	
Left ventricle	Depolarization		QRS	0.8	
Epicardium Left ventricle	Depolarization	225			20-40
Right ventricle	Depolarization	250			
Right ventricle	Repolarization	400		Transverse	
Left ventricle	Repolarization		T		
Endocardium					
Left ventricle	Repolarization	600			

As a result, both intracellular and extracellular currents are confined to the direction parallel to the propagation of the plane waveform, and flow in a linear path. In particular when using the condition $I_i + I_o = 0$ and the equation:

$$\frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial x} = -I_i r_i \quad \frac{\partial \phi_o}{\partial x} = -I_o r_o \quad (1.1)$$

Where: ϕ_i, r_i, I_i : they are respectively, potential, resistance, and current in the inter-cellular side.

ϕ_o, r_o, I_o : they are respectively, potential, resistance, and current in the out-cellular side.

$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}$: the gradient of potential.

We obtain
$$\frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial x} = I_o r_i \quad \frac{\partial \phi_o}{\partial x} = -I_o r_o \quad (1.2)$$

Integrating from $x=-\infty$, to $x=x$ gives

$$\phi_i = r_i \int I_o \partial x \quad \phi_o = -r_o \int I_o \partial x \quad (1.3)$$

Subtracting the second of (1.3) from the first, and applying $V_m = \phi_i - \phi_o$, the definition of the transmembrane potential, we obtain:

$$V_m = (r_i + r_o) \int I_o \partial x \quad (1.4)$$

From equation (1.4) we obtain the following important relationships valid for linear core conductor conditions, namely that

$$\phi_i = \frac{r_i}{r_i + r_o} V_m, \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_o = -\frac{r_o}{r_i + r_o} V_m \quad (1.5)$$

These equations describe ‘‘voltage divider’’ conditions and were first pointed out by Hodgkin and Rushton (1946).

Figure 1.8. Isochronic surfaces of the ventricular activation (From Durrer et., 1970).

1.4.2 Depolarization wave

We may now apply equation (1.5) to the propagation wave under investigation. The variation in the value of $V_m(x)$ is easy to infer from Figure 1.9. C (dashed line) since in the *activated* region it is at the plateau voltage, generally around +40 mV whereas in the *resting* region it is around -80 mV. The *transition* region is usually very narrow (about 1 mm corresponding to a depolarization of about 1 ms and a velocity < 1 m/s), as the figure shows. Application of Equation 1.5 results in the extracellular potential (ϕ_o) behaviour shown in figure 6.9. C (solid line). In the Figure 1.9, the ratio $(r_o/r_o + r_i) = 0.5$ has been chosen on the basis of experimental evidence for propagation along the cardiac fiber axis (Kliber and Riegger, 1986). The transmembrane current i_m can be evaluated from $V_m(x)$ in Figure 1.9. C by applying the general cable equation (1.5) as the following:

$$i_m = \frac{1}{r_i + r_o} \frac{\partial^2 V_m}{\partial x^2} \quad (1.6)$$

This current is confined to the depolarization zone. As shown in Figure 1. 9. A, just to the right of the centerline it is inward (thick arrows), and just to the left it is outward (thin arrows). The inward portion reflects the sodium influx, triggered by the very large and rapid rise in sodium permeability. The current outflow is the “local circuit”

Figure 1. 9. The genesis of the electrocardiogram.

current which initially depolarizes the resting tissue, and which advancing to the left (i.e., in the direction propagation). The transmembrane current course is approximated in Figure 1. 9. E using Equation 1. 6.

An examination of the extracellular potential ϕ_o shows it to be uniform except for a rapid change across the warfront. Such a change from plus to minus is what one would expect at a double layer source where the dipole direction is from right to left (from minus to plus). So we conclude that for the depolarization (activation) of cardiac tissue a double layer appears at the wavefront with the dipole orientation in the direction of propagation. One can also approximate the source as proportional to the transmembrane current –estimated here by a lumped negative point source (on the right) and a lumped positive point source (on the left) which taken together constitute a dipole in the propagation direction (to the left).

Finally a double layer, whose positive side is pointing to the recording electrode (to the left), produce a positive (ECG) signal (Figure 1. 9. G).

1.4.3 Repolarization wave

Repolarization wave nature is mainly different from the depolarization one. Unlike depolarization, the repolarization is not a propagation phenomenon. If we examine the repolarization cells location at consecutive time instances, we can however approximate the repolarization with a proceeding wave phenomenon.

As stated previously, when a cell depolarizes another cell close to it then depolarizes and produces an electric field which trigger the depolarization phenomenon. In this way the depolarization proceeds as a propagating wave within cardiac tissue.

Repolarization in a cell occurs because the action pulse has only a certain duration, thus the cell repolarizes at certain instant of time after its depolarization, not because of the repolarization of an adjoining cell. If the action pulses of all cells are of equal duration, the repolarization would of course accurately follow the same sequence as depolarization. In reality, however, this is not the case in ventricular muscle. The epicardial cells action pulses (on the outer surface) are of shorter duration than those of the endocardial cells (on the inner surface). Therefore, the “isochrones” of repolarizing cells proceed from the epicardium to the endocardium, giving the illusion that the repolarization proceeds as a wave from epicardium to endocardium.

If the cardiac action pulses were always of the same shape, then following propagation of depolarization from right to left, the recovery (repolarization) would also proceed from right to left. This case is depicted in the highly idealized Figure 1. 9. B, where the cells activated earliest must necessarily recover first. The recovery of cardiac cells is relatively slow, requiring approximately 100 ms (compare this with time_required to complete activation roughly 1 ms). For this reason in figure 1. 9. B we have depicted the recovery interval is much wider than the activation interval. The polarity of $V_m(x)$ decreases from its plateau value of +40 mV on the left to the resting value of -80 mV on the right (Figure 1. 9. D (dashed line)). Again, Equation 1. 5 may be applied, in this case showing that the extracellular potential ϕ_o (solid line) increases from minus to plus. In this case the double layer source is directed from left to right. And, it is spread out over a wide region of the heart muscle. (In fact, if activation occupies 1 mm, then recovery occupies 100 mm, a relationship that could only be suggested in figure 1.9B, since in fact, it encompasses the entire heart). The transmembrane current I_m can be again evaluated from $V_m(x)$ in Figure 1. 9. D by applying Equation 1. 6. As shown in figure 1. 9. B, to the right of centerline it is outward (thick arrows) and just to the left it is inward (thin arrows). The outward portion reflects the potassium efflux due to the rapid rise of potassium permeability. The current inflow is again the “local circuit” current. The transmembrane current course during repolarization is approximated in Figure 1. 9. F. Thus, during repolarization, a double layer is formed that is similar to that observed during depolarization. The double layer in repolarization, however, has a polarity opposite to that in depolarization, and thus its negative side points toward the recording electrode, as a result, a negative (ECG) signal is recorded (Figure 1. 9. H).

1.5 Heart Diseases

Heart diseases include a variety of disorders. These can be summarized as diseases of the:

1. Pericardium (the lining around the exterior of the heart).
2. Heart valves (degeneration of the valves, infection of the valves or endocarditis).
3. Myocardium (disease of the heart muscle caused by the Ischemia).
4. Impulse forming and conduction system of the heart (abnormal electrical activity of the heart, also called cardiac arrhythmias).

5. Blood vessels (for example, heartworm infection injures the heart by damaging the blood vessels in the pulmonary arteries).

In this thesis we investigate two manifestations of the heart diseases: Arrhythmia and Ischemia.

1.5.1 Arrhythmia

An arrhythmia is an abnormal rhythm of the heart-beats. It can be due to abnormal function of the sinus node or it can arise from other areas which normally do not initiate electrical impulses. The arrhythmia can be manifested as rapid and regular heart-beats (tachycardia), rapid and irregular heart-beats (fibrillation), slow heart-beats (bradycardia), and abnormal extra beats occurring before the anticipated normal beats in a periodic fashion (premature contractions). Arrhythmias originating from the heart upper chambers (above the ventricles) are called supraventricular arrhythmias. Those originating in the heart lower chambers (ventricles) are called ventricular arrhythmias. The symptoms caused by arrhythmias depend on the type, severity, duration and frequency of arrhythmia. The severity of symptoms is also related to the underlying function of the heart. A young person with a normal heart may tolerate the arrhythmia very well but an older person with some associated heart diseases will tolerate the same arrhythmia poorly. The arrhythmia-related symptoms are variable and include palpitations (feeling of rapid beats), weakness, fatigue, chest discomfort, shortness of breath, dizzy spells, and in the most severe form as actual loss of consciousness and cardiac arrest.

1.5.1.1 How to diagnose arrhythmias

To detect an arrhythmia the recording must be done exactly when the patient is having the arrhythmia. Because of the sporadic nature of the arrhythmias the better option is to attach the electrodes to the patient's chest which are then connected to a tape recorder. The heart-beats recorded in the tape are then transferred in a machine that can analyze, display, and record these beats. This is called Ambulatory ECG Recording or Holter Monitoring. This recording is usually done for 24 hours. If the patient does not have the arrhythmia in 24 hours, the recording may be repeated but at times the arrhythmia may not occur and thus not recordable after several attempts. For such type of very sporadic arrhythmia, another type of recorder, activated by the patient, is available. It is similar to the Holter Tape Recorder but is smaller. When the patient has symptoms presumed to be due to arrhythmia, he or she will push a button to record the heart-beats. This recording can be transmitted via telephone from this recorder to a receiver located in the hospital. The medical staff can then review the recording, relate with the symptoms and make an accurate diagnosis. This is called Transtelephone ECG Recording.

1.5.1.2 How to treat arrhythmias

Arrhythmias may not require treatments if they are infrequent and associated with very little symptoms. Sometimes, the symptoms may be significantly improved by avoiding things which precipitate arrhythmias such as excessive use of caffeine. The treatment of underlying heart diseases may also result in significant improvement in the occurrence of arrhythmia. When the arrhythmia is not correctable by these measures and requires specific treatment, various options are available.

- Antiarrhythmic Drugs

These drugs can reduce arrhythmia occurrence and/or decrease the severity. However, the patient has to take the medication on a lifelong basis. Further, the drugs may cause various side effects and rarely even aggravate the arrhythmia. Therefore, close monitoring and follow-up by the physician is necessary. The drugs only prevent the arrhythmia and do not result in permanent cure. If available, it is preferable to choose a mode of therapy which can achieve permanent cure without a significant risk (see below).

- Radiofrequency Catheter Ablation

Many types of abnormal, fast heart rhythm disturbances (tachycardia) can be permanently cured by this new non-surgical approach. Catheters (long cables) are introduced into the heart through the blood vessels and the focus of arrhythmia is identified by recording the electrical activity from inside the heart. A specialized computerized recording and analysis system is used for this purpose. Once the arrhythmia focus is identified, radiofrequency energy (modified high-frequency electrical current) passed through the catheter to that area. This causes heating of tissue in that area and permanently destroys the tiny bundles of heart muscle responsible for the arrhythmia. The permanent cure rate is above 95% with a very low rate of recurrence (1-2%).

- Pacemakers

Pacemakers are primarily needed for the treatment of slow heart rhythms (bradycardia). The artificial pacemaker is a small electrical device which monitors the heart beat and emits electrical impulses which stimulate heart to maintain a regular rhythm. The pacemaker is embedded under the skin and is connected to the heart with electrical wires (leads) which are introduced through the blood vessels. The monitoring of heart-beats and electrical impulses transmission are conducted through these leads. The modern pacemakers are very complex and advanced due to developments in computer applications. These pacemakers can regulate heart rhythm for the varying needs of the patient i.e. rest, sleep, and exercise etc.

- Implantable Defibrillators

These devices are similar to pacemakers but applied treatment in more serious and life-threatening arrhythmias. The device monitors the heart-beat and if a very fast and life-threatening arrhythmia (ventricular fibrillation) occurs, it will deliver an internal electrical shock and restore the heart rhythm back to normal. You may have observed various scenes of cardiac arrest when the paramedical personnel apply electrical shock to the chest of the patient for resuscitation. This device performs the same life-saving function automatically and is available to the high risk patients all the time. The current advanced forms of these devices also perform many other functions such as terminating the fast heart rhythm (tachycardia) by delivering rapid electrical impulses and regulating slow heartbeat like a pacemaker. There is a tremendous amount of memory in these devices and the patient's arrhythmias are stored in the device which can later be retrieved and analyzed by the physicians using special programmers. This is an excellent example of a beneficial use of modern technology for the diagnosis and treatment of life-threatening arrhythmias.

1.5.2 Ischemia

This is a condition in which fatty deposits (cholesterol) accumulate in coronary arteries walls and restrict blood flow through them. This causes a reduction in blood flow and oxygen to the heart muscle usually manifested as chest pain (angina) commonly during effort when the heart muscle needs more blood flow. A blood clot can develop over these deposits causing complete obstruction of blood flow. This results in death of the cells supplied by this blood vessel and causes heart attack.

Ischemic heart disease is one of the most common causes of death in the industrialized world, as many as half of the death in North America and Europe are related to this group of diseases. Three different manifestations can be derived from ischemic heart disease:

1- angina pectoris: the least severe and defined as discomfort or chest pain.

2- myocardial infarction: ischemia results in necrosis (death) of a certain part of the myocardium. An infarction is often associated with pain, usually lasting from a few hours to a couple of days. For many patients who suffer from an infarction circulation is maintained and the only remaining sign is found in the ECG. For a small

percentage of these patients, a state of shock with pallor, coolness and low blood pressure occurs, in these cases mortality is around 70 %.

3-sudden cardiac death: is the most severe manifestation in which ventricular fibrillation causes mechanical failure of the heart. Chest massage and electrical defibrillation may terminate the defibrillation if applied within a few minutes.

1.5.2.1 How to diagnose ischemia

Coronary artery disease is diagnosed by its symptoms (angina) in patients who have the risk factors, e.g. family history, smoking, high blood pressure, diabetes, and increased blood cholesterol etc. The physician can further enhance the diagnosis by using non-invasive tests such as ECG at rest, ECG during supervised exercise (exercise treadmill test), and echocardiogram. A conclusive diagnosis can be achieved by an invasive test (cardiac catheterization). In this test a thin tube called catheter is inserted into a blood vessel in the groin or arm and guided into the coronary arteries. A dye is injected into the coronary arteries and a moving picture is taken by x-ray to clearly delineate the location and extent of narrowing in these arteries.

1.5.2.2 How to treat ischemia

-Prevention

It is more important to prevent coronary artery disease than to treat it once established. For this reason a good exercise program avoiding smoking and a healthy diet are the most important factors.

-Medical Treatment

Medications are given to increase blood flow through the narrow arteries and/or decrease the requirements of the heart muscle for increased blood supply by reducing its work. Other medicines to reduce blood cholesterol and prevent clot formation (Aspirin) are essential parts of medical treatment. Medical treatment must be combined with a well-balanced diet and exercise program. If medical treatment is not effective or a large part of the heart muscle is in jeopardy, one of the direct procedures to increase blood flow (described below) may be required.

-Balloon Angioplasty

This procedure is commonly known as Percutaneous Transluminal Coronary Angioplasty (PTCA). This is a non-surgical procedure in which a catheter is introduced into the coronary artery in the same fashion as described in diagnostic catheterization. The catheter passes through the narrow area of the artery and the balloon surrounding the catheter is inflated to open the artery. Other interventions can also be applied using the catheter e.g. placement of a stent to keep the artery patent, cutting and extracting cholesterol deposits by rotating blades (atherectomy), and use of laser to burn the cholesterol deposits.

-Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery

To increase blood flow in a coronary artery, a detour is created around its narrow or blocked part by sewing a segment taken from another blood vessel (vein or artery from an area other than the heart). One end of this piece is sewed before the narrowing and the other after this. The veins are taken from the legs and therefore patients who undergo surgery have scars on one or both legs. There is an increasing trend of using arterial segments rather than veins because they respond better to pulsatile blood flow of coronary arteries. This increases the longevity of the patency of these grafts. Sometimes PTCA or surgery may not give good results due to the bad quality of patients' own coronary arteries or they may carry increased risk due to poor function of the heart. In such cases, medical treatment might be a better option.

CHAPTER 2

ELECTROCARDIOGRAM SYSTEM

Introduction

Augustus Désiré Waller measured the human electrocardiogram in 1887 using Lippmann's *capillary electrometer* (Waller, 1887). He selected five electrode locations: the four extremities and the mouth (Waller, 1889). In this way it became possible to achieve a sufficiently low contact impedance and thus to maximize the ECG signal. Furthermore, the electrode location is unmistakably defined and the attachment of electrodes facilitated at the limb positions. The five measurement points produce altogether 10 different leads (see Fig. 2. 1. A). From these 10 possibilities he selected five - designated *cardinal leads*. Two of these are identical to the *Einthoven leads I and III* described below.

Willem Einthoven also used the capillary electrometer in his first ECG recordings. His essential contribution to ECG-recording technology was the development and application of the *string galvanometer*. Its sensitivity greatly exceeded the previously used capillary electrometer. The string galvanometer itself was invented by Clément Ader (Ader, 1897). In 1908 Willem Einthoven published a description of the first clinically important ECG measuring system (Einthoven, 1908). The above-mentioned practical considerations rather than bioelectric ones determined the Einthoven lead system, which is an application of the 10 leads of Waller. The Einthoven lead system is illustrated in Figure 2. 1. B.

Figure 2. 1. (A) The 10 ECG leads of Waller. (B) Einthoven limb leads and Einthoven triangle. The Einthoven triangle is an approximate description of the lead vectors associated with the limb leads.

The Einthoven *limb leads* (standard leads) are defined in the following way:

$$\text{Lead I: } V_I = \phi_L - \phi_R$$

$$\text{Lead II: } V_{II} = \phi_F - \phi_R \quad (2. 1)$$

$$\text{Lead III: } V_{III} = \phi_F - \phi_L$$

Where: V_I = the voltage of Lead I. V_{II} = the voltage of Lead II. V_{III} = the voltage of Lead III. ϕ_L = potential at the left arm. ϕ_R = potential at the right arm. ϕ_F = potential at the left foot.

(Left arm, right arm, and left leg (foot) are also represented with symbols LA, RA, and LL, respectively.)

According to Kirchhoff's law¹ (G. R. Kirchhoff 1847) these lead voltages have the following relationship:

$$V_I + V_{III} = V_{II} \quad (2. 2)$$

hence only two of these three leads are independent.

The lead vectors associated with Einthoven's lead system are conventionally found based on the assumption that the heart is located in an infinite, homogeneous volume conductor (or at the center of a homogeneous sphere representing the torso). One can show that if right arm, left arm, and left leg positions are at the vertices of an equilateral triangle with the heart located in its center, the lead vectors also form an equilateral triangle. A simple model results from assuming that the cardiac sources are represented by a dipole located in the center of a sphere representing the torso, hence in the center of the equilateral triangle. With these assumptions, the voltages measured by the three limb leads are proportional to the projections of the electric heart vector on the sides of the lead vector triangle, as described in Figure 2. 1. B. The voltages of the limb leads are obtained from Equation 2. 3, which is duplicated below (Einthoven, Fahr, and de Waart, 1913, 1950).

$$\begin{aligned} V_I &= p \cos(\alpha) = p_y \\ V_{II} &= \frac{p}{2} \cos(\alpha) - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} p \sin(\alpha) = \frac{1}{2} p_y - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} p_z = -0.5 p_y - 0.87 p_z \quad (2. 3) \\ V_{III} &= \frac{p}{2} \cos(\alpha) - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} p \sin(\alpha) = \frac{1}{2} p_y - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} p_z = -0.5 p_y - 0.87 p_z \end{aligned}$$

Substituting Equation 2.3 for Equation, 2.2, we can again demonstrate that Kirchhoff's law - that is, Equation 2. 2 - is satisfied, since we obtain:

$$V_I + V_{III} = \frac{p}{2} \cos(\alpha) - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} p \sin(\alpha) = V_{II} \quad (2. 4)$$

V_I , V_{II} , and V_{III} are oriented in the frontal plan and bipolar limb leads.

2.1 Wilson Central Terminal

Frank Norman Wilson (1890-1952) investigated how electrocardiographic *unipolar* potentials could be defined. Ideally, those are measured with respect to a remote reference (infinity). But how can it achieve this in the volume conductor of the human body size electrodes already placed at the extremities? In several articles about the subject, Wilson and colleagues (Wilson, Macleod, and Barker, 1931, Wilson et al., 1934) suggested the use of the *central terminal* as this reference. This was formed by connecting a 5 k Ω resistor from each terminal of the limb leads to a common point called the central terminal (CT), as shown in Figure 2. 2. Wilson suggested that unipolar potentials should be measured with regarding this terminal which approximates the potential to infinity.

Actually, the Wilson central terminal is not independent, but is the average of the limb potentials. This is easily demonstrated by noting that in an ideal voltmeter there is no lead current. Consequently, the total current into the central terminal from the limb leads must add to zero to satisfy the conservation of current (see Figure 2. 2). Accordingly, we require that:

$$L_R + L_L + L_F = \frac{\phi_{CT} - \phi_R}{5000} + \frac{\phi_{CT} - \phi_L}{5000} + \frac{\phi_{CT} - \phi_F}{5000} \quad (2. 5)$$

¹ The algebraic sum of the voltage drops in any closed path in a circuit and the electromotive forces in that path is equal to zero.

$$\phi_{CT} = \frac{\phi_R + \phi_L + \phi_F}{3}$$

Since the central terminal potential is the average of the extremity potentials it can be argued that then it does not depend on any of those in particular and therefore is a satisfactory reference. In clinical practice good reproducibility of the measurement system is vital. Results appear to be quite consistent in clinical applications. Wilson advocated 5 kΩ resistances; these are still widely used though, at present, the high-input ECG amplifiers impedance would allow much higher resistances. A higher resistance increases the CMRR and diminishes the artefact size introduced by the electrode/skin resistance. It's easy to show that in the image space the Wilson central terminal is found in the center of the Einthoven triangle, as shown in Figure 2. 3.

Figure 2. 2. Wilson central terminal (CT) is formed connecting a 5 kΩ resistance to each limb electrode and interconnecting the free wires, the CT is the common point. Wilson central terminal represents the average of the limb potentials. Because no current flows through a high-impedance voltmeter, Kirchoff's law requires that $I_R + I_L + I_F = 0$.

Figure 2. 3. (A) Wilson central terminal circuit (CT). **(B)** The location of the Wilson central terminal in the image space (CT'). It is located in the center of the Einthoven triangle.

2.2 Goldberger Augmented Leads

Three additional limb leads, V_R , V_L , and V_F are obtained by measuring the potential between each limb electrode and the Wilson central terminal. For instance the measurement from the left foot gives:

$$V_F = \phi_F - \phi_{CT} = \frac{2\phi_F - \phi_R - \phi_L}{3} \quad (2. 6)$$

In 1942 E. Goldberger observed how these signals can be augmented by omitting that resistance from the Wilson central terminal, connected to the measurement electrode (Goldberger, 1942 a and b). In this way, the aforementioned three leads may be replaced with a new set of leads that are called *augmented* leads because of the augmentation of the signal (see Figure 2.4). As an example, the equation for the augmented lead aV_F is:

$$V_{aVF} = \phi_F - \phi_{CT/aVF} = \phi_F - \frac{\phi_L + \phi_R}{2} = \frac{2\phi_F - \phi_L - \phi_R}{2} \quad (2. 7)$$

A comparison between Equation 2. 7 and Equation 2. 6 shows the augmented signal to be 50% larger than the signal chosen as reference by the Wilson central terminal. It is important to note that the three augmented leads,

aV_R , aV_L , and aV_F , are fully redundant with regarding to the limb leads I, II, and III. (This holds also for the three unipolar limb leads V_R , V_L , and V_F). Augmented unipolar limb leads are oriented in the frontal plane.

2.3 Precordial Leads

In order to measure the potentials close to the heart Wilson introduced the *precordial leads* (chest leads) in 1944 (Wilson et al., 1944). These leads, V_1 - V_6 are located over the left chest as described in Figure 2. 5. The points V_1 and V_2 are located in the fourth intercostal space on the sternum right and left side, V_4 is located in the fifth intercostal space at the midclavicular line, V_3 is located between the points V_2 and V_4 , V_5 is found at the same horizontal level as V_4 but on the anterior axillary line, V_6 is found at the same horizontal level as V_4 but at the midline. These leads are oriented in the horizontal plane.

Figure 2. 4. (A) The circuit of the Goldberger augmented leads. (B) The location of the Goldberger augmented lead vectors in the image space.

Figure 2. 5. Precordial leads.

2.4 Modification of the 12-Lead System

The 12-lead system as described here is the one with the greatest clinical use. There are also some other modifications of the 12-lead system for particular applications.

In exercise ECG, the signal is distorted because of muscular activity, respiration, and electrode artifacts due to perspiration and electrode movements. The distortion due to muscular activation can be minimized by placing the electrodes on the shoulders and on the hip instead of the arms and the leg, as suggested by R. E. Mason and I. Likar (1966). The Mason-Likar modification is the most important modification of the 12-lead system used in exercise ECG.

The accurate location of the right arm electrode in the Mason-Likar modification is a point in the infraclavicular fossa medial to the border of the deltoid muscle and 2 cm below the lower border of the clavicle. The left arm electrode is located similarly on the left side. The left leg electrode is placed at the left iliac crest. The right leg electrode is placed in the region of the right iliac fossa. The precordial leads are located in the Mason-Likar modification in the standard places of the 12-lead system.

In ambulatory monitoring of the ECG, as in the Holter recording, the electrodes are also placed on the surface of the thorax instead of the extremities.

Note: next part of this chapter gives a summary of the normal and abnormal ECG cases with the corresponding diagnostic situations, and it was obtained from some parts of the cardiology literature that pertain the electrocardiography (Goldman

MJ (1986), Macfarlane PW, and Lawrie TDV (1989), Nelson CV, and Geselowitz DB (1976), Pilkington TC, and Plonsey R (1982), Scheidt S (1983), Scheidt S (1984).

2.5 Orientation of the 12 Lead ECG

It is important to remember that the 12- lead ECG provides spatial information about the heart's electrical activity in 3 approximately orthogonal directions: right- left, superior-inferior, and anterior- posterior. Each of the 12 leads represents a particular orientation in space as follows:

- **Bipolar limb leads (frontal plane)**
 - Lead I: RA(-) to LA(+), right left or lateral.
 - Lead II: RA(-) to LF(+), superior inferior.
 - Lead III LA(-) to LF(+), superior inferior.
- **Augmented unipolar limb leads (frontal plane)**
 - Lead aVR: RA(+) to [LA&LF](-), rightward.
 - Lead aVL: LA(+)to [RA&LF](-), leftward.
 - Lead aVF : LF(+) to [RA&LA](-), inferior.
- **Unipolar(+) chest leads (horizontal plane)**
 - Leads V1,V2,V3: posterior anterior
 - Leads V4,V5,V6: right left or lateral

where RA,LA, and LF are the right arm, left arm and left foot respectively, and each of the 6 frontal plane leads has a negative and positive orientation (as indicated by '+' and '-' signs). See Figure 2. 6.

Figure 2. 6. Frontal plane leads orientation.

Figure 2. 7. The normal electrocardiogram.

2.6 Characteristics of a Normal 12 Leads ECG.

There is a wide range of normal variability in the 12 lead ECG. The following normal ECG characteristics, therefore, are not absolute. It takes considerable ECG reading experience to discover all the normal variants, and correlating the various ECG findings with the particular patient's clinical status, in order to interpretate the ECG. In the following paragraph we explain the features of a normal ECG. Figure 2. 7 illustrates a normal ECG.

2.6.1 Heart rate: is the number of beats in one minute of time, in the normal case, the heart rate must be between 60 and 90 beats per minute (bpm).

2.6.2 Wave form description

- **P wave:** represents the sequential activation of the right and left atria, and it is common to see notched or biphasic P waves of right and left atrial activation. P duration is < than 0.12 sec, P amplitude is < than 0.25 mV, and in the frontal plane P wave axis is between 0° and +75°.

- **QRS complex:** represents the simultaneous activation of the right and left ventricles, although most of the QRS waveform is derived from the larger left ventricle musculature. QRS duration is ≤ 0.10 sec, and QRS amplitude is quite variable from lead to lead and from person to person. Two determinants of QRS voltages are: firstly the ventricular chambers size (the larger is the chamber, the larger is the voltage), and secondly the proximity of chest electrodes to ventricular chamber (the closer, the larger the voltage). In the frontal plane leads the normal QRS axis range (+90° to -30°), this implies that the QRS be mostly positive (upright) in leads II and I.

Normal Q-waves reflect normal septal activation, they are narrow (<0.04 s duration) and small (<25% the amplitude of Rwave). They are seen in the leads I and aVL when the QRS axis is to the left of +60°, and in leads II, III, aVF when the QRS axis is to the right of +60°, small “septal” Q-waves may be seen in leads V5 and V6. Small R-waves begin in V1 or V2 and progress in the size to V5. The R-V6 is usually smaller than R-V5. In inverse the S-waves begin in V6 or V5 and progress in size to V2. S-V1 is usually smaller than S-V2.

- **ST Segment and T Wave** ST segment is a misnomer, because a discrete ST segment distinct from the T wave is usually absent. More often the ST-T wave is a smooth, continues wave form beginning with the J-point (end of QRS), slowly rising to the peak of the T and followed by rapid descent to the isoelectric baseline. This originates an asymmetrical T wave. In some normal individuals, particularly women, the T wave is symmetrical and a distinct, horizontal ST segment is present. The normal T wave is usually in the same direction as QRS except in the right precordial leads. In the normal ECG the T wave is always upright in leads I,II,V3-6, and inverted in lead aVR where normal ST segment elevation occurs in leads with large S-wave (e.g., V1-V3), and the normal configuration is concave upward. ST segment with concave upwards appearance may also be seen in other leads, this is often called early repolarization, although it's a term with little physiologic meaning. Convex or straight upward ST segment elevation (e.g., leads II, III, aVF) is abnormal and suggests transmural injury or infarction. ST segment depression is always an abnormal finding, and often indicates an ischemic abnormality.

2.6.3 ECG intervals

- 1- **RR:** is the ventricular cardiac cycle duration (an indicator of ventricular rate).
- 2- **PP:** is the atrial cycle duration (an indicator of atrial rate).
- 3- **PR:** is the interval measured from the atrial depolarization onset (p-wave) to the ventricular depolarization onset (QRS complex). In a normal ECG, it is in the range 0.12- 0.2 sec.
- 4- **QRS duration :** is the ventricular muscle depolarization duration. In a normal ECG, it is usually in the range 0.06- 0.10 sec.
- 5- **QT:** is the ventricular depolarization and repolarization duration, in the normal status QT was determined, QT has an upper limit at 70 bpm, so it must be ≤ 0.40 sec, for every 10 bpm increase above 70 subtract 0.02 sec, and for every 10 bpm decrease below 70 add 0.02 sec. For example (QT $\leq 0.38s$ @ 80 bpm, and $\leq 0.42s$ @ 60 bpm). Bazett gave a formula to calculate the critical QT interval from the measured on, and the RR interval as follows:

$$QT_c = \frac{QT_m}{\sqrt{RR}} \quad (2.8)$$

where QT_c, QT_m, RR are critical QT, measured QT, and RR interval respectively.

2.7 Characteristics of an Abnormal 12 Leads ECG:

2.7.1 Heart arrhythmia: In normal sinus rhythm, a resting heart rate of below 60 bpm is called bradycardia and a rate of above 90 bpm is called tachycardia. Arrhythmias may be seen on 12-lead ECGs or on strips of one or more leads. Some arrhythmias are obvious at first glance and don't require intense analysis. Others, however, require detective work, i.e., logical thinking based on a knowledge of cardiac electrophysiology. The analysis should begin with identifying characteristics of *impulse formation* (if known) as well as *impulse conduction*. Here there are some things to think about:

- **Descriptors of impulse formation:** it means determine the pacemaker, or the region of impulse formation. Three main questions must be done here: where is the abnormal rhythm coming from? What is the expected rate? And how many atrial and ventricular responses are regulars?

- I. Site of origin: may be the sinus node (e.g., sinus tachycardia or atrial fibrillation . See Figure 2. 8), the atria (e.g., premature atrial conduction PAC. See Figure 2. 9), the AV junction (e.g., junctional escape rhythm. See Figure 2. 10), or the ventricles (e.g., premature ventricular conduction PVC. See Figure 2. 11).

Figure 2. 8. Atrial fibrillation, HR(A:350 bpm, V slow to rapid).

Figure 2. 9. Premature atrial conduction PAC.

Figure 2. 10. Premature Junctional conduction PJC.

Figure 2. 11. Premature ventricular conduction PVC.

- II. Heart rate: if it accelerated – faster than expected (e.g., accelerated junctional rhythm @ 75bpm), Slower than expected (e.g., marked sinus bradycardia @ 40bpm), or Normal (e.g., junctional escape rhythm).
 - III. Ventricular or atrial regularity response: the irregularity may be caused by ventricular bigeminy, atrial fibrillation, or multifocal PVCs).
- **Descriptors of impulse conduction:** how abnormal rhythm conducts through the heart? The impulse may be antegrade (forward), or retrograde (backward). The abnormal rhythm conduction may be caused from the sino-atrial, intra-atrial, atrio-ventricular(AV blocks), or intra-ventricular(e.g., bundle branch or fascicular blocks) blocks. The most common is the AV block explained in the next paragraph. In the following paragraphs we will show examples of intra-ventricular blocks.

2.7.2 PR interval:

- **The short PR below 0.12 sec (preexcitation syndromes):**

- I. WPW(Wolff-Parkinson-White) syndrome: an accessory pathway(called the “Kent” bundle) connects the right atrium to the right ventricle, or the left atrium to the left ventricle, and this permits the early ventricles activation (delta wave in the ECG), and short PR interval. See Figure 2. 12.
- II. LGL (Lown-Ganong-Levine) syndrom: an AV nodal bypass track into the His bundle exists, and this permits an early ventricles activation without a delta wave because the ventricle activation sequence is normal.
- III. AV Junctional Rhythm: retrograde P wave may occur before the QRS complex, in the QRS complex (hidden from view), or after the QRS complex. Here inverted P waves in II, III, and aVF take place.
- IV. Ectopic atrial rhythms: originated near the AV node. In this case PR interval is very short because atrial activation originates close to the AV node. Here the P wave is different from the sinus P.

Figure 2. 12. Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome.

Figure 2. 13. 2° degree AV cardiac blocks: **A:** Wenckebach, and **B:** Mobitz.

- **Prolonged PR above 0.2 sec**

- I. First degree AV block (PR interval usually constant) : may be caused by an intra-atrial conduction delay, slowed conduction in AV node, slowed conduction in HIS bundle, or slowed conduction in the bundle branch which is most common.
- II. Second degree AV block: here PR interval may be normal or prolonged, but some P waves are not conducted. This syndrome has two types: in the first (called “ Wenckebach”) the PR interval is increasing until non-conducted P wave occurs. In the second one (called “Mobitz”) there are fixed PR intervals and non-conducted P waves. See Figure 2. 13.
- III. AV dissociation : some PR may be prolonged, but the P waves and QRS complexes are dissociated. See Figure 2. 14.

Figure 2. 14. 3° degree cardiac block.

2.7.3 QRS duration

- I. QRS duration 0.1- 0.12 may be caused by an incomplete right or left bundle branch block (RBBB, LBBB respectively. See Figure 2.15), non-specific intraventricular conduction delay, or some cases of left anterior or posterior fascicular block. Figures 2.16.A and 2.16.B illustrate an example of ECG signal in the left anterior and posterior fascicular block cases respectively.
- II. QRS duration ≥ 0.12 sec may be caused by a complete right or left bundle branch block (see Figure 2.15.A), non-specific intraventricular conduction delay, or an ectopic rhythms originated in the ventricles (e.g., tachycardia, paced rhythm, or premature ventricle conduction PVC).

Figure 2. 15. Bundle branch blocks, **A:** left bundle branch block, and **B:** right bundle branch block.

Figure 2. 16. Left ventricular blocks **A:** left anterior fascicular block, **B:** left posterior fascicular block.

2.7.4 QT interval

The long QT interval abnormality is ≥ 0.47 for males and ≥ 0.48 for females. This abnormality may have an important clinical implication, since it usually indicates a state of increased vulnerability to malignant ventricular arrhythmias, syncope, and sudden death. The prototype arrhythmia of the long QT interval syndromes is a polymorphic ventricular tachycardia characterized by varying QRS morphology and amplitude around the isoelectric baseline. The causes of the long QT interval are:

- I. Drugs (many antiarrhythmics, tricyclics, phenothiazines, and others).
- II. Electrolyte abnormalities ($\downarrow K^+$, $\downarrow Ca^{++}$, $\downarrow Mg^{++}$).
- III. CNS diseases (especially subarachnoid² haemorrhage, stroke, and trauma).
- IV. Hereditary.
- V. Coronary heart diseases (e.g., some post- myocardial infarction patients).

Frontal plane QRS axis

- **Left axis deviation ≥ -30 (i.e., lead II is mostly negative):** it may be caused from:

² Is the compartment within the spinal column which contains the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF).

- I. Left anterior fascicular block: in this case we note rS complex in lead II, III, aVF, small q in lead I and /or aVL, and axis from -45 to -90
 - II. Inferior myocardial infarction with Qr complex in lead II (making lead II negative).
 - III. Inferior myocardial infarction + Left anterior fascicular block with QS or qrS complex in lead II.
 - IV. Some case of left ventricular hypertrophy.
 - V. Some case of left bundle branch.
 - VI. Some cases of Wolff-Parkinson-White and a large negative delta wave in lead II.
 - VII. Ostium primum³ and other endocardial cushion defects.
- **Right axis deviation $\geq +90$ (i.e., lead I is mostly negative):** it may be caused from:
- I. Left posterior fascicular block : here we note rS complex in lead I, qR in lead II, III, aVF.
 - II. Many cases of right heart overload and pulmonary hypertention.
 - III. High lateral wall myocardial infarction with Qr or QS complex in leads I and aVL.
 - IV. Some cases of right bundle branch block.
 - V. Some cases of Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome.

Figure 2. 17. Right axis deviation.

Figure 2. 18. Left axis deviation.

- **Bizarre QRS axis: $+150$ to -90 (i.e., lead I and lead II are both negative)** it may be caused by:
- I. Consider limb error (usually right and left arm universal).
 - II. Dextrocardia⁴.
 - III. Some cases of complex congenital heart disease.
 - IV. Some cases of ventricular tachycardia.

2.7.5 ST segment and T wave abnormalities

The basic Concept is the *specificity* of ST-T wave abnormalities. The specificity is provided more by the clinical circumstances in which the ECG changes are found than by the particular changes themselves. Thus the term, *nonspecific ST-T wave abnormalities*, is frequently used when the clinical data are not available to correlate with the ECG findings. This does not mean that the ECG changes are unimportant! It is the responsibility of the clinician providing care for the patient to ascertain the importance of the ECG findings. There are many factors affecting the ST-T configuration include:

³The anterior leaflet of the mitral valve is bifid, resulting in incompetence.

⁴Is an anomaly in which the primitive heart tube folds to the left in a mirror image of a normal bulboventricular loop. This usually occurs when all the organ systems are reversed, a condition called *situs inversus*.

- I. Intrinsic myocardial disease (e.g., myocarditis, ischemia, infarction, infiltrative or myopathic processes).
- II. Drugs (e.g., digoxin, quinidine, tricyclics, and many others).
- III. Electrolyte abnormalities of potassium, magnesium, calcium.
- IV. Neurogenic factors (e.g., stroke, hemorrhage, trauma, tumor, etc.).
- V. Metabolic factors (e.g., hypoglycemia, hyperventilation).
- VI. Atrial repolarization (e.g., at fast heart rates the atrial T wave may pull down the beginning of the ST segment).
- VII. Ventricular conduction abnormalities and rhythms originating in the ventricles.

The ST-T wave changes independent on changes in ventricular activation, and that may be the result of global or segmental pathologic processes that affect ventricular repolarization:

- I. Drug effects (e.g., digoxin, quinidine, etc).
- II. Electrolyte abnormalities (e.g., hypokalemia).
- III. Ischemia, infarction, inflammation, etc.
- IV. Neurogenic effects (e.g., subarachnoid hemorrhage causing long QT).

The ST-T Wave changes that are normal ST-T wave changes solely due to alterations in the sequence of ventricular activation:

- I. ST-T changes seen in bundle branch blocks (generally the ST-T polarity is opposite to the major or terminal deflection of the QRS).
- II. ST-T changes seen in fascicular block.
- III. ST-T changes seen in nonspecific individual ventricular conduction delays.
- IV. ST-T changes seen in Wolff- Parkinson- White preexcitation.
- V. T changes in PVCs, ventricular arrhythmias, and ventricular paced beats.

ST-T abnormalities are:

- **The ST Segment elevation:** may be caused from:

- I. Normal Variant "Early Repolarization" (usually concave upwards, ending with symmetrical, large, upright T waves). See Figure 2. 19 , note high take off of the ST segment in leads V4-6, the ST elevation in V2-3 is generally seen in most normal ECG's, the ST elevation in V2-6 is concave upwards.
- II. Ischemic Heart Disease (usually convex upwards, or straightened): like as Acute transmural injury - as in this acute anterior myocardial infarction, Persistent ST elevation after acute myocardial infarction suggests ventricular aneurysm, ST elevation may also be seen as a manifestation of Prinzmetal's (variant) angina (coronary artery spasm), and ST elevation during exercise testing suggests extremely tight coronary artery stenosis or spasm (transmural ischemia).
- III. Acute Pericarditis: that may be presented in the ECG as a concave upwards ST elevation in most leads except aVR, unlike "early repolarization" so the T waves have usually low amplitude, and the heart rate is usually increased, No reciprocal ST segment depression (except in aVR), or may see PR segment depression, a manifestation of atrial injury.

IV. Other Causes: as Left ventricular hypertrophy (in right precordial leads with large S-waves), Left bundle branch block (in right precordial leads with large S-waves), Advanced hyperkalemia⁵, hypothermia⁶ (prominent J-waves or Osborne waves).

- **The ST Segment depression:** ST segment depression is often characterized as horizontal, upsloping, or upsloping. See Figure 2. 20. This abnormality may be caused from:

I. Normal variants or artifacts: that may be Pseudo-ST-depression (wandering baseline due to poor skin-electrode contact), Physiologic J-junctional depression with sinus tachycardia (most likely due to atrial repolarization), or Hyperventilation-induced ST segment depression.

II. Ischemic heart disease : like us Subendocardial ischemia (exercise induced or during angina attack - as illustrated in Figure 2. 21 , note the horizontal" ST depression in lead V6) .

Figure 2. 19. normal variant of ST segment.

Figure 2. 20. ST segment depression.

Figure 2. 21. Ischemic heart disease.

⁵ Means an abnormally elevated level of potassium in the blood

⁶ Is a decrease in the core body temperature to a level at which normal muscular and cerebral functions are impaired.

**CHAPTER
3****DISTORTION FACTORS IN THE ECG****Introduction**

As we have seen in the precedent chapters ECG signal represents an extremely important measure for cardiologists, as it provides vital information about a patient's cardiac condition.

ECG signal may be corrupted from different kinds of noise that generating errors by distorting the signal during the diagnosis. This problem was very well studied in the literature, and many attempts were done in order to filter the corrupted or noisy ECG, and recognize its diagnostic parameters. Generally, the frequency band of the ECG is about 0.05-100 Hz. And that of the QRS is about 5-15 Hz. It isn't difficult to filter the ECG when the noise frequency band is outside its range, but the task becomes more complex if the noise overlap the interest signal.

In this chapter we study the types of noise present in the ECG signal which may effect in the detection of various characteristics of the signal such as the QRS complexes, T and P waves. The various considered noise types were electromyographic interference, 50Hz power line interference, base line drift due to respiration, abrupt base line shifts, and a composite noise constructed from all of the other noise types.

3.1 Effect of the Inhomogeneity of The Thorax

As discussed before it is assumed that in the standard 12-lead ECG system the source is a dipole in a fixed location and the volume conductor is either infinite homogeneous or spherical homogeneous. If this is the case, the lead vectors of the 12 leads form a symmetric star model. However, this is not the case; rather, the thorax includes several inhomogeneities, and the shape of the thorax is not spherical. These facts have a considerable effect on the directions and magnitudes of the lead vectors. This effect has been discussed in many publications. In the following part of the data from a study of Jari Hyttinen (1989, 1993a,b) is presented. Hyttinen constructed a computer model from the transfer impedance data of a physical torso model constructed by Stanley Rush (1975). The computer model used a cubic spline fitting of the data to interpolate the lead vectors for all points of the thorax surface in relation to all points within the heart area. The real values of the 12 lead vectors of the standard 12-lead system were calculated with this model. The result is illustrated in Figure 3. 1. It is apparent that the biggest errors are the very high sensitivities of the leads V2 and V3 as well as the form of the enhancement of the vertical forces in the frontal plane. The frontal plane is also tilted backwards. These effects are similar to those obtained from the image surface of the finite, homogeneous torso model of Frank.

3.2 Brody Effect**3.2.1 Description of the Brody effect**

Daniel Brody investigated the intracardiac blood mass effect on the ECG lead field (Brody, 1956). The intracardiac blood resistivity is about $1.6 \Omega \text{ m}$ and the cardiac muscle averagingm one about $5.6 \Omega \text{ m}$. The heart is surrounded almost everywhere by the lungs whose resistivity is about $10\text{-}20 \Omega \text{ m}$.

From the above data one notes that the conductivity increases about 10-fold from the lungs to the intracardiac blood mass. Therefore, the lead field current path tends to include the well-conducting intracardiac

blood mass. Consequently, the lead field bends from the linear direction of the homogeneous model to the radial direction, as illustrated in Figure 3. 2. As a consequence, the ECG lead is more sensitive to radial than tangential dipole elements, in contrast to the homogeneous model which predicts that the sensitivity is uniform and unrelated to gross myocardial anatomy. This phenomenon is called the *Brody effect*. The Brody effect is, in fact, more complicated than described above, as reported by Van Oosterom and Plonsey (1991).

Figure 3. 1. The lead vectors of the standard 12-lead ECG in a finite, homogeneous torso model calculated from the model of Hyttinen (1989; 1993). Compare with the idealized lead vectors.

3.2.2 Effect of the ventricular volume

R. W. Millard performed an interesting series of experiments to show the Brody effect on the ECG signal (Voukydis, 1974). He recorded the x, y, and z signals from a dog using the Nelson lead system and calculated the magnitude and the two angles of the electric heart vector in spherical coordinates. The result is shown in Figure 3. 3.

These investigators noted that during the QRS-complex the electric heart vector exhibits three different peaks, which they named M_1 , M_2 , and M_3 . It is known that from these, the peaks M_1 and M_2 arise mainly from radial electric forces and the peak M_3 arises mainly from tangential forces (though, unfortunately, they did not confirm this interpretation with intramural source measurements).

Millard modified the extent of the Brody effect by changing the volume of the left ventricle during the QRS-complex by removing blood with a catheter. As a consequence, the M_2 peak decreased and the M_3 peak increased. The effect was stronger as more blood was removed from the ventricle, as can be seen in Figure 3. 4.

These experimental results are easy to explain. As mentioned, the M_2 peak is formed from radial electric forces, which are enhanced by the Brody effect. If this effect is attenuated by venesection, the corresponding peak is attenuated. The peak M_3 is formed from tangential forces, which are attenuated by the Brody effect. If the Brody effect is reduced by venesection, the corresponding M_3 signal will be less attenuated (i.e., increased in magnitude).

Figure 3. 2. The Brody effect. The spherical volume represents the more highly conducting intracavitary blood mass. Its effect on an applied uniform lead field shows an increased sensitivity to radial and decreased sensitivity to tangential dipoles in the heart muscle region.

Figure 3. 3. The electric heart vector of a dog in the consistent orthogonal and spherical coordinates (M = magnitude, E = elevation angle, A = azimuth angle).

3.2.3 Effect of the blood resistivity

Nelson et al. investigated the Brody effect yet in another way (Nelson et al., 1972). They changed the resistivity of blood by changing its hematocrit. In this way they were able to vary the resistivity from half normal to four times normal. The latter corresponds to the average resistivity of heart muscle.

When the blood resistivity was decreased to half-normal value, the Brody effect increased and consequently the M_2 peak, which is believed to correspond to the radial part of the activation, also increased. The M_3 peak, corresponding to the tangential part of the activation, decreased. When the resistivity was increased fourfold, the opposite effect was produced on the electric heart vector, as expected (see Figure 3. 5). Note that in the latter case the Brody effect should not arise, and the lead fields should be less distorted since the nominal intracavitary and muscle resistivities are equal. However, since the cardiac muscle is anisotropic, these ideas are only approximate.

Figure 3. 4. The effect of decreasing the ventricular volume on the electric heart vector amplitude. LVED = left ventricular end-diastolic.

Figure 3. 5. The effect of blood resistivity on the magnitude of the electric heart vector.

3.2.4 Integrated effects

More recent investigations of inhomogeneities effect have been based on model investigations. Rudy (Rudy, Plonsey, and Liebman, 1979) used an eccentric spheres model of the heart and thorax in which the lungs, pericardium, body surface muscle and fat, as well as intracavitary blood could be represented. Some conclusions reached from this study include the following:

1. Although the Brody effect of the intracavitary blood is clearly demonstrated, the effect is diminished, when the remaining inhomogeneities are included.
2. Both abnormally low and high lung conductivities reduce the magnitude of surface potentials.
3. Low skeletal muscle conductivity enhances the surface potentials.
4. Increasing heart conductivity results in an increase in body surface potentials.

Other investigators have used realistic models of torso, lungs, heart, etc. to determine the effect of inhomogeneities. Gulrajani and Mailloux (1983) showed that the introduction of inhomogeneities in their model simulation of body surface potentials results in a smoothing of the contours without a large change in the pattern. Because of the predominant endocardial to epicardial activation, they noted a very significant Brody effect. In addition to the spatial filtering noted above, these investigations also reported temporal filtering of the ECG signal.

3.3 Effect of Respiration

Both the lungs resistivity and position change during respiration. The heart orientation and location also change during the respiratory cycle. Ruttkay-Nedeck described certain cyclic changes in the measured electric heart vector to be the consequence of respiration (Ruttkay-Nedeck, 1971). Figure 3. 6 illustrates the change of the QRS- and T-vector magnitudes between midrespiration and full inspiration. Data was pooled from seven healthy male subjects using McFee-Parungao (axial) leads. Statistically significant changes ($p > .05$) exist only in the mid-part of the QRS-complex.

Figure 3. 7 shows the effect of inspiration on the electric heart vector elevation compared to the midrespiration state. The effect is statistically significant only at 1/10 the normalized QRS-complex duration.

Figure 3. 6. The effect of inspiration on the electric heart vector during the QRS-complex and ST-T-wave. The ordinate plots the difference in magnitude [mV] between heart vector magnitude determined in midrespiration and full inspiration. See that the QRS- or ST-T-interval divided into 10 equal points (so that the corresponding waveforms are time-normalized).

Figure 3. 7. Effect of inspiration on the elevation angle of the time normalized heart vector for the QRS-complex and T-wave (top and bottom, respectively). See that the QRS- or ST-T-interval divided into 10 equal points (so that the corresponding waveforms are time-normalized).

A drift of the baseline with respiration can be represented by a sinusoidal component at the frequency of respiration added to the ECG signal. The amplitude and frequency of the sinusoidal are variables, the effect of the respiration is shown in Figure 3. 8.

3.4 Motion Artifacts and the Effect of Electrode Location

Motion artifacts are transient baseline changes caused by changes in the electrode-skin impedance with electrode motion. As this impedance changes the ECG amplifier sees a different source impedance which forms a voltage divider with the amplifier input impedance, therefore the amplifier input voltage depends on the source impedance which changes as the electrode position changes. The usual cause of motion artifacts will be assumed to be variations or movements of the subjects. The peak amplitude and duration of the artifact are variable, as illustrated in Figure 3. 9 This type of interference represents an abrupt shift in baseline due to movement of the patient while the ECG is being recorded.

Figure 3. 8. Respiration effect presented in a trace of ECG signal.

Figure 3. 9. Motion artifact presented in a trace of ECG signal.

Simonson et al. investigated the effect of electrode displacement on the QRS-complex when recorded by SVEC III, Frank, and McFee vectorcardiographic systems (Simonson et al., 1966). In the first test, in the SVEC III, Frank and McFee systems, the electrode V3 was displaced 2 cm down, all electrodes were displaced 2 cm down and the distance between electrodes A and B (on the left side) was changed from 11 cm to 9 cm, respectively. In the second test, all electrodes were moved 2 cm up, the C electrode was moved 2 cm up and the A and B electrodes were moved 2 cm up, respectively. The results are shown in Figure 3. 10. The authors concluded that SVEC III was least sensitive and Frank most sensitive to electrode displacement. In addition, the displacement error depend on the body shape.

Another type of noise or a transient interference caused by the loss of contact between the electrode and the skin that effectively disconnects the measurement system from the subject. The loss of contact can be permanent, or intermittent as would be the case when a loose electrode is brought in and out of contact with the skin as a result of movements and vibration. This switching action at the measurement system input can result in large artifacts since the ECG signal is usually capacitively coupled to the system.

3.5 Artifact of Muscle Contraction

Muscle contractions cause artifactual millivolt level potentials to be generated. The baseline electromyogram is usually in the microvolt range and therefore is usually insignificant. It is simulated by adding a random noise to the ECG signal. The maximum noise level is formed by adding random signal precision numbers of $\pm 50\%$ of the ECG maximum amplitude to the uncorrupted ECG. A plot of the ECG corrupted by electromyographic noise is given in the Figure 3. 11.

Figure 3. 10. Effect of electrode location on the VCG signal.

Figure 3. 11. Artifact of muscle contraction presented in a trace of ECG signal.

Figure 3. 12. Power line interference superimposed on a trace of ECC signal.

3.6 Power Line Interference:

It consists of 50-60 Hz pickup and harmonics, which can be modelled as sinusoid. Characteristics which might need to be varied in a model of power line noise, of 60 Hz component (as most of the signals of study were digitized in USA) include the amplitude and frequency content of the signal. The amplitude varies up to 50 % of the peak to peak ECG amplitude. It is shown in the Figure 3. 12.

**CHAPTER
4****ECG SIGNAL PROCESSING****Introduction**

Digital Signal Processing (DSP) is one of the most powerful technologies that will shape science and engineering in the twenty-first century. Revolutionary changes have already been made in a broad range of fields: communications, medical signal & imaging, radar sonar, high fidelity music reproduction, and oil prospecting, to name just a few. Each of these areas developed a deep DSP technology, with its own algorithms, mathematics, and specialized techniques. This combination of breadth and depth makes it impossible for any one individual to master all of the DSP technology that has been developed. DSP education involves two tasks: learning general concepts that apply to the field as a whole, and learning specialized techniques for our particular area of interest. This chapter starts our journey in the world of Digital Signal Processing by describing the effect that DSP has made in ECG signal processing field.

ECG signal as we have cited in the precedent chapter, may be corrupted by different types of noise that are diverse in nature. It expands over a range of frequency from about 1 to 100 Hz. Every component of the ECG signal may have a certain characteristic in the plane of frequency that diversifies it from another one. For example QRS complex has a frequency band from about 5 to 15 Hz. This is the reason that in the ECG signal filtering literature the filter designers would deal with both frequency and time domains simultaneously. So firstly they deal with the frequency domain in order to separate the most recognizable component in the ECG, the QRS complex. Then the procedure continues in the time domain to perfects the features extraction process. In addition, in order to distinguish well the noisy ECG signal, many filters in the time domain were proposed in the literature in order to reduce or, sometimes, eliminate completely the effect of diverse noise types, especially the one which overlap the ECG frequencies. Lately in this thesis we propose a method to attain this aim.

4.1 Digital Filters

In signal processing, the function of a filter is to remove unwanted parts of the signal, as random noise, or to extract useful parts of the signal, as the components lying within a certain frequency range. There are two main kinds of filter, analog and digital. They are quite different in their physical makeup and their way to work. An *analog* filter uses analog electronic circuits made up of components as resistors, capacitors and op amps to produce the required filtering effect. Such filter circuits are widely used in these applications as noise reduction, video signal enhancement, graphic equalisers in hi-fi systems, and many other areas. There are well-established standard techniques for designing an analog filter circuit for a given requirement. At all stages, the signal being filtered is an electrical voltage or current which is the direct analogue of the physical quantity (e.g. a sound or video signal or transducer output) involved.

A *digital* filter uses a digital processor to perform numerical calculations on sampled values of the signal. The processor may be a general-purpose computer such as a PC, or a specialised DSP (Digital Signal Processor) chip. The analog input signal must first be sampled and digitated using an ADC (analog to digital converter) .The following block diagram (Figure 4. 1) illustrates the basic idea. The resulting binary numbers, representing successive sampled values of the input signal, are transferred to the processor, which carries out numerical

calculations on them. These calculations typically involve multiplying the input values by constants and adding the products together. If necessary, the results of these calculations, which now represent sampled values of the filtered signal, are output through a DAC (digital to analog converter) to convert the signal back to analog form. Note that in a digital filter, the signal is represented by a sequence of numbers, rather than a voltage or current. The following list gives some of the main advantages of digital over analog filters:

1. A digital filter is programmable, i.e. its operation is determined by a program stored in the processor's memory. It means that the digital filter can easily be changed without affecting the circuitry (hardware). An analog filter can only be changed by redesigning the filter circuit.
2. Digital filters are easily designed, tested and implemented on a general-purpose computer or workstation.
3. The characteristics of analog filter circuits (particularly those containing active components) are subject to drift and are dependent on temperature. Digital filters do not suffer from these problems, and so are extremely stable with respect both to time and temperature.
4. Unlike their analog counterparts, digital filters can handle low frequency signals accurately. As the speed of DSP technology continues to increase, digital filters are being applied to high frequency signals in the RF (radio frequency) domain, which in the past was the exclusive preserve of analog technology.
5. Digital filters are much more versatile in their abilities to process signals in a variety of ways, this includes the ability of some types of digital filter to adapt to changes in the characteristics of the signal.
6. Fast DSP processors can handle complex combinations of filters in parallel or cascade (series), making the hardware requirements relatively simple and compact in comparison with the equivalent analog circuitry.

Figure 4. 1. The system of the digital filter.

Analogue or digital filters are widely applied in order to reduce the influence of interference superimposed on the ECG. Especially the digital filter, that performs very well when the spectra of the signal and noise are not significantly overlap. For example a low- pass filter with a 100 Hz cut of frequency generally works well to attenuate noise frequencies better than 100 Hz in ECG signal. However, if high level noise frequencies were to span the frequency range from 50-100 Hz, attempting to remove them using a 50 Hz low-pass filter would attenuate some of the components of the ECG signal as well as the noise. High amplitude noise corruption within the frequency band of the signal may completely obscure the signal. Thus, conventional filtering schemes fail when the signal and noise frequency spectra significantly overlap. Many digital techniques were proposed in the literature to separate the ECG signal from the superimposed noise. In this chapter we are going to explain in details the famous and most important proposed methods in order to reduce the artifact and the noise superimposed on the ECG and facilitate the automatic detection of the ECG components (QRS complex and P,T, waves).

4.1.1 Operation of digital filters

In this section, we explain the basic theory of the operation of digital filters. This is essential to understanding how digital filters are designed and used. Suppose the "raw" signal which is to be digitally filtered is in the form of a voltage waveform described by the function $V = X(t)$, where t is the time. This signal is sampled at time intervals h (the sampling interval). The sampled value at time $t = ih$ is $x_i = x(ih)$. Thus the digital values transferred from the ADC to the processor can be represented by the sequence $[x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots]$ corresponding to the values of the signal wave form at $[t = 0, h, 2h, 3h, \dots]$, and $t = 0$ is the instant at which sampling begins.

At time $t = nh$ (where n is some positive integer), the values available to the processor are $[x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n]$. The digital output from the processor to the DAC consists of the sequence of values $[y_0, y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots, y_n]$. In general, the value of y_n is calculated from the values $[x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n]$.

The way in which the y 's are calculated from the x 's determines the filtering action of the digital filter.

4.1.2 Recursive and non-recursive filters

For all the examples of digital filters formerly discussed, the current output (y_n) is calculated solely from the current and previous input values ($x_n, x_{n-1}, x_{n-2}, \dots$) This type of filter is said to be *non-recursive*.

A *recursive* filter is the one which in addition to input values also uses previous *output* values. These, like the previous input values, are stored in the processor's memory. The word *recursive* literally means "running back", and refers to the fact that previously-calculated output values that go back into the calculation of the latest output. The expression for a recursive filter therefore contains values going back into the calculation of the latest output. The expression for a recursive filter therefore contains not only terms involving the input values ($x_n, x_{n-1}, x_{n-2}, \dots$) but also terms in (y_{n-1}, y_{n-2}, \dots).

Some people use an alternative terminology for the non-recursive filter: FIR (or Finite Impulse Response) filter, and a recursive filter as an IIR (or Infinite Impulse Response) filter. These terms refer to the differing "impulse responses" of the two types of filter. The impulse response of a digital filter is the output sequence from the filter when a *unit impulse* is applied at its input. (A unit impulse is a very simple input sequence consisting of a single value of 1 at time $t = 0$, followed by zeros at all subsequent sampling instants). A FIR filter is the one whose impulse response is of finite duration. An IIR filter has an output that terms feed-back energy into the filter input and keep it going. The term IIR is not very accurate because the actual impulse responses of nearly all IIR filters reduce virtually to zero in a finite time. Nevertheless, these two terms are widely used.

Now we introduce the *transfer function* of a digital filter. This is obtained from the symmetrical form of the filter expression, and it allows us to describe a filter by means of a convenient, compact expression. We can also use the transfer function of a filter to work out its frequency response. First of all, we must introduce the *delay operator*, denoted by the symbol z^{-1} . When applied to a sequence of digital values this operator gives the *previous* value in the sequence. Therefore it introduces a delay of one sampling interval. Applying the operator z^{-1} to an input value (x_n) it gives the previous input (x_{n-1}): $z^{-1}x_n = x_{n-1}$. Similarly, applying the z^{-1} operator to an output, it gives the previous output: $z^{-1}Y_n = Y_{n-1}$. to delay three or more sampling intervals, the appropriate power of z^{-1} being used. Let us now use this notation in the description of a recursive digital filter. Consider, for example, a general second-order filter, given in its symmetrical form by the expression

$b_0y_n + b_1y_{n-1} + b_2y_{n-2} = a_0x_n + a_1x_{n-1} + a_2x_{n-2}$ (where a, and b are the filter coefficients. The number of one type of these parameters represents the filter order). We will make use of the following identities:

$z^{-1}x_n = x_{n-1}$, $z^{-1}x_{n-1} = x_{n-2}$, $z^{-1}y_n = y_{n-1}$, $z^{-1}y_{n-1} = y_{n-2}$ Substituting these expressions into the digital

filter gives: $(b_0 + b_1z^{-1} + b_2z^{-2})y_n = (a_0 + a_1z^{-1} + a_2z^{-2})x_n$. Rearranging this one to give a direct relationship

between the output and input for the filter, we get:
$$\frac{y_n}{x_n} = \frac{a_0 + a_1z^{-1} + a_2z^{-2}}{b_0 + b_1z^{-1} + b_2z^{-2}} \quad (4.1)$$

This is the general form of the transfer function for a second-order recursive (IIR) filter. For filters of order higher than 2, further terms involving higher powers are added to both the numerator and denominator of the transfer function. A non-recursive (FIR) filter has a simpler transfer function which does not contain any denominator terms. The coefficient b_0 is usually taken to be equal to 1, and all the other b coefficients are zero. The transfer function of a second-order FIR filter can therefore be expressed in the general form:

$$\frac{y_n}{x_n} = a_0 + a_1z^{-1} + a_2z^{-2} \quad (4.2)$$

4.1.3 Digital FIR used in the ECG Processing

Pan. J and Tompkins. W. J, 1985 proposed an ECG band-pass filter that reduces the influence of muscle noise, 60 or 50 Hz interference, baseline wander, and T-wave interference. The desirable pass-band to maximize the QRS energy is approximately 5-15 Hz. This filter is a recursive filter in which poles are located to cancel zeros on the unit circle of the z plane. And it is composed of a low and a high pass filters (*equation 4.3 and 4.4 respectively*) to achieve a 3 dB pass-band from about 5-12 Hz. The amplitude response in the frequency plane is illustrated in the Figure 4.2.A where the filter performance on a trace of ECG is illustrated in the figure 4.3. B

Figure 4.2. A. Amplitude response of the pass-band filter.

Figure 4.2. B. Pan & Tompkins band-pass filter performance.

$$y(nT) = 2y(nT - T) - y(nT - 2T) + x(nT) - 2x(nT - 5T) + x(nT - 12T) \quad (4.3)$$

$$y(nT) = y(nT - T) - x(nT) / 32 + x(nT - 16T) - x(nT - 17T) + x(nT - 32T) / 32 \quad (4.4)$$

Another pass-band type filter was proposed in the literature by (G. Clifford 2000). In order to eliminate the effects of the motion, and respiration (*see sections 3.4, and 3.5 this thesis*). As the precedent filter, this filter is composed of low and high-pass filters. The high and low-pass filters are a FIR types. The transfer function of the low-pass filter contains 128 coefficients, where the high-pass filter transfer function

contains 310 coefficients (*the coefficients of this filter is reported in [34]*). Figure 4. 3. A illustrates the amplitude response in the frequency plane, and 4. 3. B shows the performance on a trace of ECG.

Figure 4. 3. A. the amplitude response in the frequency plane of G. Clifford FIR band-pass filters (cascaded) : 70dB 0.05-40Hz 1dB ripple.

Figure4. 3. B. The performance of G. Clifford band-pass filter.

4.1.4 IIR filters used in the ECG Processing

4.1.4.1 Narrow-band filters

A common need in ECG processing is to isolate a narrow band of frequencies from a wider bandwidth signal. Two types of frequency responses are available: the *band-pass* and the *band-reject* (also called a **notch filter**). Notch filter is more used in the ECG processing in order to eliminate or reduce power line effects (50, or 60 Hz) interferences (*see section 3.7 in this thesis*). Two main parameters must be determined before designing the notch filter: f_{rej} is the center frequency or the rejected frequency, and BW is the band width of frequency. Both of these are expressed as a function of the sampling frequency, and therefore must be between 0 and 0.5. From these specified values, we can calculate the other intermediate parameters R, and K, and then the recursive coefficients a, and b, as they were described from (Steven W. Smith 1997-1999).

$$R = 1 - 3BW, \quad K = \frac{1 - 2R \cos(2\pi f_{rej}) + R^2}{2 - 2 \cos(2\pi f_{rej})} \quad (4.5)$$

$$a_0 = K, \quad a_1 = -2K \cos(2\pi f_{rej}), \quad a_2 = K, \quad b_1 = 2R \cos(2\pi f_{rej}), \quad b_1 = -R^2 \quad (4.6)$$

Figures 4.5.A and 4.5.B illustrate the amplitude response in the frequency plane and the performance on an ECG signal of a notch filter respectively. Chosen notch filter has f_{rej} of about 60 Hz, and BW of about 0.11, where the signal was sampled at 360 Hz (MIT BIH database, record 104). So the filter acts as powerline(60 Hz) interferences filter.

4.1.4.2 Chebyshev filters

There are three widely used filters, namely, Butterworth, Chebyshev, and Elliptic filters. Chebyshev performs better than the others in the ECG signal processing.

So it is employed. We have two types of Chebyshev filters: Type I Chebyshev filters are all pole filters that exhibit equi-ripple behaviour in the pass-band and a monotonic characteristic in the stop-band. Figures 4. 4. A and B illustrate the response of amplitude in the frequency plane and the performance on the ECG of the I type Chebyshev ($R_p = 0.5$, $N = 3$, and the pass-band = [0.1 20] Hz) respectively.

On the other hand, the family of Type II Chebyshev filters contains both poles and zeros and exhibits a monotonic behaviour in the pass-band and an equi-ripple behaviour in the stop-band. The zeros of this class of

filters lie on the imaginary axis in the s-plane. Figures 4.4.C. and 4.4.D illustrate the response of amplitude in the frequency plane and the performance on the ECG of the II type Chebyshev (Rs=2, N=4, and the pass-band =[0.1 20] Hz) respectively. Not that Chebyshev filter reduces the noise amplitude(good), but at the same time reduces the signal amplitude(bad)

Figure 4. 5. A. The amplitude response in the frequency plane of the notch filter.

Figure 4. 5. B. The performance of the notch filter, on a trace of ECG signal.

Let ϵ be the pass-band ripple, Ω_p be the pass-band cutoff frequency in rad/sec, A be the stopband attenuation parameter and Ω_s be the stop band cut-off in rad/sec. The parameters ϵ and A are related to parameters R_p and A_s respectively of the dB-scale and the relation is given by (Pablo Lugana et al., 1992):

$$\epsilon = (10^{R_p/10} - 1)^{1/2} \tag{4.7}$$

$$A = 10^{A_s/20} \tag{4.8}$$

Also $\Omega_c = \Omega_p$ and $\Omega_r = \Omega_s / \Omega_p$. The order N , of the Chebyshev filter is given by:

$$g = ((A^2 - 1) / \epsilon^2)^{1/2} \tag{4.9}$$

$$N = [(\log_{10} (g + (g^2 - 1)^{1/2}) / (\log_{10} (\Omega_r^2 - 1)^{1/2}))]^{1/2} \tag{4.10}$$

Chebyshev filters were rarely used in literature of ECG signal processing. Only in some individual cases Chebyshev filters are used as an intermediate stage in the QRS detection algorithms, in order to allow more freedom in choosing the transfer function when the other types of filter fail to reduce the effect of white noise (Antti Ruha, et al., 1997).

Figure 4. 4. A. the amplitude response in the frequency plane of the Chebyshev filter type I.

Figure 4. 4. B. Performance of the Chebyshev filter type I.

Figure 4. 4. C. the amplitude response in the frequency plane of the Chebyshev filter type II.

Figure 4. 4. D. Performance of the Chebyshev filter type II.

4.2 Moving Average Filter:

The moving average is the most common filter in DSP, mainly because it is the easiest digital filter to understand and use. In spite of its simplicity, the moving average filter is *optimal* for a common task: reducing random noise while retaining a sharp step response. This makes it the premier filter for time domain encoded signals. However, the moving average is the *worst* filter for frequency domain encoded signals, with little ability to separate one band of frequencies from another. Relatives of the moving average filter include the Gaussian, Blackman, and multiple-pass moving average. These have slightly better performance in the frequency domain, at the expense of increased computation time.

As the name implies, the moving average filter operates by averaging a number of points from the input signal to produce each point in the output signal. In equation form, this is written:

$$y_i = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=0}^{M-1} x_{i+j} \quad (4. 11)$$

Where x is the input signal, y is the output signal, and M is the number of points in the average. Figure 4.5 illustrates how an eleven, and 22 points moving average windows work over a noisy trace of ECG signal. The smoothing action of this filter decreases the amplitude of the random noise (good), but also reduces the sharpness of the QRS complexes and causes a loss in the other component like as the T wave (bad).

Figure 4. 5. Performance of the moving window average filter on a trace of noisy ECG (signal was sampled at 360 s/s):
A. An eleven points window average filter.
B. A forty points window average filter.

(Pan& Tompkins 1985) used the this method as intermediate stage in their QRS detection algorithm. Next chapter of this thesis will explain this algorithm.

4.3 Linear Adaptive Filters

Linear adaptive filters are self-designing filters based on an algorithm which allows the filter to “learn” the initial input statistics and to track them if they are time varying. These filters estimate the deterministic signal and remove the noise uncorrelated with the deterministic signal. We have considered adaptive impulse correlated filter which requires the signal and a reference input. The least mean square algorithm is used to adjust the weights of the adaptive filter in order to minimize the error and estimate the deterministic component through filter output. This algorithm is well known in literature(Ju-Won Lee and Gun-Ki Lee, 2005), and can be expressed by the following equation

$$\omega_{k+1} = \omega_k + 2 \mu \xi_k X_k \quad (4. 12)$$

Where ω_k is the weight vector, X_k is the reference input, ξ_k is the error, and μ is the convergence factor. The convergence factor μ selection becomes a trade off between convergence rate and the steady state mean square error. If μ is large learning occurs quickly, but if it is too large it may lead to instability and errors may even increase. To ensure stable learning, the learning rate must be less than the reciprocal of the largest eigenvalue of the correlation matrix $X^T X$ of the input vectors. Figure illustrates the topology of this type of filter:

4.3.1 Electromyography effects filter

Using linear adaptive filter technique, A 15-tap filter was implemented in MATLAB® with a reference of a random values signal, The filter traverses through the signal and reduce the noise which is caused by electromyography. Figure(4. 6) illustrates the structure of this filter represented schematically.

Present filter is widely used to filter the ECG signal, but its convergence and performance cause distortions and even poor performance, depending on the environment and the patient’s condition. Figure (4. 7) illustrates an example of a poor performance of this filter on a trace of signal taken from the record 104 of the MIT database,

Figure 4. 6. The topology of the linear adaptive filter.

Figure 4. 7. The poor performance of the linear adaptive filter on a trace taken from the record 104 of the MIT database.

4.4 Wavelet Filters

Wavelets are transform methods that have received great deal of attention over the past several years. The wavelet transform is a time-scale representation method that decomposes signals into basis time functions and scale, which makes it useful in applications as ECG signal de-noising, ECG wave detection, ECG data

compression, and ECG features extraction, etc. There are many techniques based on wavelet theory, as wavelet packets, wavelet approximation and decomposition, discrete and continuous wavelet transform, etc. Wavelets are generated according to the following equation from a mother wavelet.

$$\psi_{j,k}(t) = 2^{j/2} / \psi(2^j t - k) \quad (4.13)$$

The wavelet system is a set of building blocks to construct or represent a signal or function. It's a two dimensional expansion set. A linear expansion would be:

$$f(t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} c_k \varphi(t - k) + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{+\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{+\infty} d_{j,k} \psi(2^j t - k) \quad (4.14)$$

Most of the wavelet theory results are developed using filter banks. In application one has never to deal directly with the scaling functions or wavelets, only filters coefficients in the filter banks are needed (C. S. Burrus, et..1998). A full wavelet packet decomposition binary tree for tree scale wavelet packet transform is shown in Figure

The Energy in a signal is given in terms of the WT coefficients by Parsaval's relation as:

$$\int |f(t)|^2 dt = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} |c_k|^2 + \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} |d_{j,k}|^2 \quad (4.15)$$

4.4.1 Removal of the baseline wander

An algorithm was proposed from (Behzad Mozaffary, et .., 2004) for the removal of the baseline wander in ECG signal based on the assumption that the baseline and ECG signal constitute a mixture of two independent signals, mixed in a linear fashion. The wavelet transform of this signal is computed. In each scale using the wavelet coefficients, the energy of the signal for both the coarse and detail levels is calculated. These energies represent the energy of the decomposed signal in assumed scale.

$$E_{j,l} = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} |C_m|^2, \quad E_{j,h} = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} |d_{j,k}|^2 \quad (4.16)$$

In these equations $E_{j,l}$ is the energy of the signal in the coarse level of scale j (low pass filtering branch), and $E_{j,h}$ is the energy of the signal in the detail level of scale j (high pass filtering branch). Next step is to compare $E_{j,l}$ and $E_{j,h}$ then choose the branch of binary tree with the higher energy. The higher energy branches will be followed until reaching a point where energy difference exceeds a preset threshold level. In this point the binary tree is complete, and the baseline wander signal is identified. Using the wavelet coefficients obtained, the inverse wavelet transform is calculated. In wavelet domain the baseline wander is subtracted from original data record and a baseline wander free ECG signal is identified. In Figure 4. 9 the block diagram of the algorithm is shown.

Baseline wander removing using the above-mentioned concept was tested on ECG data records. The test database was extracted from the MIT-BIH databases, and "103" record was used. We tested the algorithm to remove the baseline wander of the record itself as shown in Figure 4. 10, and also we added different low frequency

waveforms as ramp and sine wave to ECG record and the algorithm was applied. These are shown in Figures 4.11.A and 4.11.B. As figures show, this algorithm removes baseline wander excellently.

Figure 4. 9. The block diagram of the removal of baseline wander by using wavelet technique.

Figure 4. 10. The performance of the filter on a trace of the record 103 taken from MIT data base.

Figure 4. 11. A. The performance of the filter on a trace of the record 103 after adding a ramp signal.

Figure 4. 11. B. The performance of the filter on a trace of the record 103 after adding a sine signal.

This algorithm removes the not correlated to ECG components and has such characteristics somehow added to it. Since the spectrum of the baseline is located below the spectrum of the ECG signal, its energy concentration in corresponding time-scale plane does not change much as the scale is changed in the binary tree, but the energy of the ECG signal decreases to varying of scale. Therefore, in the binary tree search it's possible to reach a point in which the energy of the ECG signal almost vanishes (no details in that scale) with a considerable energy for baseline wander.

4.4.2 Reduce the effects of the white noise:

In the same way we propose in this thesis a method to reduce the effect or the white noise superimposed on the ECG signal. We can easily understand the problem looking at the example illustrated in the Figure 4. 12, which represents a 1000 samples ECG signal taken from the record (104) of MIT BIH database. This signal is corrupted by many types of noise see Figure 4. 13.

Figure 4. 12. An example of ECG signal corrupted from different kinds of noise.

Figure 4. 13. Gaussian white noise signal (random values generated in Matlab environment).

The basic one-dimensional model is:

$$S(n) = F(n) + \sigma E(n) \quad (4. 17)$$

In this model we suppose that $E(n)$ is a white noise, and the noise level σ is supposed to be equal to 1. De-noising objective is to suppress the noise part of the signal s and to recover F . Time n is equally spaced. De-noising procedure involves the three steps described below:

- 1- compute the 'db4'⁷ wavelet decomposition of the original signal S , selecting 3 levels.
- 2- threshold detail coefficients for each level from 1:N, using the soft thresholding method.
- 3- compute the wavelet reconstruction (inverse wavelet) using the original approximation coefficients and the modified detail coefficients.

First and third steps aren't difficult, the question now is how the thresholding step is proceeding

In order to answer to this question let S denote the signal, and T the threshold value. Then hard and soft threshold signals are expressed as follows:

- In the hard thresholding method	$Y=S \quad \text{if} \quad abs(S) > T.$ $Y=0 \quad \text{if} \quad abs(S) \leq T.$
- Where In the soft thresholding method	$Y= Sign(S)(abs(S) - T) \quad \text{if} \quad abs(S) > T.$ $Y=0 \quad \text{if} \quad abs(S) \leq T.$

Hard thresholding can be described as the usual process of setting to zero the elements whose absolute values are lower than the threshold. Soft thresholding is an extension of hard thresholding, first setting to zero the elements whose absolute values are lower than the threshold and then shrinking the nonzero coefficients towards 0. Figure 4. 14 shows these two thresholding methods).

The threshold selection rules are:

1. Sure: based on *Stein's Unbiased Estimate of Risk* (quadratic loss function). You get an estimation of the risk for a particular threshold value T , which minimizes the risks.
2. Fixed form: yielding mini-max performance multiplied by a small factor proportional to $L=log(length(S))$. Fixed form threshold equal to $T = \sqrt{2 L}$

⁷ Daubechies wavelet transform is named after its inventor , the mathematician Ingrid Daubechies. The Daubechies D4 transform has four wavelet and scaling function coefficients. The scaling function coefficients are: $h_0 = \frac{1 + \sqrt{3}}{4\sqrt{2}}$, $h_1 = \frac{3 + \sqrt{3}}{4\sqrt{2}}$, $h_2 = \frac{3 - \sqrt{3}}{4\sqrt{2}}$, $h_3 = \frac{1 - \sqrt{3}}{4\sqrt{2}}$.

Figure 4. 14. A: original signal, B: hard thresholding, and C: soft thresholding.

- Mixture: is a mixture of the two previous options. As a result, if the signal-to-noise ratio is very small, the Sure estimation is very noisy. So the fixed method is used.

Matlab® facilitates the threshold value computation by using the function ‘thselect’ which requires to specify the signal vector and the name of the method.

Suppose a noise signal generated as a 1000 sample points of random normal values of distribution, In this case we may compute the threshold value in our case of study. See the next Table:

Method	Stein's Unbiased (SURE)	Fixed threshold	Mixture
Threshold value	2. 0735	2. 449	2. 449

Because y is a standard Gaussian noise, we expect that each method kills roughly all the coefficients and returns the result $F(S)=0$, for Santein’s Unbiased Risk Estimation roughly 3% coefficients is saved, while for other selection rules coefficients are set to 0. So in our example the Fixed form threshold rule wins, and the soft threshold method exhibits an efficiency to remove the noise. Figure 4. 15. A shows the filter performance on the same noisy trace of the ECG illustrated above. Where the Figures 4. 15. B, C, and D represent the performance of this filter on a three traces chosen from the available records of the MIT database. It is noted that the method is efficient for families of signals f that have only a few nonzero wavelet coefficients. So these signals have a sparse wavelet representation.

Figure 4. 15. Performance of present filter:

A: Filtered ECG signal before illustrated in Figure 4.12.

B: C, and D: ECG traces taken from the records 104, 108, 205 of the MIT database, respectively.

CHAPTER 5

QRS DETECTION

Introduction

Electrocardiogram (ECG) analysis is an important tool in the management of cardiac diseases. One of the most relevant tasks in automatic ECG analysis is the detection and characterization of every wave particularly of the QRS complex. QRS complex is the most striking waveform within the electrocardiogram (ECG). Since it reflects the electrical activity within the heart during the ventricular contraction, the time of its occurrence, as well as its shape, provides much information about the current state of the heart. The QRS complex contains signal components in a relatively wide of frequency band from about 2 to 100 Hz, with peak at 10-15 Hz.

Due to its characteristic shape serves as the basis for the automated determination of the heart rate, as an entry point for classification schemes of the cardiac cycle, and often it is also used in ECG data compression algorithms. In that sense, QRS detection provides the fundamentals for almost all automated ECG analysis algorithms.

Therefore, choosing the QRS detection algorithm is an essential step in the development of a real time ECG analysis system. Experience, over several years, shows that the proposed strategies for ECG analysis and particularly for QRS complex detection based on signal processing techniques, have reached asymptotic detection performance. This is mainly due to the multiplicity of situations met in clinical environments.

Many QRS detection algorithms have been proposed in the literature, in this chapter we develop one of these algorithms which was proposed from M. Pauletti and C. Marchesi in 2001 and we evaluate the performance of this developed algorithm by comparing it with other four algorithms (Pan and Tompkins, 1985; Suppappola and Sun 1991; So H and Chan K L, 1997, Antti *et al.*, 1997). The tested detectors have been chosen considering both complexity and efficiency but prioritising the low complexity against the efficiency. This evaluation process is performed on the available records of MIT-BIH database.

5.1 Pan and Tompkins QRS Detection Algorithm (Pan. J and Tompkins. W. J, 1985):

This algorithm identifies the QRS complexes based upon digital analyses of the slope, amplitude, and width of the ECG data. The algorithm implements a special digital band-pass filter. It can reduce false detection caused by the various types of interference present in the ECG signal. This filtering permits the use of low thresholds, thereby increases the detection sensitivity. The algorithm automatically adjusts the thresholds and parameters periodically to adapt to changes in QRS morphology and heart rate. In summary it consists of the following steps:

5.1.1 Band-pass filtering: here we have used the same filter that we have explained in section 4. 1. 3 of this thesis, this filter is a 3 dB band-pass from about 5-12 Hz, but it is composed from a low-pass and high-pass filters, the derivative functions of a low-pass and high pass filters are illustrated in the equations 5. 1, and 5. 2 respectively.

$$y(nT) = 2y(nT - T) - y(nT - 2T) + x(nT) - 2x(nT - 5T) + x(nT - 12T) \quad (5. 1)$$

$$y(nT) = y(nT - T) - x(nT)/32 + x(nT - 16T) - x(nT - 17T) + x(nT - 32T)/32 \quad (5. 2)$$

5.1.2 Differentiation: after filtering, the signal is differentiated to provide the QRS complex slope information.

A five-point derivative was used with the following equation.

$$y(nT) = (1/8)[2x(nT) + x(nT - T) - x(nT - 3T) - 2x(nT - 4T)] \quad (5.3)$$

Figure 5. 2. shows the frequency response of this derivative is nearly linear between the dc and 30 Hz.

Figure 5. 2. Amplitude response of the digital derivative filter.

Figure 5. 3. The relationship of the QRS complex to the moving integration waveform. (A) ECG signal. (B) Output of the moving -window integrator. QS: QRS width. W: width of the integrator window.

5.1.3 Squaring function

After differentiation, the signal is squared point by point. This makes all data points positive, and does non-linear amplification of the output of the derivative emphasizing the higher frequencies (i.e., *predominantly the ECG frequencies*). The output of the squaring function was hard limited to a maximal value of 255.

5.1.4 Moving-window integration

The purpose of moving-window integration is to obtain wave-form feature information in addition to slope of the R wave. It is calculated from:

$$y(nT) = (1/N)[x(nT - (N-1)T) + x(nT - (N-2)T) + \dots + x(nT)] \quad (5.4)$$

where N is the number of samples in the width of the integration window. Figure 5.3 shows the relationship between the moving-window integration wave form and the QRS complex. The number of samples N in the moving window is important. Generally, the width of the window should be approximately the same widest possible QRS complex. If the window is too wide, the integration waveform will merge the QRS and T complexes together. If it is too narrow, some QRS complexes will produce several peaks in the integration waveform. These can cause difficulty in subsequent QRS detection process. The width of the window is determined empirically. For the sample rate of 200 samples/s the window is 30 samples wide (150ms).

5.1.5 Fiducial Mark determination & Adjusting the Thresholds

The QRS complex corresponds to the rising edge of the integration waveform. The duration of the rising edge is equal to the width of the QRS complex. A fiducial mark for the temporal location of the QRS complex can be determined from this rising edge according to the desired waveform feature to be marked such as the maximal slope or the peak of the R-wave.

The thresholds are automatically adjusted to float over the noise. Low thresholds are possible because of the improvement of the signal-to-noise ratio by the band-pass filter. The higher of the two thresholds in each of the two sets is used for the first analysis of the signal. The lower one is used if no QRS is detected in a certain time interval so that a search-back technique is necessary to look back in time for the QRS complex. The set of thresholds initially applied to the integration waveform is computed from

$$SPKI = 0.125 PEAKI + 0.875 SPKI \text{ (if PEAKI is the signal peak).}$$

$$\text{NPKI} = 0.125 \text{PEAKI} + 0.875 \text{NPKI} \text{ (if PEAKI is the noise peak).}$$

$$\text{THRESHOLD I1} = \text{NPKI} + 0.25(\text{SPKI} - \text{NPKI}), \text{THRESHOLD I2} = 0.5 \text{THRESHOLD I1.}$$

where all the variables refer to the integration waveform:

PEAKI is the overall peak, SPKI is the running estimate of the signal peak, NPKI is the running estimate of the noise peak, THRESHOLD I1 is the first threshold applied, and THRESHOLD I2 is the second threshold applied.

A peak is a local maximum determined by observing the signal change direction within a predefined time interval. The signal peak SPKI is a peak previously established by the algorithm to be QRS complex. The noise peak NPKI is any peak that is not related to the QRS (e.g., T wave). The thresholds are based upon running estimates of SPKI and NPKI. That is, new values of these variables are computed in part from their prior values.

When a new peak is detected first it must be classified as a noise peak or a signal peak. To be a signal peak, the peak must exceed THRESHOLD I1 as the signal is first analyzed or THRESHOLD I2 if search back is required to find the QRS. When the QRS complex is found using the second threshold $\text{SPKI} = 0.25 \text{PEAKI} + 0.75 \text{SPKI}$.

The set of thresholds applied to the filtered ECG is determined from:

$$\text{SPKF} = 0.125 \text{PEAKF} + 0.875 \text{SPKI} \text{ (if PEAKF is the signal peak)}$$

$$\text{NPKF} = 0.125 \text{PEAKF} + 0.875 \text{NPKF} \text{ (if PEAKF is the noise peak)}$$

$$\text{THRESHOLD F1} = \text{NPKF} + 0.25(\text{SPKF} - \text{NPKF}), \text{THRESHOLD F2} = 0.5 \text{THRESHOLD F1.}$$

Where all the variables refer to the filtered ECG PEAKF is the overall peak, SPKF is the running estimate of the signal peak, NPKF is the running estimate of the noise peak, THRESHOLD F1 is the first threshold applied, and THRESHOLD F2 is the second threshold applied. When the QRS complex is found using the second threshold $\text{SPKF} = 0.25 \text{PEAKF} + 0.75 \text{SPKF}$. For the irregular heart rates, the first threshold of each set is reduced by half so as to increase the detection sensitivity and to avoid missing beats: $\text{THRESHOLD I1} = 0.5 \text{THRESHOLD I1}$ and $\text{THRESHOLD F1} = 0.5 \text{THRESHOLD F1}$.

Present algorithm was tested on the available Records of MIT-BIH database, and EUROPEAN ST-T database. Figure 5. 4. illustrates the performance of Pan & Tompkins algorithm over an arbitrary traces taken from records 104, and 108 of MIT-BIH database, and the record E0110 of ST-T EUROPEAN database.

Figure 5. 4. Performance of Pan& Tompkins QRS detection algorithm:

A, B: a trace taken from the record 104 of MIT-BIH database, note that a false negative beat has taken place.
C, D: a trace taken from the record 108 of MIT-BIH database, note that three false positive beats have taken places.
E, F: a trace taken from the record E0110 of EUROPEAN database, note that different false positive and negative beats have been taken places. The lines which plotted in red and green represent the THRESHOLD I1 and THRESHOLD I2 respectively.

5.2 Suppappola and Sun QRS Detection Algorithm (Suppappola and Sun 1991):

This algorithm uses a non-linear transform called MOBD (Multiplication of Backward Difference), which derives from the formula:

$$y(n) = \prod_{k=0}^4 |x(n-k) - x(n-k-1)| \quad (5.5)$$

An integration average window (20 points) is applied on the $y(n)$, and then the QRS detection process is performed with a set of adaptive thresholds. Because of no other signal pre-processing, noise and artifacts have to be additionally detected in the resulting feature signal. Figure 5.5. illustrates the performance of present algorithm on arbitrary traces taken from records 104 and 108 of MIT-BIH database, and E0110, E0112 of EUROPEAN database.

Figure 5.5. Performance of Suppappola and Sun QRS detection algorithm:

A, B, C, and D represent the algorithm performance over arbitrary traces taken from records 104, and 108 of the MIT-BIH database, E0110, and E0112 of the EUROPEAN database respectively. Note the false positive cases in A (record 104 of MIT-BIH), and B (record 108 of MIT-BIH), these false positive cases may take place when the signal is corrupted from different types of noise. MOBD is not sufficient to reduce or cancel the noise and artefacts.

5.3 So H and Chan K L, 1997 QRS Detection Algorithm (So H and Chan K L, 1997):

This algorithm is based on the maximum slope of the ECG data adaptive thresholding, and it is intended to implement on the ambulatory ECG monitor. The computational requirement is kept at a reasonable level, without compromising its accuracy. In the following paragraph we explain this algorithm:

Let $x(n)$ represents the amplitude of the ECG data at discrete n . The slope of the ECG wave is obtained by:

$$\text{slope}(n) = -2x(n-2) - x(n-1) + x(n+1) + 2x(n-2) \quad (5.6)$$

the slope threshold is given by:

$$\text{slope_thresh} = \frac{\text{thresh_param}}{16} \text{maxi} \quad (5.7)$$

when two consecutive ECG data satisfy the condition that $\text{slope}(n) > \text{slope_thresh}$, the onset of the QRS complex is detected. The parameter `thresh_param` can be set as 2, 4, 8, 16, or 32. After the detection of the onset of the QRS complex the maximum point (`maxi`) is searched and taken as the R point. `Maxi` is then updated by:

$$\text{maxi} = \frac{\text{first_max} - \text{maxi}}{\text{filter_param}} + \text{maxi} \quad (5.8)$$

where first_max = height of the R point - height of the QRS onset, and filter_param can be set as 2, 4, 8, or 16, the initial maxi is the maximum slope of the first 250 data points(samples) in the ECG file. Present algorithm was tested on the MIT and European ST-T database. The performance over some traces is shown in the Figure 5. 6.

Figure 5. 6. Performance of So. H and Chan. K L. QRS detection algorithm: **A, B, C,D, E,** and **F** represent the algorithm performance over arbitrary traces taken from records 200, 104, 228, and 108 of the MIT-BIH database, E0106, and E0104 of the EUROPEAN database respectively. Note the false positive cases in A (record 200 of MIT-BIH), B (record 104 of MIT-BIH), D (record 108 of MIT-BIH).

5.4 Antti QRS Detection Algorithm (Antti *et al.*, 1997):

A QRS detection algorithm employs the signal processing in the digital filter domains. As we show in the following diagram:

5.4.1 Notch filter: removes any residual power line interference from the sampled signal. The notch filter is realized using digital filter methods (we have explained in detail this filter in Chapter 4).

5.4.2 Band-pass filter (15-40 Hz): attenuates the low frequency noise that can be caused by motion artifacts. The chosen pass-band (15-40 Hz) filter output joined to the white noise allows a function apt to a better matched filter running in the following stage. The band-pass filter uses current, two delayed input samples and two delayed output samples to calculate the output, as the following:

$$y(nT) = x(nT) - 2x(nT - 16T) + x(nT - 32T) - 2y(nT - 8T) + y(nT - 16T) \quad (5.9)$$

5.4.3 Matched filter: this filter provides an optimal signal to noise ratio (SNR) and, above all, a symmetrical output pulse waveform. The matched filter output for the filter impulse response length ($N=30$) is calculated as:

$$y(nT) = \sum_{i=0}^{30} k_i x(nT - iT) \quad (5.10)$$

where $x(nT)$ is input sample, $y(nT)$ is output sample, and k is the coefficient of the filter. The matched filter impulse response is optimized for each patient by selecting the filter coefficients in the beginning of a measurement by selecting a good representative of the bandpass-filtered QRS complex. It has been used the Least Mean Square (*LMS*) as an optimization method, in order to minimize the error between a selected input representing the pass-band filtered signal multiplied by a coefficient equal 0.1, and the pass-band filtered signal as a target. This method is realized using an adaptive linear filter with a tapped delay window combined of 30 samples. See Figure 5. 7.

Figure 5. 7. Matched filter topology.

Typical filtered wave forms of almost noiseless and noisy ECG signals are shown in Figure 5.8, the symmetrical output pulse waveform of the matched filter is clearly shown. In order to provide a better timing- resolution the signal obtained from the matched filter output is linearly interpolated to three times the original sampling rate to 1080 s/s.

5.4.5 Thresholding: QRS detection from the filtered signal is subsequently performed by an adaptive threshold detector, which uses a threshold of about 40% of the maximum value occurred in the filter's stages output over

the last 1.5 sec. For 200 ms after each QRS detection the threshold is raised to 90% of the maximum value previously presented to prevent a false detection due to T wave. The detection and the threshold adaptation algorithm can be describe using a pseudo code as follows.

Variable definitions:

- ENV: matched filter output envelope.
- THR: threshold constant (0.4 to 0.6).
- THRES: threshold coefficient.
- DET: binary value detection signal.
- ETR: envelope rise rate constant (2).
- ETD: envelope decay rate constant (5-15).
- EHC: envelope hold time constant (2s).
- T-LASTP: detection threshold keep time (200ms).

For (“each output sample $x(i)$ from the matched filter”)

If $(x(i) > \text{THRES} * \text{ENV})$

then $\text{DET}(i) = 1$ else $\text{DET}(i) = 0$.

If $(x(i) > \text{ENV})$ then $\text{ENV} = \text{ENV} + \text{ETR} * x(i)$.

If $(x(i) < \text{ENV})$ and (“EHC seconds has passed since the previous update”)

then $\text{ENV} = 0.9 * \text{ENV}$.

If $(\text{DET}(i) = 0)$ and $(\text{DET}(i-1) = 1)$

then $\text{THRES} = 0.9$.

If (“more than T-LASTP has passed since the previous detection”) and $(\text{THRES} > \text{THR})$

then $\text{THRES} = 0.9 * \text{THRES}$.

This algorithm was tested on all the available records of MIT-BIH database, and some records of the ST-T EUROPEAN database. Figure 5.8. illustrates the algorithm performance over arbitrary traces. An insufficiency in the performance of selected filters to extract the QRS complexes from another negative components of the noisy signal has been noted in some noisy signal and it doesn't reduce the effects of artefacts.

Figure 5.8. Performance of Antti QRS detection algorithm:

A, B, C, D, E, and **F** represent the algorithm performance over arbitrary traces taken from records104, 108, and 200 of the MIT-BIH database, E0106, E0110 and E0112 of the EUROPEAN database respectively. Note the false positive cases in **A** (record 200 of MIT-BIH), **B** (record 104 of MIT-BIH), **D** (record 106 of EUROPEAN database), here the filter fails to separate the QRS from other components of the noisy signal.

5.5 Developed Algorithm

All the QRS detection algorithms explained above and others proposed in the literature (Gritzali, 1988; Polli *et.*, 1995; Kadambe *et al* 1999; Daskalov and Stoyanov, 2004), illustrate a good performance when the ECG signal is pure, not corrupted by noise. In the case of noisy ECG signals, some of these algorithms have an acceptable performance as (Pan & Tompkins) algorithm; other algorithms fail completely and illustrate a bad performance as (MOBD algorithm). So this section solves the problems denoted in the QRS detection algorithms by developing:

- 1-The pre-processing step: guarantees a notable reduction or an elimination of the noise superimposed on ECG signal.
- 2-The thresholding step: guarantees a high resolution or a capacity to recognize the QRS waveform from another negative components.

This algorithm develops the method proposed by (M. Pauletti and C. Marchesi, 2001), and in the Figure 5. 9 we illustrate a diagram representing schematically the stages of the developed QRS detection algorithm.

Figure 5. 9. Developed QRS detection algorithm represented schematically.

5.5.1 Pre-processing

It is intended for filtering and reducing the influence of noise superimposed on the ECG. This stage facilitates the QRS detection task. Firstly, a pass-band (0.05-40Hz) FIR filter was used in order to remove the continuous shift and draft baseline. Its coefficients were designed with Sptool (see section in this thesis 4.1.3). Secondly, a notch filter was used in order to reduce the 60Hz or 50 Hz powerline interference (see section in this thesis 4.1.4.I). Finally the signal was resampled to obtain a sampling frequency of 1000 s/s. Figure 5.10 illustrates the performance of the pre-processing step over a noisy ECG trace.

5.5.2 Non linear operator

An original non linear operator was introduced by (M. Pauletti, C. Marchesi, 2001). It is based on a continuous estimation of the length of an ideal curve interpolating signal samples.

In the discrete time domain we can approximate the arc length relative to the i -th sample with the chord length, obtaining:

$$U_i = D_t \sum_w \sqrt{1 + \frac{D_y^2}{D_t^2}} \quad (5.11)$$

D_t is the sampling interval, D_y represents the i -th increment and w is a rough estimate of the duration of the episode (or waveform) to detect.

Figure 5.10. Pre-processing performance:

A and **B**: are arbitrary traces of noisy signals taken from records 104, and 108 of MIT-BIH database respectively. These two records are famous in the literature as noisy signals, because they contain different types of noise.

Now, being D_t a constant, taking the square to further enhance the edges (i.e. the duration of the line referred to time) we obtain:

$$U = \sum_w D_y^2 \quad \text{or even} \quad U_i = \sum_{K=i-n}^{i+n} \Delta\phi_k^2 \quad (5.12)$$

if $\Delta\phi$ is a finite difference operator and $w=2n+1$ the filter window we have as initial condition:

$$U_n = \sum_{k=0}^{2n} (y_k - y_{k-2})^2 \quad (5.13)$$

the recursive equation
$$U_i = U_{i-1} - (y_{i-n-2} - y_{i-n})^2 + (y_{i+n-2} - y_{i+n})^2 \quad (5.14)$$

The performance of this operator is shown in the Figure 5.11.

5.5.3 Thresholding

As we see, there are two main components: the first one corresponds to the QRS complexes, and the second one corresponds to the T and P waves, that disturb QRS detection process.

In order to eliminate it and threshold the QRS complexes, we propose a new threshold method based on the fuzzy clustering c-mean algorithm (S. Osowski et, 2000).

Let the output of the nonlinear operator be $U = [u_1, \dots, u_n]$, we want to partition it into J clusters, each represented by a centre $cent_j$.

Denote C the partition matrix made by rows C_j , where $C_j = [c_{j,1} \dots c_{j,n}]$ and each element represents the membership degree of the data vector U in the j th cluster ($j = 1, \dots, J$) and ($i = 1, \dots, n$). The fuzzy clustering algorithm searches for the partition matrix and cluster centres such that the objective function E is minimized

$$E = \sum_{j=1}^J C_j^m d^2(U, \text{cent}_j) \quad (5.15)$$

subject to $\sum_{j=1}^J C_j = 1$

the parameter m controls the fuzziness of the clusters (usually $m=2$). The function $d_j = d(U, \text{cent}_j)$ measures the distance between the data vector U and the centre j of the j th cluster.

$$d^2(U, \text{cent}_j) = (U - \text{cent}_j)^T M_j (U - \text{cent}_j) \quad (5.16)$$

where M_j is a positive definite value adjusted to the actual shapes of the j th cluster. M_j is defined as:

$$M_j = \sqrt{F_j} F_j^{-1} \quad (5.17)$$

where F_j is the cluster covariance $F_j = C_j^m (U - \text{cent}_j)(U - \text{cent}_j)^T$ (5.18)

Given a data vector U , we choose the number of clusters J (in our case 2 or 3), the weighting coefficient m , and the termination tolerance ξ . The partitioned matrix C is initialized randomly in such a way, that condition (3) is satisfied. Then the algorithm iterates through the following steps:

1- Determine the cluster prototypes cent_j ($j=1, \dots, J$), $\text{cent}_j = \frac{\sum C_j^m U}{\sum C_j^m}$ (5.19)

2- Calculate F_j according to equation (5.18).

3- Compute the distance d_j^2 according to (5.16).

4- Update the partition matrix $C_j = \frac{1}{(d_j)^{2/(m-1)}}$ if $d_j(i) = 0$ then take $C_j(i) = 1$.

5- iterate until $\|C - C^{-1}\| \leq \varepsilon$.

6- Take the C_j vector that corresponds to the max centre of clusters, and threshold it by choosing the threshold value, according to the standard deviation value (STD) of the signal vector:

$$\text{If } C_j(i) > \text{std} * \max(C_j) \Rightarrow C_j(i) = 1 \Rightarrow \text{QRS complex.}$$

$$\text{else if } C_j(i) \leq \text{std} * \max(C_j) \Rightarrow C_j(i) = 0 \Rightarrow \text{P\&T waves.}$$

Figure (5.11) illustrates the performance of this method on the same signals reported in Figure (5.10).

A control procedure was added to the QRS detection process in order to:

1. *controlling* the periods that correspond to the distance between the QRSs detected (RR periods). In the case of a too much long distance with respect to the preceding one (based on signal STD), it means that there are missed QRSs. So the algorithm searches them using another adaptive threshold value, less than the previous one. Then the procedure repeats this step, until all the missed QRSs are detected.

If the STD is negligible there is a signal pause, and the procedure stops the search of QRSs.

2. *correct* the width of all detected QRSs, in order to ignore the very small ones with respect to the mean of the others. A false positive QRS might be caused by the high T-wave amplitude.

Figure 5.11. The performance of the non-linear operator and thresholding process over the same filtered ECG traces reported in the Figure (5.10).

5.6 Test And Evaluate The QRS Detection Algorithms

As an object of study we look at the performance of five different QRS detection algorithms, one of these is our developed method and the others were cited and well explained above. All the five algorithms were tested by using the MIT-BIH database.

The “row data” produced by a classification scheme during the test are counts of the correct and incorrect classifications from each class. This information is then normally displayed in a *confusion matrix*. A confusion matrix is a form of contingency table showing the differences between the true and predicted classes for a set of labelled (i.e. Table I). Tp and Tn are the numbers of true positives and true negatives respectively, Fp and Fn are the numbers of false positives and false negatives respectively. The row totals, Cn and Cp are the number of truly negative and positive examples, the column totals Rn and Rp are the number of predicted negative and positive examples, N being the total number of examples ($N = Cn + Cp = Rn + Rp$). Although the confusion matrix shows

all of the information about the classifier’s performance, more meaningful measures can be extracted from it to illustrate certain performance criteria, for example:

- Accuracy (1-error) = $\frac{(Tp+Tn)}{(Cp+Cn)} = P(C)$ (5. 20)

- Sensitivity ($1-\beta$) = $\frac{Tp}{Cp} = P(Tp)$ (5. 21)

- Specificity ($1-\alpha$) = $\frac{Tn}{Cn} = P(Tn)$. (5. 22)

- Positive predictive value = $\frac{Tp}{Rp}$ (5. 23)

- Negative predictive value = $\frac{Tn}{Rn}$ (5. 24)

All these performance measures are valid only for one operating point, an operating point normally chosen to minimize the probability of error, i.e., produces a classifier with the highest overall accuracy. However, in

general it is not misclassification we want to minimize, but rather misclassification cost. Misclassification cost is normally defined as follows,

$$Cost = F_p C_{Fp} + F_n C_{Fn} \quad (5.25)$$

Tables 5. I, II, III, and IV illustrate the results represented as a confusion matrix of the studied QRS detection algorithms. Figures 5. 12 and 5. 13 show a comparison between the mean value of sensibility, specificity, accuracy and error.

Figure 5. 12. An Evaluation of sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of the five QRS detection algorithms over the MIT-BIH database records, represented as mean values.

Figure 5. 13. The mean error of the five QRS detection algorithms evaluated over the MIT-BIH database records.

Table 5. I. Results of QRS developed QRS detection algorithm.

Record	Total Beats	FP	FN	TP	TN	P+	N+	Se%	Sp %	Accuracy %	Error %
100	2273	0	2	2271	2273	0,999	1,00	100	100	100	0,04
101	1865	3	0	1865	1862	1,000	1,00	100	100	100	0,08
102	2187	24	0	2187	2163	1,000	0,99	100	99	99	0,55
103	2084	0	1	2083	2084	1,000	1,00	100	100	100	0,02
104	2229	17	0	2229	2212	1,000	0,99	100	99	100	0,38
105	2572	4	19	2553	2568	0,993	1,00	99	100	100	0,45
106	2027	0	78	1949	2027	0,962	1,00	96	100	98	1,92
107	2137	0	2	2135	2137	0,999	1,00	100	100	100	0,05
108	1763	41	22	1741	1722	0,988	0,98	99	98	98	1,79
109	2532	0	42	2490	2532	0,983	1,00	98	100	99	0,83
111	2124	2	5	2119	2122	0,998	1,00	100	100	100	0,16
112	2539	17	0	2539	2522	1,000	0,99	100	99	100	0,33
113	1795	0	45	1750	1795	0,975	1,00	97	100	99	1,25
114	1879	11	2	1877	1868	0,999	0,99	100	99	100	0,35
115	1953	2	2	1951	1951	0,999	1,00	100	100	100	0,10
116	2412	1	22	2390	2411	0,991	1,00	99	100	100	0,48
117	1535	3	37	1498	1532	0,976	1,00	98	100	99	1,30
118	2288	1	22	2266	2287	0,990	1,00	99	100	99	0,50
119	1987	1	0	1987	1986	1,000	1,00	100	100	100	0,03
121	1863	1	1	1862	1862	0,999	1,00	100	100	100	0,05
122	2476	0	21	2455	2476	0,992	1,00	99	100	100	0,42
123	1518	1	0	1518	1517	1,000	1,00	100	100	100	0,03
124	1619	0	0	1619	1619	1,000	1,00	100	100	100	0,00
200	2601	21	0	2601	2580	1,000	0,99	100	99	100	0,40
201	2000	13	12	1988	1987	0,994	0,99	99	99	99	0,63
202	2136	0	13	2123	2136	0,994	1,00	99	100	100	0,30
203	2980	0	47	2933	2980	0,984	1,00	98	100	99	0,79
205	2656	74	0	2656	2582	1,000	0,97	100	97	99	1,39
207	2332	0	15	2317	2332	0,994	1,00	99	100	100	0,32
208	2955	31	7	2948	2924	0,998	0,99	100	99	99	0,64
209	3005	32	22	2983	2973	0,993	0,99	99	99	99	0,90
210	2650	61	0	2650	2589	1,000	0,98	100	98	99	1,15
212	2748	0	0	2748	2748	1,000	1,00	100	100	100	0,00
213	3251	4	67	3184	3247	0,979	1,00	98	100	99	1,09
214	2262	7	102	2160	2255	0,955	1,00	95	100	98	2,41
215	3363	0	70	3293	3363	0,979	1,00	98	100	99	1,04
217	2208	0	60	2148	2208	0,973	1,00	97	100	99	1,36
219	2287	0	42	2245	2287	0,982	1,00	98	100	99	0,92
220	2048	14	0	2048	2034	1,000	0,99	100	99	100	0,34
221	2427	15	8	2419	2412	0,997	0,99	100	99	100	0,47
222	2483	13	11	2472	2470	0,996	0,99	100	99	100	0,48
223	2605	0	32	2573	2605	0,988	1,00	99	100	99	0,61
228	2053	52	0	2053	2001	1,000	0,97	100	97	99	1,27
230	2256	0	34	2222	2256	0,985	1,00	98	100	99	0,75
231	1573	17	0	1573	1556	1,000	0,99	100	99	99	0,54
232	1780	44	20	1760	1736	0,989	0,98	99	98	98	1,80
233	3079	18	5	3074	3061	0,998	0,99	100	99	100	0,37
234	3785	18	12	3773	3767	0,997	1,00	100	100	100	0,0009

Table 5. II. Results "Tompkins" QRS detection algorithm.

Record	Total Beats	FP	FN	TP	TN	P+	N+	Se%	Sp %	Accuracy %	Error %
100	2273	0	0	2273	2273	1,000	1,000	100	100	100	0,00
101	1865	5	11	1854	1860	0,994	0,994	99	100	100	0,43
102	2187	7	21	2166	2180	0,990	0,990	99	100	99	0,64
103	2084	27	33	2051	2057	0,984	0,984	98	99	99	1,44
104	2229	1	1	2228	2228	1,000	1,000	100	100	100	0,04
105	2572	91	155	2417	2481	0,957	0,940	94	96	95	4,78
106	2027	5	9	2018	2022	0,996	0,996	100	100	100	0,35
107	2137	11	4	2133	2126	0,998	0,998	100	99	100	0,35
108	1763	233	291	1472	1530	0,863	0,835	83	87	85	14,86
109	2532	21	2	2530	2511	0,999	0,999	100	99	100	0,45
111	2124	12	10	2114	2112	0,995	0,995	100	99	99	0,52
112	2539	11	2	2537	2528	0,999	0,999	100	100	100	0,26
113	1795	0	0	1795	1795	1,000	1,000	100	100	100	0,00
114	1879	3	37	1842	1876	0,980	0,980	98	100	99	1,06
115	1953	13	31	1922	1940	0,984	0,984	98	99	99	1,13
116	2412	22	47	2365	2390	0,981	0,981	98	99	99	1,43
117	1535	12	7	1528	1523	0,995	0,995	100	99	99	0,62
118	2288	4	17	2271	2284	0,990	0,993	99	100	100	0,46
119	1987	13	15	1972	1974	0,992	0,992	99	99	99	0,70
121	1863	4	19	1844	1859	0,990	0,990	99	100	99	0,62
122	2476	1	3	2473	2475	0,999	0,999	100	100	100	0,08
123	1518	8	9	1509	1510	0,994	0,994	99	99	99	0,56
124	1619	0	0	1619	1619	1,000	1,000	100	100	100	0,00
200	2601	6	12	2589	2595	0,995	0,995	100	100	100	0,35
201	2000	19	20	1980	1981	0,990	0,990	99	99	99	0,98
202	2136	6	8	2128	2130	0,996	0,996	100	100	100	0,33
203	2980	53	113	2867	2927	0,962	0,962	96	98	97	2,79
205	2656	0	4	2652	2656	0,998	0,998	100	100	100	0,08
207	2332	4	12	2320	2328	0,995	0,995	99	100	100	0,34
208	2955	4	32	2923	2951	0,989	0,989	99	100	99	0,61
209	3005	3	3	3002	3002	0,999	0,999	100	100	100	0,10
210	2650	2	18	2632	2648	0,993	0,993	99	100	100	0,38
212	2748	0	0	2748	2748	0,996	1,000	100	100	100	0,00
213	3251	4	15	3236	3247	0,995	0,995	100	100	100	0,29
214	2262	2	10	2252	2260	0,996	0,996	100	100	100	0,27
215	3363	0	1	3362	3363	0,999	1,000	100	100	100	0,01
217	2208	4	16	2192	2204	0,993	0,993	99	100	100	0,45
219	2287	0	0	2287	2287	0,972	1,000	100	100	100	0,00
220	2048	0	1	2047	2048	0,993	1,000	100	100	100	0,02
221	2427	2	2	2425	2425	0,964	0,999	100	100	100	0,08
222	2483	320	266	2217	2163	0,894	0,893	89	87	88	11,80
223	2605	41	13	2592	2564	0,995	0,995	100	98	99	1,04
228	2053	25	35	2018	2028	0,953	0,983	98	99	99	1,46
230	2256	10	11	2245	2246	0,995	0,995	100	100	100	0,47
231	1573	0	1	1572	1573	0,995	0,999	100	100	100	0,03
232	1780	6	8	1772	1774	0,996	0,996	100	100	100	0,39
233	3079	10	2	3077	3069	0,999	0,999	100	100	100	0,19
234	3785	5	5	3780	3780	0,999	0,999	100	100	100	0,001

Table 5. III. Results of “Suppappola” QRS detection algorithm.

Record	Total Beats	FP	FN	TP	TN	P+	N+	Se%	Sp %	Accuracy %	Error %
100	2273	4	8	2265	2269	0,996	1,00	100	100	100	0,26
101	1865	14	9	1856	1851	0,995	0,99	100	99	99	0,62
102	2187	24	12	2175	2163	0,995	0,99	99	99	99	0,82
103	2084	15	10	2074	2069	0,995	0,99	100	99	99	0,60
104	2229	260	122	2107	1969	0,945	0,88	95	88	91	8,57
105	2572	66	501	2071	2506	0,805	0,97	81	97	89	11,02
106	2027	140	75	1952	1887	0,963	0,93	96	93	95	5,30
107	2137	19	13	2124	2118	0,994	0,99	99	99	99	0,75
108	1763	343	298	1465	1420	0,831	0,81	83	81	82	18,18
109	2532	112	80	2452	2420	0,968	0,96	97	96	96	3,79
111	2124	32	150	1974	2092	0,929	0,98	93	98	96	4,28
112	2539	17	0	2539	2522	1,000	0,99	100	99	100	0,33
113	1795	19	45	1750	1776	0,975	0,99	97	99	98	1,78
114	1879	11	12	1867	1868	0,994	0,99	99	99	99	0,61
115	1953	29	61	1892	1924	0,969	0,99	97	99	98	2,30
116	2412	14	22	2390	2398	0,991	0,99	99	99	99	0,75
117	1535	103	66	1469	1432	0,957	0,93	96	93	94	5,50
118	2288	102	228	2060	2186	0,900	0,96	90	96	93	7,21
119	1987	98	65	1922	1889	0,967	0,95	97	95	96	4,10
121	1863	12	7	1856	1851	0,996	0,99	100	99	99	0,51
122	2476	41	21	2455	2435	0,992	0,98	99	98	99	1,25
123	1518	33	7	1511	1485	0,995	0,98	100	98	99	1,32
124	1619	12	9	1610	1607	0,994	0,99	99	99	99	0,65
200	2601	299	140	2461	2302	0,946	0,89	95	89	92	8,44
201	2000	61	12	1988	1939	0,994	0,97	99	97	98	1,83
202	2136	92	13	2123	2044	0,994	0,96	99	96	98	2,46
203	2980	98	33	2947	2882	0,989	0,97	99	97	98	2,20
205	2656	124	88	2568	2532	0,967	0,95	97	95	96	3,99
207	2332	36	22	2310	2296	0,991	0,98	99	98	99	1,24
208	2955	53	61	2894	2902	0,979	0,98	98	98	98	1,93
209	3005	143	139	2866	2862	0,954	0,95	95	95	95	4,69
210	2650	108	25	2625	2542	0,991	0,96	99	96	97	2,51
212	2748	503	119	2629	2245	0,957	0,82	96	82	89	11,32
213	3251	20	111	3140	3231	0,966	0,99	97	99	98	2,01
214	2262	32	222	2040	2230	0,902	0,99	90	99	94	5,61
215	3363	64	189	3174	3299	0,944	0,98	94	98	96	3,76
217	2208	52	160	2048	2156	0,928	0,98	93	98	95	4,80
219	2287	66	260	2027	2221	0,886	0,97	89	97	93	7,13
220	2048	365	18	2030	1683	0,991	0,82	99	82	91	9,35
221	2427	93	11	2416	2334	0,995	0,96	100	96	98	2,14
222	2483	88	0	2483	2395	1,000	0,96	100	96	98	1,77
223	2605	66	96	2509	2539	0,963	0,97	96	97	97	3,11
228	2053	128	33	2020	1925	0,984	0,94	98	94	96	3,92
230	2256	48	150	2106	2208	0,934	0,98	93	98	96	4,39
231	1573	66	58	1515	1507	0,963	0,96	96	96	96	3,94
232	1780	68	151	1629	1712	0,915	0,96	92	96	94	6,15
233	3079	133	121	2958	2946	0,961	0,96	96	96	96	4,12
234	3785	150	166	3619	3635	0,956	0,96	96	96	96	0,04

Table 5. IV. Results of “ So-Chan “ QRS detection algorithm.

Record	Total Beats	FP	FN	TP	TN	P+	N+	Se%	Sp %	Accuracy %	Error %
100	2273	8	6	2267	2265	1,00	1,00	100	100	100	0,31
101	1865	13	12	1853	1852	0,99	0,99	99	99	99	0,67
102	2187	24	31	2156	2163	0,99	0,99	99	99	99	1,26
103	2084	97	104	1980	1987	0,95	0,95	95	95	95	4,82
104	2229	509	133	2096	1720	0,94	0,77	94	77	86	14,40
105	2572	142	224	2348	2430	0,91	0,94	91	94	93	7,12
106	2027	250	112	1915	1777	0,94	0,88	94	88	91	8,93
107	2137	174	184	1953	1963	0,91	0,92	91	92	92	8,38
108	1763	256	209	1554	1507	0,88	0,85	88	85	87	13,19
109	2532	147	122	2410	2385	0,95	0,94	95	94	95	5,31
111	2124	103	198	1926	2021	0,91	0,95	91	95	93	7,09
112	2539	200	133	2406	2339	0,95	0,92	95	92	93	6,56
113	1795	36	122	1673	1759	0,93	0,98	93	98	96	4,40
114	1879	134	66	1813	1745	0,96	0,93	96	93	95	5,32
115	1953	142	64	1889	1811	0,97	0,93	97	93	95	5,27
116	2412	154	22	2390	2258	0,99	0,94	99	94	96	3,65
117	1535	241	37	1498	1294	0,98	0,84	98	84	91	9,06
118	2288	124	188	2100	2164	0,92	0,95	92	95	93	6,82
119	1987	98	104	1883	1889	0,95	0,95	95	95	95	5,08
121	1863	73	93	1770	1790	0,95	0,96	95	96	96	4,46
122	2476	111	88	2388	2365	0,96	0,96	96	96	96	4,02
123	1518	107	64	1454	1411	0,96	0,93	96	93	94	5,63
124	1619	28	33	1586	1591	0,98	0,98	98	98	98	1,88
200	2601	109	200	2401	2492	0,92	0,96	92	96	94	5,94
201	2000	98	89	1911	1902	0,96	0,95	96	95	95	4,68
202	2136	124	33	2103	2012	0,98	0,94	98	94	96	3,68
203	2980	34	24	2956	2946	0,99	0,99	99	99	99	0,97
205	2656	124	65	2591	2532	0,98	0,95	98	95	96	3,56
207	2332	254	214	2118	2078	0,91	0,89	91	89	90	10,03
208	2955	214	109	2846	2741	0,96	0,93	96	93	95	5,47
209	3005	261	281	2724	2744	0,91	0,91	91	91	91	9,02
210	2650	119	172	2478	2531	0,94	0,96	94	96	95	5,49
212	2748	121	134	2614	2627	0,95	0,96	95	96	95	4,64
213	3251	119	109	3142	3132	0,97	0,96	97	96	96	3,51
214	2262	123	202	2060	2139	0,91	0,95	91	95	93	7,18
215	3363	144	263	3100	3219	0,92	0,96	92	96	94	6,05
217	2208	324	60	2148	1884	0,97	0,85	97	85	91	8,70
219	2287	214	200	2087	2073	0,91	0,91	91	91	91	9,05
220	2048	167	133	1915	1881	0,94	0,92	94	92	93	7,32
221	2427	107	161	2266	2320	0,93	0,96	93	96	94	5,52
222	2483	113	312	2171	2370	0,87	0,95	87	95	91	8,56
223	2605	241	96	2509	2364	0,96	0,91	96	91	94	6,47
228	2053	301	198	1855	1752	0,90	0,85	90	85	88	12,15
230	2256	77	38	2218	2179	0,98	0,97	98	97	97	2,55
231	1573	219	133	1440	1354	0,92	0,86	92	86	89	11,19
232	1780	120	58	1722	1660	0,97	0,93	97	93	95	5,00
233	3079	111	94	2985	2968	0,97	0,96	97	96	97	3,33
234	3785	73	134	3651	3712	0,96	0,98	96	98	97	0,03

Table 5. V. Results of "Antti" QRS detection algorithm.

Record	Total Beats	FP	FN	TP	TN	P+	Rn	Se%	Sp %	Accuracy %	Error %
100	2273	11	16	2257	2262	0,99	1,00	99	100	99	0,59
101	1865	17	33	1832	1848	0,98	0,99	98	99	99	1,34
102	2187	24	28	2159	2163	0,99	0,99	99	99	99	1,19
103	2084	92	25	2059	1992	0,99	0,96	99	96	97	2,81
104	2229	93	33	2196	2136	0,99	0,96	99	96	97	2,83
105	2572	261	492	2080	2311	0,81	0,90	81	90	85	14,64
106	2027	89	115	1912	1938	0,94	0,96	94	96	95	5,03
107	2137	19	32	2105	2118	0,99	0,99	99	99	99	1,19
108	1763	403	311	1452	1360	82	77	80	20,25	0,82	0,77
109	2532	79	111	2421	2453	0,96	0,97	96	97	96	3,75
111	2124	120	138	1986	2004	0,94	0,94	94	94	94	6,07
112	2539	33	68	2471	2506	0,97	0,99	97	99	98	1,99
113	1795	71	45	1750	1724	0,97	0,96	97	96	97	3,23
114	1879	33	101	1778	1846	0,95	0,98	95	98	96	3,57
115	1953	112	222	1731	1841	0,89	0,94	89	94	91	8,55
116	2412	147	130	2282	2265	0,95	0,94	95	94	94	5,74
117	1535	124	66	1469	1411	0,96	0,92	96	92	94	6,19
118	2288	66	189	2099	2222	0,92	0,97	92	97	94	5,57
119	1987	154	133	1854	1833	0,93	0,92	93	92	93	7,22
121	1863	41	15	1848	1822	0,99	0,98	99	98	98	1,50
122	2476	33	21	2455	2443	0,99	0,99	99	99	99	1,09
123	1518	111	66	1452	1407	0,96	0,93	96	93	94	5,83
124	1619	69	140	1479	1550	0,91	0,96	91	96	94	6,45
200	2601	166	151	2450	2435	0,94	0,94	94	94	94	6,09
201	2000	281	258	1742	1719	0,87	0,86	87	86	87	13,48
202	2136	241	261	1875	1895	0,88	0,89	88	89	88	11,75
203	2980	191	298	2682	2789	0,90	0,94	90	94	92	8,20
205	2656	292	698	1958	2364	0,74	0,89	74	89	81	18,64
207	2332	274	155	2177	2058	0,93	0,88	93	88	91	9,20
208	2955	266	133	2822	2689	0,95	0,91	95	91	93	6,75
209	3005	163	147	2858	2842	0,95	0,95	95	95	95	5,16
210	2650	299	125	2525	2351	0,95	0,89	95	89	92	8,00
212	2748	371	508	2240	2377	0,82	0,86	82	86	84	15,99
213	3251	304	67	3184	2947	0,98	0,91	98	91	94	5,71
214	2262	101	211	2051	2161	0,91	0,96	91	96	93	6,90
215	3363	174	263	3100	3189	0,92	0,95	92	95	94	6,50
217	2208	173	181	2027	2035	0,92	0,92	92	92	92	8,02
219	2287	66	200	2087	2221	0,91	0,97	91	97	94	5,82
220	2048	221	180	1868	1827	0,91	0,89	91	89	90	9,79
221	2427	153	78	2349	2274	0,97	0,94	97	94	95	4,76
222	2483	299	143	2340	2184	0,94	0,88	94	88	91	8,90
223	2605	161	113	2492	2444	0,96	0,94	96	94	95	5,26
228	2053	212	134	1919	1841	0,93	0,90	93	90	92	8,43
230	2256	124	184	2072	2132	0,92	0,95	92	95	93	6,83
231	1573	64	184	1389	1509	0,88	0,96	88	96	92	7,88
232	1780	194	144	1636	1586	0,92	0,89	92	89	91	9,49
233	3079	112	24	3055	2967	0,99	0,96	99	96	98	2,21
234	3785	144	144	3641	3641	0,96	0,96	96	96	96	0,04

CHAPTER
6

DETECTION OF T & P WAVES

Introduction

As mentioned in chapters 1 and 2 the P wave is a rounded peak occurred before the QRS complex and it represents the electric activities of right and left atriums. In some abnormal cases two rounded peak have been presented and indicate an atrial block in the heart, this block lets the impulse cardiac signal to conduct to the left atrium after delay, so the electrical activities of the left and right atriums are represented separately in the ECG. This kind of cardiac block is rare and is not considered in the literature of the automatic ECG analysis and classification. T wave is a rounded peak appeared after the QRS complex, and it represents the second part of the ventricular electrical activity which called the left and right ventricular repolarization.

Therefore, the P and T waves can be found based on the location of the QRS complex. P wave offset is found thanks to backward research in ECG data starting from the QRS onset while the P wave onset thanks to forward research between the offset of precedent T wave and the offset of current P wave. Between the onset and offset of the P wave the peak can be easily identified by examining the amplitude of the ECG data.

For the T wave detection the onset is first searched from the offset of QRS complex to the onset of the successive P wave, then the T wave offset is searched between the onset of current T wave and the onset of the successive P wave. Finally the peak can be identified between the onset and offset.

Sometimes the detected T wave in the previous beat is overlapped with the P wave in the current beat which is incorrect. This is because the P wave is missing in some beats. Therefore the T wave is mistakenly identified as the current P wave during P wave detection.

Different algorithms were proposed in literature (So H H, and Chan K L, 1997, M. Sabry-Rizk, et., 2000) in order to resolve this problem and improve the P and T waves identification. In this chapter we explain some of these algorithms and we propose a new method for the detection of T and P waves. Our method is based on the developed QRS detection algorithm (see chapter 5), and a 6 points derivative function, in order to compute the slope between the current QRS offset and the successive QRS onset. Firstly we identify the current T wave, then it is easy identify the successive P wave between the offset of the current T wave and the onset of the successive QRS. In the same manner the R peak is searched between the onset and offset of the current QRS. A high resolution has been obtained, the R, T, and P peaks were identified in different condition and the method was applied on all the available records of MIT-BIH and EUROPEAN databases.

6.1 P, QRS, and T Waves Detection Utilizing Nonlinearly Synthesised ECG Component (M.Sabry-Rizk, et., 2000)

This algorithm uses the Volterra series⁸. Volterra series has been solved by placing the equations that describe it in a discrete form, into a matrix form.

⁸ It provides an important type of representation for nonlinear models. Volterra series analysis is an extension of small-signal analysis into the field of weakly nonlinear behaviour. In small-signal analysis, the signal is assumed to be small enough that the output can be considered a linear function of the input, in input-output Volterra modelling the output can be represented in the form of a polynomial as:

$$y = a_1x + a_2x^2 + a_3x^3$$

$$y = X h \quad (6.1)$$

Where y consists in the predicted ECG data, h contains the coefficients used to construct the Volterra Kernels, and X is a data matrix constructed from a number of samples previously taken from the data. Figure 6.1 shows a schematic diagram of a predictor /synthesiser. The optimal coefficients in the least mean square sense may then be found by applying:

$$h = X^+ y \quad (6.2)$$

where X^+ is the pseudo-inverse of the data matrix X . The above equation may be solved adaptively using the total least square algorithm.

Figure 6. 1. A diagram of a predictor /synthesiser.

Sufficiently accurate predicted ECG components can be obtained by using the quadratic Volterra (ZGALLAI, W. 2000). The problem of removal of degeneracy in adaptive Volterra networks by dynamic structuring (LYNCH, R.M, et., 1990) is also considered to reduce the number of coefficients by more than a half in both the quadratic Volterra descriptors, to make the algorithm suitable for online applications.

Present algorithm was tested by using the records of MIT-BIH database. The performance is good in some cases of a classic normal sinus rhythm, especially when the signal is not affected by noise. See Figure 6.2.A. In other hand the algorithm fails to recognize the ECG components in the following conditions:

- 1- In the case of noisy ECG signal. Figure 6.2.C. shows that the detection process fails to identify a T wave when the noise is presented.
- 2- When the ventricular cardiac blocks are presented and the PR interval is longer than 0.12 sec, the algorithm fails to identify the T wave from the consecutive P wave, and sometimes fails completely to detect the P and T waves. Figures 6.2.C. shows the performance of present algorithm on a trace of ECG signal with a typical RBBB⁹.

Also, it was noted in all the precedent cases that the algorithm is able to identify the QRS complexes always when the ECG signal is pure and the noise is not presented.

⁹ Right Bundle Branch Block.

6.2 So-Chan Algorithm (So. H. H and Chan K. L., 1997)

This algorithm is based on So-Chan QRS detection algorithm(see chapter 5). The P wave and T wave can be found based on the location of the QRS complex. The slope threshold for P and T waves detection, pt_thresh , is determined by:

$$pt_thresh = pt_param * slope_thresh \quad (6.3)$$

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure 6.2. Performance of nonlinear Volterra series algorithm; **(A)**: a trace of normal rhythms taken from record 100 of MIT-BIH, **(B)**: a trace of paced rhythms + noise taken from record 104 of MIT-BIH, **(C)**: a trace of RBBB rhythms taken from record 124 of MIT-BIH.

Where pt_param is set between 0.1 to 0.3, $slope_thresh$ is computed by using the equation (5.7). The algorithm is to locate the onset, peak, and offset of the P and T waves.

The P wave offset is located by backward search in ECG data, starting from the QRS onset. The search distance is set based on a PR interval less than 0.2 second. If two consecutive data points have their $slope(n) > pt_thresh$, the first data point is identified as the P wave offset. Searched P wave onset is located in the distance preceding the identified QRS complex onset. If two consecutive data points have their $slope(n) > pt_thresh$, the first data point is identified as the P wave onset. Finally between the P wave onset and offset, the peak can be easily identified by examining the amplitude of the ECG data.

For the T wave detection, the onset is first searched. From the end of the QRS complex, if any two consecutive data points having their $slope(n) > pt_thresh$, then the first point is regarded as the T wave onset. Similarly, the T wave offset is found at a further distance. Finally between the onset and offset of the T wave, the peak can be easily identified by examining the amplitude of the ECG data.

Figure 6. 3. Performance of So-Chan algorithm on:
(A): a trace of normal rhythms taken from record 100 of MIT-BIH.
(B): a trace of paced rhythms + noise taken from record 104 of MIT-BIH.
(C): a trace of RBBB rhythms taken from record 124 of MIT-BIH.

We have tested this algorithm by using the MIT-BIH database, and we have noted that the algorithm fails:

1. In detecting correctly the T wave in a normal ECG with slow sloping ST-T segments See Figure 6.3.A.
2. In the presence of noise. See Figure 6.3.B.
3. In the presence of cardiac ventricular block (i.e., RBBB). See Figure 6.3.C.

Regarding the QRS detection we have taken this algorithm as object of study in Chapter 5.

6.3 Joeng Algorithm

A different algorithm is used for the T- and P-wave detection, based on the Joeng algorithm (H.-K. Joeng, et.,1989). Joeng's equation is in non-causal form. Since future values are not available, it has to be transformed into a causal form:

$$D(n) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^8 (4-i)X(n-i)}{60} \quad (6.4)$$

The remaining signal is smoothed with a moving average filter. The algorithm searches for the T-wave after a QRS complex has been detected. The T-wave is expected within a specific time window (see Figure 6.4). The start and duration of the window depends on the RR-interval (P. Laguna et., 1990).

If the RR-interval > 0.7 s:

TwaveWindowBegin = 0.08s after QRS end

TwaveWindowEnd = 0.44s

If RR-interval < 0.7 s:

TwaveWindowBegin = 0.04s after QRS end

TwaveWindowEnd= (0.7RR_interval-0.06) s

Figure 6. 4. Search windows for T- and P-wave Location.

Within this window, the minimum, maximum and order of the derived function slopes are important for detecting the T-wave. Biphasic T-waves can be identified in the same way. The change of slope, as well as the end of the T-wave, is detected based on thresholds. The slope must include positive and negative values and the slope magnitude needs to be at least 0.006 mV/s for a T-wave to be detected.

The P-wave is located between the end of the T-wave and the beginning of a new QRS complex (see Figure 6.4). The detection rule for a P-wave is a positive slope followed by a negative slope. The magnitude of both slopes has to be higher than 0.004 mV/s. The algorithm searches for this combination until the beginning of a new QRS complex is detected. The last wave detected is the P-wave. Figure 6.5 illustrates the performance of Joeng algorithm represented schematically over a trace of normal ECG taken from record 100 of MIT database.

We have tested this algorithm by using the available MIT-BIH database records, and we have noted that the algorithm has a good performance in the cases of normal and paced rhythms, but it fails:

1. In the presence of noise. See Figure 6.6.A.
2. In the presence of cardiac ventricular block (i.e., RBBB, and LBBB). See Figure 6.6.B. and 6.6.B. respectively.

Figure 6. 5. Joeng algorithm represented schematically.

Figure 6. 6. Performance of Joeng algorithm on:
 (A): a trace of paced rhythms + noise taken from record 104 of MIT-BIH.
 (B): a trace of RBBB rhythms taken from record 124 of MIT-BIH.
 (C): a trace of LBBB rhythms taken from record 111 of MIT-BIH.

6.4 Developed Algorithm

In this section we develop a new algorithm for the P&T waves detection. This algorithm is composed of five main stages represented schematically in the Figure 6.7 :

6.4.1 QRS-detection: here we have used the developed QRS detection algorithm (*see chapter 5, section 5.5*) in order to recognize the complex QRS. Figure 6.7.A illustrates the binary output waveforms that correspond to the QRS complexes.

6.4.2 R-detection: this stage applies in the distance within the QRS waveform a recursive six points derivative function (*illustrated in equation 6.5*). Then the algorithm searches the point that corresponds to the R-peak, this point may have a positive or a negative value according to the direction of R-peak. So if the R-peak has a positive upward direction then the R-peak point corresponds to the maximum value of the ECG signal within the QRS waveform, when, in other hand, the sign of derivative function is a negative. Else if the R-peak has a negative downward direction then the R-peak point corresponds to the maximum positive value of the derivative function within the QRS waveform. In order to estimate the direction of the R-peak, we compute the slope within the QRS waveform between the first and middle distance points of the ECG signal, if this slope is negative the R-peak has a downward direction, else if the computed slope is positive the R-peak has an upward direction.

$$y_n = y_{n-1} - [x_{n+1} + 2x_{n+2} + 3x_{n+3} - x_{n-1} - 2x_{n-2} - 3x_{n-3}] \quad (6.5)$$

6.4.3 Determine the RR-intervals: after the R-peaks search and detection, the RR- intervals were determined easily by computing the distances between the two consecutive R-peaks. In order to calculate the RR- intervals in seconds we must divide the results on the sampling frequency.

6.4.4 T-wave detection: firstly the algorithm determines the T-wave window by using the same rule of Joeng algorithm mentioned in the precedent section. Then the T-peak is searched within the determined T-window in the same way that we have used to detect R- peak.

6.4.5 P-wave detection: firstly the algorithm determines the P-wave window between the end of a current T-window and the begin of successive QRS wave form. Then the P-peak is searched within the determined P-window in the same way of the R-peak detection.

Figure 6. 7. Developed P&T waves detection algorithm represented schematically.

Next Figures illustrate the performance of the developed algorithm. In order to illustrate a comparison between the different discussed algorithms, we use here the same set of ECG records .

Figure 6. 8. Performance of developed algorithm on the same famous noisy ECG trace, taken from record 104 of MIT-BIH database. Note that an excellent performance is obtained though the ECG signal is superimposed by noise.

Figure 6. 9. Performance of developed algorithm on the same ECG trace with LBBB rhythms, taken from record 111 of MIT-BIH database

Figure 6. 10. Performance of developed algorithm on the same ECG trace with RBBB rhythms, taken from record 124 of MIT-BIH database.

Developed algorithm realizes an important development in order to recognize automatically the ECG patterns, and extracts their features we need to classify the normal and abnormal ECG cases. In other hand, as we have seen in Figure (6.7), the present algorithm is based on our developed QRS detection algorithm (*which was discussed in chapter 5*). So it realizes approximately the same ratios of sensibility and specificity with a high level of accuracy.

CHAPTER
7

ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS

Introduction

This chapter provides an overview on the Artificial Neural Network *ANN*, as a major paradigm for the Intelligent diagnosis systems, in order to interpret automatically the *ECG* signal. Neural nets have gone through two major development periods – the early 60's and the mid 80's. They were a key development in the machine learning field. ANN were inspired by biological findings relating to the brain behaviour, as a network of units called neurons. The human brain is estimated to have around 10 billion neurons, each connected on average to 10.000 other neurons. Each neuron receives signals through synapses that control the effects of the signals on the neuron. These synaptic connection are believed to play a key role in the brain behaviour. The fundamental building block in an ANN is the mathematical model of a neuron as shown in Figure (7.1). The three basic components of the artificial neurons are :

1. The synapses or connecting links that provide weights, ω_j , to the input values, x_j for $j = 1, \dots, m$.
2. An adder that sums the weighted input values to compute the input to the activation function

$$v = \omega_0 + \sum_{j=1}^m \omega_j x_j, \text{ where } \omega_0 \text{ is called the bias, and it is a numerical value associated with the}$$

neuron. It is convenient to think of the bias as the weight for an input x_0 , whose value is always

$$\text{equal to one, so that } v = \sum_{j=1}^m \omega_j x_j.$$

3. An activation function g (also called a squashing or transfer function) that maps V to $g(V)$ the output value of the neuron. This function is a monotone function. Table 7. I illustrate a complete list of transfer functions.

Figure 7. 1. Mathematical model of a neuron.

While there are numerous different ANN architectures that have been studied by researchers, the most successful application in data mining of neural networks have been multilayer feed forward networks. These are networks in which there is an input layer consisting in nodes that simply accepted the input values, and successive layers of nodes that are neurons as depicted in Figure 7. 1 .

Table 7. I. A complete list of transfer functions.

Function	Description	Representation
Compet	Returns output vectors with elements between 0 and 1, but with their size relations intact. Softmax does not has a derivative function.	
Hard-limit	Limits neuron output to either 0, if the net input argument n is less than 0, or 1, if n is greater than or equal to 0. This function is used to create neurons that make classification decisions.	
Symmetric hard-limit	$g = \text{Symmetric hard-limit}(v) = \begin{cases} (1) \dots & \text{if } v \geq 0 \\ (-1) \dots & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$	
Linear	Applies a linear relation. Neurons of this type are used as linear approximators in linear filters.	
Positive Linear	Applies a linear positive relation.	
Log-sigmoid	Takes an input, which may have any value between plus and minus infinity, and squashes the output into the range 0 to 1.	
Tangent Sigmoid	Takes an input, which may has any value between plus and minus infinity, and squashes the output into the range -1 to 1.	
Radial Basis	The radial basis function has a maximum of 1 when its input is 0. A radial basis neuron acts as a detector that produces 1 whenever the input p is identical to its weight vector p.	
Satlin	Takes an input N, and returns values of N truncated into the interval [0, 1].	
Symmetrical Satlin	Takes an input N, and returns values of N truncated into the interval [-1, 1].	
Softmax	Takes one input argument, and returns output vectors with elements between 0 and 1, but with their size relations intact.	
Triangular Basis	Takes one input N, and returns each element of N passed through a radial basis function.	

The neurons outputs in a layer are neurons inputs in the next layer. The last layer is called the output layer. Layers between the input and output layers are known as hidden layers. Figure 7.2 is a diagram for this architecture.

In a supervised setting where a neural network is used to predict a numerical quantity there is one neuron in the output layer and its output is the prediction. When the network is used in the classification, the output layer has typically as many nodes as the number of classes and the output layer node with the largest output value gives the network's estimate of the class for a given input. In the special case of two classes it is common to have just one node in the output layer, the classification between the two classes being made by applying a cut-off to the output value at the node.

Figure 7. 2. Architecture of multilayer neural networks.

7.1 Single Layer Network

Let us begin by examining neural networks with just one neurons layer (output layer only, no hidden layer). The simplest network consists in just one neuron with the function g chosen to be the identity function, $g(v) = v$

for all v . In this case notice that network output is $\sum_{j=0}^m \omega_j x_j$, a linear function of the input vector x components

x_j . If we are modelling the dependent variable y using multiple linear regression, we can interpret the neural

network as a structure that predicts a value \hat{y} for a given input vector x with the weights being the coefficients. If we chose these weights to minimize the mean square error using observations in a training set, these weights would simply be the least squares estimates of coefficients. The weights in the neural net are also designed to minimize mean square error in a training data set. There is, however, a different orientation in the case of neural nets: the weights are “learned”. The network is presented with a training data one by one and the weights are revised after each case in attempt to minimize the mean square error. This process of incremental adjustment of weights is based on the error made on training cases and is known as ‘training’ of the neural net. The most universally used dynamic updating algorithm for the neural net version of linear regression is known as the Widrow-Hoff rule or the least-mean-square (LMS) algorithm. It is simply stated. Let $x(i)$ denote the input vector x for the i^{th} case used to train the network, and the weights *before* this case is presented to the net by the vector

$\omega(i)$. The updating rule is $\omega(i+1) = \omega(i) + \eta (y(i) - \hat{y}(i)) x(i)$ with $\omega(0) = 0$. It can be shown that if the

network is trained in this way by repeatedly presenting test data observations one by one then for suitably small (absolute) values of η the network will learn (converge to) the optimal values of ω . Note that the training data may have to be presented several times $\omega(i)$ to define the optimal ω . The advantage of dynamic updating is that the network tracks moderate time trends in the underlying linear model quite effectively.

If we use the single layer neural network to classify in c classes, we would use c nodes in the output layer. If we think of classical discriminant analysis in neural network terms, the coefficients in Fisher's classification functions give us weights for the network, optimal if the input vectors come from Multivariate Normal Distributions (MND) with a common covariance matrix.

To classify in two classes the linear optimization approach that we examined in class, it can be viewed as choosing optimal weights in a single layer neural network using the appropriate objective function.

Maximum likelihood coefficients for logistic regression can also be considered as weights in a neural network to minimize a function of the residuals called the deviance. In this case the logistic function $g(v) = \left(\frac{e^v}{1 + e^v}\right)$ is the activation function for the output node.

7.2 Multilayer Neural Network

Multilayer networks are undoubtedly the most popular networks used in application. While it is possible to consider many activation functions. In practice it has been found that the logistic (also called the sigmoid)

function $g(v) = \frac{e^v}{1 + e^v}$ as the activation function (or minor variants such as the *tanh* function), works best. In fact

the revival of interest in neural nets was sparked by successes in training neural networks using this function in place of the historically (biologically inspired) step function (the "perceptron"). Notice that using a linear function, it does not achieve anything in multilayer networks that is beyond what can be done with single layer networks with linear activation function. The practical logistic function arises from the fact that it is almost linear in the range where g is between 0.1 and 0.9 but has a squashing effect on very small or very large values of v . In theory it is sufficient to consider networks with two layers and, this is certainly the case for many applications. There is, however, a number of situations where three and sometimes four and five layers have been more effective. To predict the output node is often given a linear activation function to provide forecasts that are not limited to the zero to one range. An alternative is to scale the output to the linear part (0.1 to 0.9) of the logistic function. Unfortunately there is no clear theory to guide us to choose the number of nodes in each hidden layer in indeed the number of layers. The common practice is to use trial and error, although there are schemes to combine optimization methods like as an example genetic algorithms for network training for these parameters. Since trial and error is a necessary part of neural net applications, it is important to understand the standard method used to train a multilayer network: backpropagation. It is no exaggeration to say that the backpropagation algorithm speed made of neural nets a practical tool, in the way that the simplex method made of linear optimization a practical tool. The revival of strong interest in neural nets in the mid 80s was in large due to the efficiency of the backpropagation algorithm.

7.3 Backward Propagation Algorithm

We'll discuss the backpropagation algorithm to classify problems. There is a minor adjustment to predict problems where we are trying to predict a continuous numerical value. In that situation we change the activation function for output layer neurons to the identity function that has *output value=input value*. (An alternative is to rescale and recenter the logistic function to permit the outputs to be approximately linear in the range of dependent variable values).

The backpropagation algorithm cycles executes in two distinct passes, a forward pass followed by a backward pass through the layers of the network. The algorithm alternates between these passes several times as it scans the training data. Typically, the training data has to be scanned several times before the networks "learn" to do a good classification.

7.3.1 Forward pass: Computation of outputs of all the neurons in the network

The algorithm starts with the first hidden layer using as input values the independent variables of a case (often called an exemplar in the machine learning community) from the training data set. The neuron outputs are computed for all neurons in the first hidden layer by performing the relevant sum and activation function evaluation. These outputs are the inputs for neurons in the second hidden layer. Moreover the relevant sum and activation function calculations are performed to compute the outputs of second layer neurons. This continues layer by layer until we reach the output layer and compute the outputs for this layer. These output values constitute the neural net's guess at the value of the dependent variable. If we are using the neural net for classification. (if $c=2$, we use just one output node with a cut-off value to map an numerical output value to one of the two classes). Let us denote by ω_{ij} the weight of the connection from node i to node j . The values of ω_{ij} are initialized to small (generally random) numbers in the range 0.00 ± 0.05 . These weights are adjusted to new values in the backward pass as described below.

7.3.2 Back pass: Propagation of error and adjustment of weights

This phase begins with the computation of error for every neuron in the output layer. A popular error function is the squared difference between O_k the output of the node k and Y_k the target of that node. The target value is just 1 for the output node corresponding to the class of the exemplar and zero for other output nodes. (In practice it has been found better to use values of 0.9 and 0.1 respectively). For each output layer node compute its error terms as:

$$\delta_k = O_k(1 - O_k)(Y_k - O_k) \quad (7.1)$$

These errors are used to adjust the weights of the connections between the last-but-one layer of the network and the output layer. The new value of the weight ω_{jk} of the connection from node j to node k is given by:

$$\omega_{ij}^{new} = \omega_{ij}^{old} + \eta O_j \delta_k \quad (7.2)$$

Here η is an important tuning parameter that is chosen from trial and error by repeated runs on the training data. Typical values for η are in the range 0.1 to 0.9. Low values give slow but steady learning, high values give erratic learning and may lead to unstable network.

The process is repeated for the connections between nodes in the last hidden layer and the last-but-one hidden layer. The weight for the connection between nodes i and j corresponding to (7. 2): $\omega_{ij}^{new} = \omega_{ij}^{old} + \eta O_i \delta_j$ where $\delta_j = O_j(1 - O_j) \sum_k \omega_{jk} \delta_k$, for each node j in the last hidden layer. The backward

propagation of weight adjustments along these lines continues until we reach the input layer. At this time we have a new set of weights on which we can make a new forward pass when presented with a training data observation.

7.3.3 Multiple local optima and epochs

The backpropagation algorithm is a version of the steepest descent optimization method applied to the problem of finding the weights that minimize the error function of the network output. Due to the complexity of the function and the large numbers of weights that are being “trained” as the network “learns”, there is no assurance that the backpropagation algorithm (and indeed any practical algorithm) will find the optimum weights that minimize error. The procedure can get stuck at a local minimum. It has been found useful to randomize the cases presentation order in a training set between different scans. It is possible to speed the algorithm by batching, which is updating the weights for several exemplars in a pass. However, at least the extreme case of using the entire training data set on each update has been found to get stuck frequently at poor local minima. A single scan of all cases in the training data is called an epoch. Many applications of feedforward networks and backpropagation require several epochs before errors are reasonably small. A number of modifications has been proposed to reduce the epochs needed to train a neural net. One commonly employed idea is to incorporate a momentum term that injects some inertia in the weight adjustment on the backward pass. This is done by adding a term to the expression for weight adjustment for that connection. This fraction is called the momentum control parameter. High values of the momentum parameter will force successive weight adjustments to be in similar direction. Another idea is to vary the adjustment parameter δ so that it decreases as the number of epochs increases. Intuitively this is useful because it avoids to overfit that is more likely to occur at later epochs than earlier ones.

7.3.4 Overfitting and the choice of training epochs

A weakness of the neural networks is that it can be easily overfitted, causing the error rate on validation data to be much larger than the error rate on the training data. It is therefore important not to overtrain the data. A good method for choosing the number of training epochs is to use the validation data set periodically to compute the error rate for it while the network is being trained. The validation error decreases in the early epochs of backpropagation but after a while it begins to increase. The point of minimum validation error is a good indicator of the best number of epochs for training and the weights at that stage are likely to provide the best error rate in new data.

7.4 Quasi-Newton Algorithms

Newton's method is an alternative to the conjugate gradient methods for fast optimization. The basic step of Newton's method is:

$$\omega_{ij}^{new} = \omega_{ij}^{old} - A_{ij}^{-1} g_{ij} \quad (7.3)$$

where A_{ij} is the Hessian matrix¹⁰ (second derivatives) of the performance index at the current values of the weights and biases. Newton's method often converges faster than conjugate gradient methods. Unfortunately it is complex and expensive to compute the Hessian matrix for feedforward neural networks. There is a class of algorithms that is based on Newton's method, but which doesn't require calculation of second derivatives. These are called quasi-Newton (or secant) methods. They update an approximate Hessian matrix at each iteration of the

¹⁰ The Hessian matrix is the matrix of second derivatives of the energy with respect to geometry.

algorithm. The update is computed as a function of the gradient. The quasi-Newton method that has been very successful in published studies is the Broyden, Fletcher, Goldfarb, and Shanno (BFGS) update.

7.4.1 One Step Secant algorithm

Since the BFGS algorithm requires more storage and computation in each iteration, it needs a secant approximation with smaller storage and computation requirements. The one step secant (OSS) does not store the complete Hessian matrix; it assumes that at each iteration, the previous Hessian was the identity matrix. This has the additional advantage that the new search direction can be calculated without computing a matrix inverse.

7.5 Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm

Like the quasi-Newton methods, the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm was designed to approach second-order training speed without having to compute the Hessian matrix. When the performance function has the form of a sum of squares (as is typical in training feedforward networks), the Hessian matrix can be approximated as and the gradient can be computed as:

$$H = J^T J \quad (7.4)$$

and the gradient can be computed as:

$$g = J^T e \quad (7.5)$$

where J is the Jacobian matrix¹¹ that contains first derivatives of the network errors with respect to the weights and biases, and e is a vector of network errors. The Jacobian matrix can be computed through a standard backpropagation technique that is much less complex than computing the Hessian matrix.

The Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm uses this approximation to the Hessian matrix in the following Newton-like update:

$$\omega_{ij}^{new} = \omega_{ij}^{old} - [J^T J + \mu I]^{-1} J^T e \quad (7.6)$$

When the scalar μ is zero, this is just Newton's method, using the approximate Hessian matrix. When μ is large, this becomes gradient descent with a small step size. Newton's method is faster and more accurate near an error minimum, so its aim is to shift towards Newton's method as quickly as possible. Thus, μ is decreased after each successful step (reduction in performance function) and is increased only when a tentative step would increase the performance function. In this way, the performance function will always be reduced at each iteration of the algorithm.

7.6 Bayesian Algorithm :

Bayesian neural networks can be found in related literature (D. Gao, Y. Kinouchi, K. Ito, X. Zhao (2003), D. Gao, Y. Kinouchi, K. Ito, X. Zhao (2005)). In the following paragraph we explain how to realize a Bayesian artificial model. Assume we have the training set D , consisting of N input-output pairs:

$$D = \left[(x^n, y^n) \mid n = 1, 2, \dots, N \right] \quad (7.7)$$

where x is an input vector consisting of I elements, and y is the corresponding class label consisting of K classes. The goal is to use an ANN to model the input-output relation ($y = k \mid x$). Let we have 6 classes $k \in (k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4, k_5, k_6)$. To realize a logistic regression model based on a Bayesian method we estimated the class probability for the given input by: $P(Y=k \mid X)$.

¹¹ The Jacobian matrix is the matrix of all first-order partial derivatives of a vector-valued function.

Assume that the outputs for the summation operation and the sigmoid activation function, in the hidden and output neurons, denoted by S_j , S_k respectively can be written as follows:

$$S_j = \tanh \left(\sum_i \omega_{ij} X_i + \omega_{j0} \right) \quad (7.8)$$

$$S_k = \left(\sum_j \omega_{kj} S_j + \omega_{k0} \right) \quad (7.9)$$

where \tanh is the tangent hyperbolic function. ω_{ij} denotes the weight matrix in the input layer and ω_{kj} the weight matrix in the output layer. To ensure that the outputs can be interpreted as probabilities, logistic regression is used to model the risk (or probability) of occurrence of arrhythmia. Let $P(Y=k|X)$ be the probability of the event $Y=1$, given the input X . This is modelled by function of a network output y by:

$$P(Y=k|X) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-S_k)} \quad (7.10)$$

The logistic regression model is simply a non linear transformation of the linear regression. The 'logistic' distribution is a *S-shaped* distribution function which is similar to the standard-normal distribution (which results in a probit regression model) but easier to work within most applications. The logistic distribution constrains the estimated probabilities to lay between 0 and 1.

The final part of the system is a multi-layer perceptron neural network, trained using the BNN algorithm. The network is optimized using a log-likelihood cost function, given by :

$$C(\omega) = -\frac{1}{k} \sum_k \sum_i Y_i(k) \ln[(Y=k|X)] \quad (7.11)$$

Where $\omega = (\omega_{ij}, \omega_{jk})$ is the vector of network weights. To minimize the cost function between the actual and desired outputs of the network, the BNN algorithm passes the information from the output neuron backwards to all hidden units to form error terms which are used to update the weights of the multi-layer network.

**CHAPTER
8****A NEW METHOD TO FILTER THE ECG SIGNAL****Introduction:**

Analogue or digital filters are widely applied in order to reduce the influence of interference superimposed on the ECG. Early work on noise and artefact reduction in the ECG used either temporal and spatial averaging technique (Paul JS, et, al., 2000). The temporal averaging method requires a large number of time frames for effective noise reduction, while the main drawback of spatial averaging is the physical limitation of placing a large number of electrodes in the same region. Besides linear noise filtering, several adaptive filtering methods have been proposed for separation and identification of the component waves from the noisy ECGs (Ju-Won Lee et., al., 2005, and Robert S.H et., al., 2001). The quasi periodic pattern of the cardiac signal has also been exploited by synchronising the parameter of the filter with the period of the signal. Other methods include subspace rotations, neural networks, and bi-spectral analysis. Many of these methods to filter out the noise and the artefacts from ECG are only partially successful, because they fail to remove the interference when it is within the same frequency range as the cardiac signal. Our method uses a dataset of suitable patterns, and estimates from this dataset an adaptive pattern, for every detected beat of the *ECG* signal. Then a neural network based on a back-propagation method is used to minimize the error between the estimated pattern and the detected beat signal.

In this Chapter we present the development of a robust electrocardiogram(*ECG*) filter, based on an intelligent pattern analysis method. Our method proceeds in three main steps: 1) we create a dataset of thirteen one beat ECG patterns, in which seven patterns are artificially produced, five patterns are taken from MIT BIH database and the last pattern is taken by averaging thirty consecutive beats of the original signal, representing the “mean beat”; 2) for every original beat the algorithm chooses from our dataset a suitable pattern which must realize the maximum correlation ratio with the original one, and this ratio must be above 90%; 3) the algorithm fits the error between every original beat and its estimated pattern, by using a neural network based on the backpropagation method. Data were obtained from the 44 available records of **MIT BIH** database, and the **ST-T EUROBEAN** databases. Different records in these databases are corrupted from various type of noise and artefacts. Noise is defined to be a part of the real signal that confuses analysis (such as the muscle movement or the electromyography noise). Artefact is defined to be any distortion of the signal caused by the recording process (such as electrode movement).

Our ECG filter exhibits a good performance and it doesn't lead to a reduction in the amplitudes of the ECG component. Especially when it filters the artefacts superimposed on the ECG signal, which are random in nature, expand over a large rang of frequency, and have a frequency component within the range of the ECG signal components.

8.1 Dataset of Patterns

We obtained thirteen patterns from three different resources: seven were artificially produced through the algorithm proposed by (G. Clifford (2004)), five were taken from the MIT-BIH database[5], and the last one was computed as the average of the thirty consecutive beats to which the ECG beat to be filtered belongs. The

patterns obtained from the first and second resource are fixed during the processing of the algorithm, whereas the last pattern changes because it is taken from the signal as it is processed by our algorithm. In the following we explain how we have created the present dataset.

8.1.1 Extract patterns from ECG signal databases

Five different patterns were extracted from the available records of MIT-BIH arrhythmia database. Each one represents a type of arrhythmic cardiac beat signal (Left and Right Bundle Branch Block, Paced Rhythm, or Bi-phasic QRS complex). Figure 8. 2 -B. illustrates these patterns.

8.1.2 Generate another ECG patterns using an artificial model

Seven patterns were generated using the non-linear artificial model proposed by Clifford, in which the ECG signal is generated by resolving the z-axis of an evolving trajectory through the 3D (x, y, z) space leads.

In order to realize a realistic ECG, the trajectory is derived by integrating three ordinary differential equations:

$$\dot{x} = \alpha x - \omega y \quad (8.1)$$

$$\dot{y} = \alpha y + \omega x \quad (8.2)$$

$$\dot{z} = - \sum_{i \in (P,Q,R,S,T)} a_i \Delta\theta_i \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta\theta_i^2}{2b_i}\right) - (z - z_0) \quad (8.3)$$

over a suitable set of parameters. Here $\alpha = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$

$\Delta\theta = (\theta - \theta_i) \bmod 2\pi$, $\theta = \alpha \tan^{-1}(y/x)$ and ω is the angular frequency around the limit cycle, the θ_i are the angles of the extrema (P,Q,R,S, and T) around the limit cycle, see Figure 8. 1.

Figure 8. 1. A limit cycle in the x-y plane is perturbed by fixed point extrema P, Q, R, S, T to produce a three-dimensional limit cycle.

The a_i are the repulsive strength of the extrema, and the b_i define the Gaussian region of influence that each of the extrema have. θ_i , b_i , and a_i therefore define the morphology of the ECG. Four of generated patterns have the P wave, and three of them haven't it. The values of θ_i and b_i are illustrated in the Table (8. I)

and they are the same for all the seven generated patterns when Table (8. II) contains the a_i values for every pattern generated. The morphologies of generated patterns are showed in Figure 8. 2 -A .

8.1.3 Extract an adaptive local pattern from the ECG signal

This pattern changes when the algorithm is proceeding along the original signal. since every 30 beats, the algorithm synchronizes the extrema (P-QRS-T) of all beats, using the FFT interpolating method and estimates a

new pattern, which represents the mean of these different 30 beats (fourteen before the studied beat and fifteen after it).

	P	Q	R	S	T
θ_i	-0.389π	-0.083π	0	0.083π	0.556π
b_i	0.25	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.4

Table 8. I. Values of θ_i and b_i .

Pattern	P	Q	R	S	T
(1)Normal	1.2	5	30	-7.5	0.75
(2)Negative R	1.2	5	-30	7.5	0.75
(3)Negative T	1.2	-5	30	-7.5	-0.75
(4)Negative R&T	1.2	-5	-30	-7.5	-0.75
(5)Negative R	0	5	-30	7.5	0.75
(6)Negative T	0	-5	30	-7.5	-0.75
(7)Negative R&T	0	-5	-30	-7.5	-0.75

Table 8. II. Values of a_i for every pattern.

Figure 8. 2. **A.** Seven heart beat patterns generated, using the artificial model. **B.** The other five patterns obtained from MIT database.

8.2 Processing Method

The algorithm works over 30 beats each time in this manner:

8.2.1 Pre-Filtering and Through Detection of ECG

The aim of this process is to reduce the influence of interference superimposed on the ECG and detects the QRS complex, P, and T waves. In Chapters 5, and 6 we have developed a method for this purpose (see sections 5.5, and 6.4 respectively).

Then the algorithm uses another time the FFT method to synchronize the externa (P-QRS-T) of all our patterns. with that of every original beat.

8.2.2 Estimate the adaptive pattern

In order to estimate the best pattern for every original beat, we compute the correlation factor between the original beat and all the estimated patterns by using the equation (8. 4).

$$(Cf) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N (X_{(n)} - \bar{X})^2 (Y_{(n)} - \bar{Y})^2}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=1}^N (X_{(n)} - \bar{X})^2 \sum_{n=1}^N (Y_{(n)} - \bar{Y})^2}} \quad (8. 4)$$

where:

$X_{(n)}, \bar{X}, Y_{(n)}, \bar{Y}$: represent the original beat, the mean value of original beat, the pattern, and the mean value of the pattern respectively.

Now the pattern which realizes the maximum Cf is taken as an estimated pattern of the original beat.

8.2.3 Backpropagation algorithm for fitting the errors

A neural network based on the back propagation method is used, in order to fitting the error between the estimated pattern and the presented beat signal. This neural network contains a one tangent sigmoid hidden layer, and a linear output layer, in addition to the input layer. The topology of this network is shown in the Figure 8. 3.

Backpropagation method was created by generalizing the Widrow-Hoff learning rule to multiple-layer networks and non-linear differentiable transfer functions.

Figure 8. 3. Neural network topology.

The simplest implementation of Backpropagation learning is to update the network weights and biases in the direction, in which the performance function decreases most rapidly the negative of the gradient.

One iteration of this algorithm can be written:

$$WB_{j+1} = WB_j - \eta g_j \quad (8.5)$$

where WB_j is a vector of current weights and biases, g_j is the current gradient, and η is the learning rate.

Backpropagation method is available in chapter 7 (see section 7.3).

However, here we take the best estimated pattern as input vector, and the corresponding original beat as a target vector. Then the network is trained, in order to fit the error between them. Finally it is simulated from the estimated pattern on the input in order obtain the filtered signal on its output. See Figure 8. 4.

8.3 Results and Discussion

A method for filtering the ECG signal was described in this chapter, and a high performance was obtained when we have applied it on the available ECG data, and unlike other classical ECG filters proposed in the literature, the present one guarantees a looseness in the components of the ECG, especially when the noise overlapping these components in the plane of frequency.

Proposed neural network with biases, two hidden tangent sigmoid layers, and a linear output layer are able to approximate the estimated pattern very well. In the Table 8. III we illustrate the means of the correlation ratios which were obtained in some ECG records of the MIT, and ST-T European databases.

Figure 8. 4. Some examples illustrate the performance of developed filter on a different one beat ECG taken from MIT-BIH database.

In some individual cases, especially when the original 30 beats haven't an enough degree of similarity in their morphologies, the method can't realize the requested correlation ratio (90%) between some of original beat and the corresponding estimated patterns, since, the pattern that represents the mean of these beats fails to become our estimated pattern, because in this case the correlation results a low ratio, due to the dissimilarity. In the other hand, our dataset has only the most common and frequent (12) patterns, the morphologies of these patterns may be not sufficient to estimate the correlated pattern in the case which we have explained above. So we are working now to enrich our data set in order to contain more patterns by using the artificial model, and another available ECG data, in this manner we may develop the accuracy of our pattern recognition method.

Figure 8. 6 illustrates some results of our method on different records of the MIT, and ST-T databases.

Table 8. III. Means of correlation ratios obtained from all the studied ECG records (MIT-BIH, and ST- European database).

MIT		ST-T	
Record	Mean ratio	Record	Mean ratio
100	0,98	e0104	0,97
101	0,97	e0105	0,92
102	0,92	e0106	0,84
103	0,91	e0107	0,88
104	0,92	e0111	0,89
105	0,91	e0113	0,91
106	0,84	e0115	0,79
107	0,93	e0119	0,92
108	0,82	e0121	0,81
109	0,92	e0123	0,8
111	0,82	e0125	0,91
112	0,96	e0127	0,92
113	0,89	e0129	0,91
114	0,91	e0133	0,84
115	0,88	e0139	0,86
116	0,94	e0147	0,83
117	0,87	e0151	0,81
118	0,92	e0155	0,84
119	0,95	e0159	0,87
121	0,93	e0161	0,81
122	0,94	e0163	0,80
123	0,92	e0203	0,88
124	0,95	e0205	0,87
200	0,88	e0207	0,90
201	0,92	e0211	0,91
202	0,94	e0213	0,91
203	0,92	e0303	0,94
205	0,91	e0305	0,96
207	0,92	e0403	0,95
208	0,84	e0405	0,94
209	0,88	e0409	0,90
210	0,92	e0411	0,91
212	0,89	e0413	0,88
213	0,91	e0415	0,99
214	0,98	e0417	0,92
215	0,92	e0501	0,93
217	0,97	e0509	0,94
219	0,94	e0515	0,95
220	0,93	e0601	0,92
221	0,92	e0603	0,93
222	0,94	e0605	0,92
223	0,95	e0607	0,93
228	0,93	e0609	0,94
230	0,93	e0611	0,93
231	0,89	e0613	0,91
232	0,95	e0615	0,94
233	0,86	e0801	0,89
234	0,92	e0817	0,88
	----	e01301	0,85
Mean	0,915	Mean	0,895

Figure 8. 5. The mean values of Correlation ratios realized between our dataset patterns and the different patterns presented in the available records of MIT-BIH and ST-T European databases.

Figure 8. 6. Filter performance represented over different ECG traces; **A, B, C,** and **D** report from the upper to the lower 10 sec tracings original ECG signal, estimated pattern, and filtered signal. ECG traces in **A, B** were taken from the MIT- BIH database, records 104 and 106 respectively. Where traces in **C** and **D** were taken from ST-T European database, records 0108 and 0114 respectively.

CHAPTER
9

HEART RATE VARIABILITY & ISCHEMIC EPISODES

Introduction

Heart rate variability is an active topic of the ECG signal analysis, since a correspondence between specific physiological components and the frequency spectrum has been identified. Specifically, these two components are the sympathetic and parasympathetic neural systems¹², which originate in the brain and affect organs throughout the body. The activity of the sympathetic system is heightened in situations requiring a large but temporary expenditure of energy, as the energy needed by the brain to process information. The activity of the parasympathetic system is heightened during times of slow but continuous energy expenditure, as processing food in the stomach. The heart is also affected by these two systems, and as expected the sympathetic system speeds up the heart rate and the parasympathetic system slows down the heart rate. Heart rate variability is the result of the intricate interplay of these two systems.

Behind spectral analysis of the heart rate variability there are the sympathetic and parasympathetic system influences that can be extracted and attributed to one of the two systems. Incidentally (and ironically), the sympathetic system has been identified to modulate the heart rate at a lower frequency than the parasympathetic system. Thus, recent publications (A. Smrdel, et, 2006) on the topic have dealt with the spectral and time-frequency analysis of the heart rate variability, hoping to be able to characterize the heart rate well enough in order to diagnose illnesses in patients that cause suppression or amplification of the variability of the heart rate.

The heart rate may be increased by slow acting sympathetic activity or decreased by fast acting parasympathetic (vagal) activity. The balance between the effects of the sympathetic and parasympathetic systems, the two opposite acting branches of the autonomic nervous system, is referred to as the sympatho-vagal balance and it's reflected in the beat-to-beat (R-to-R) changes of the cardiac cycle. The heart rate is given by the reciprocal of the RR-interval in units of beats per minute. Spectral analysis of the RR is typically used to estimate the effect of the sympathetic and parasympathetic modulation of the RR-intervals, and especially in the case of short-time ECG.

To analyze the heart rate variability there are two steps: the first step is accomplished by the ECG filtering and processing described in the previous chapters. By detecting where the heart beats occur, the heart rate as a function of time can be determined. Using these heart rate studies of the variation in heart rate with time can be done. Some of the methods applied on the heart rate are listed below:

9.1 Time-domain Methods

The time-domain parameters are the simplest ones calculated directly from the raw RR interval, or HR time series. The simplest time domain measures are the mean and standard deviation of the RR intervals. The standard deviation of RR intervals (SDNN) describes the overall variation in the RR interval signal whilst the standard deviation of the differences between consecutive RR intervals (SDSD) describes short-term variation. A

¹²The sympathetic nervous system (SNS) is a part of the autonomic nervous system (ANS), which also includes the parasympathetic nervous system (PNS). The sympathetic nervous system can accelerate heart rate; widen bronchial passages; decrease motility (movement) of the large intestine; constrict blood vessels; increase peristalsis in the esophagus; cause pupil dilation, piloerection (goose bumps) and perspiration (sweating); and raise blood pressure. Afferent messages carry sensations such as heat, cold, or pain. Where the parasympathetic system conserves energy as it slows the heart rate, increases intestinal and gland activity, and relaxes sphincter muscles in the gastrointestinal tract.

stationary time series SDDSD equals the root mean square (RMS) of the differences between consecutive RR intervals (RMSSD). There are also other commonly used parameters like NN50 which is the number of consecutive RR intervals differing more than 50 ms. The pNN50 is the percentage value of NN50 intervals. The prefix NN stands for normal-to-normal intervals (i.e. intervals between consecutive QRS complexes resulting from sinus node depolarizations). In practice, RR and NN intervals usually appear to be same. Furthermore, there are some geometric measures like the HRV triangular index and TINN that are determined from the histogram of RR intervals. See Figures 9.1 and 9.2.

Figure 9. 1. An example of the RR time parameters
(A) Mean and Standard Deviation values computed on moving window of 50 points.
(B) RR histogram.
 HRV curve was taken from the record 100 of the MIT-BIH Database.

Figure 9. 2. An example of the HRV time parameters
(C) Mean and Standard Deviation values computed on moving window of 400 points.
(D) HRV histogram.
 HRV curve was taken from the record 20031 of the Long-Term ST Database.

In this chapter we add another indicative parameter to the time-domain methods. This parameter is the ratio between two consecutive RR-periods calculated as the following:

$$Ratio_i = \left(\frac{RR_i - RR_{i+1}}{RR_i + RR_{i+1}} \right) \quad (9. 1)$$

We have used this ratio to detect the premature cardiac beats.

9.2 A Developed Algorithm to the Premature Cardiac Beat (PCB) Detection

The aim of this algorithm is to detect automatically the premature (atrio or ventricular) cardiac beat in a trace of ECG signal. In order to identify the premature beat we have computed the ratio function by using the Equation (9.1) for all our dataset records, and then the ECG signal beats were classified by using the next rule:

If $Ratio_i \leq \text{critical value}$ then $beat_i$ is a premature beat else $beat_i$ isn't.

A suitable criteria is about (-0.1) and it was stabilized statistically by observing the results of classification, that correspond to four different critical ratio values: -0.05, -0.1, -0.15, and -0.2 (see the correspondents confusion matrices¹³ reported in the Tables 9. I, II, III, IV respectively).

Our dataset records were chosen from MIT-BIH database by considering three main factors:

- 1- Patient's sex: just male, because we have noted that in some individual normal cases, some women have a prolonged QT interval. So the RR-interval is prolonged and, in these cases, is not indicative in order to recognize the premature in the cardiac rhythm.
- 2- Age: between 40-90 years, because patients in this range are statistically the most struck by this type of arrhythmia.
- 3- Medical history: all the patients in our dataset are stricken by analogue or similar pathologies.

Figure 9.3.A illustrates the percentage number of cardiac beats in our dataset with respect to the total cardiac beats of MIT-BIH database, where Figure 9.3. B illustrates the percent distribution of premature beats in our dataset with respect to others.

Figure 9.3. A. Percent ratios between our dataset and other records in MIT-BIH database.
B. Percentage ratios between premature and other beats in our dataset.

To calculate the percentage error the normal and pathological cases must be equally distributed. In order to ensure this purpose we use two weights ω_p for abnormal cases and ω_n the normal one, so $\omega_n C_n = \omega_p C_p$

Let $\omega_n = 1 \Rightarrow \omega_p = \frac{C_n}{C_p}$, the percentage error is:

$$Err = \frac{Fp + \omega_p Fn}{Cn + \omega_p Cp} \quad (9.2)$$

¹³ A confusion matrix is a form of contingency table showing the differences between the true and predicted classes for a set of labelled (C_p , C_n , R_p , R_n , T_p , F_p , T_n , F_n , Se , Sp , Acc , Err , $P+$, $N+$ are correct positive, correct negative, predictive positive, predictive negative, true positive, false positive, true negative, false negative, sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, error, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value, respectively).

Table 9. I. The classification of PCB results that correspond to the critical value (- 0, 05).

Record	Total beats	Cp	Cn	Rp	Rn	Tp	Fp	Tn	Fn
100	2273	34	2239	1088	1185	34	1054	1185	0
107	2137	59	2078	1052	1085	59	993	1085	0
109	2532	40	2492	1223	1309	40	1183	1309	0
112	2539	2	2537	1192	1347	2	1190	1347	0
116	2412	110	2302	1043	1369	110	933	1369	0
118	2288	122	2166	1077	1211	122	955	1211	0
122	2476	0	2476	1132	1344	0	1132	1344	0
200	2601	858	1743	1180	1421	858	322	1421	0
201	2000	375	1625	913	1087	375	538	1087	0
202	2136	75	2061	934	1202	75	859	1202	0
203	2980	447	2533	1311	1669	447	864	1669	0
205	2656	85	2571	1204	1452	85	1119	1452	0
209	3005	384	2621	1419	1586	384	1035	1586	0
213	3251	610	2641	1491	1760	610	881	1760	0
214	2262	257	2005	1055	1207	257	798	1207	0
217	2208	162	2046	1021	1187	162	859	1187	0
219	2287	205	2082	1029	1258	205	824	1258	0
233	3079	849	2230	1472	1607	849	623	1607	0
Total	45122	4674	40448	20836	24286	4674	16162	24286	0
Se=100%		Sp=60%		Err=40%		Acc=60%		P+ =0,22	
N+=1									

Table 9. II. The classification of PCB results that correspond to the critical value (- 0, 1).

Record	Total beats	Cp	Cn	Rp	Rn	Tp	Fp	Tn	Fn
100	2273	34	2239	41	2232	34	7	2232	0
107	2137	59	2078	75	2062	54	21	2057	5
109	2532	40	2492	53	2479	35	18	2474	5
112	2539	2	2537	19	2520	2	17	2520	0
116	2412	110	2302	132	2280	101	31	2271	9
118	2288	122	2166	136	2152	117	19	2147	5
122	2476	0	2476	7	2469	0	7	2469	0
200	2601	858	1743	920	1681	839	81	1662	19
201	2000	375	1625	411	1589	360	51	1574	15
202	2136	75	2061	101	2035	70	31	2030	5
203	2980	447	2533	488	2492	403	85	2448	44
205	2656	85	2571	91	2565	76	15	2556	9
209	3005	384	2621	421	2584	367	54	2567	17
213	3251	610	2641	688	2563	578	110	2531	32
214	2262	257	2005	309	1953	255	54	1951	2
217	2208	162	2046	191	2017	144	47	1999	18
219	2287	205	2082	210	2077	185	25	2057	20
233	3079	849	2230	891	2188	799	92	2138	50
Total	45122	4674	40448	5184	39938	4419	765	39683	255
Se =0,95%		Sp = 0,98		Err = 0,036		Acc = 0,964%		P+ = 0,85	
N+= 0,99									

Table9. III. The classification of PCB results that correspond to the critical value (-0, 15).

Record	Total beats	Cp	Cn	Rp	Rn	Tp	Fp	Tn	Fn
100	2273	34	2239	34	2239	34	0	2239	0
107	2137	59	2078	62	2075	51	11	2067	8
109	2532	40	2492	48	2484	34	14	2478	6
112	2539	2	2537	10	2529	2	8	2529	0
116	2412	110	2302	119	2293	99	20	2282	11
118	2288	122	2166	117	2171	116	1	2165	6
122	2476	0	2476	6	2470	0	6	2470	0
200	2601	858	1743	890	1711	820	70	1673	38
201	2000	375	1625	397	1603	353	44	1581	22
202	2136	75	2061	92	2044	67	25	2036	8
203	2980	447	2533	466	2514	394	72	2461	53
205	2656	85	2571	88	2568	74	14	2557	11
209	3005	384	2621	412	2593	364	48	2573	20
213	3251	610	2641	669	2582	569	100	2541	41
214	2262	257	2005	291	1971	243	48	1957	14
217	2208	162	2046	169	2039	139	30	2016	23
219	2287	205	2082	192	2095	174	18	2064	31
233	3079	849	2230	872	2207	783	89	2141	66
Total	45122	4674	40448	4934	40188	4316	618	39830	358
Se=92%		Sp=0,98%		Err=0,046		Acc=0,954		P+ =0,87	
								N+=0,99	

Table 9. IV. The classification of PCB of results that correspond to the critical value (-0, 2).

Record	Total beats	Cp	Cn	Rp	Rn	Tp	Fp	Tn	Fn
100	2273	34	2239	32	2241	32	0	2239	2
107	2137	59	2078	58	2079	50	8	2070	9
109	2532	40	2492	44	2488	31	13	2479	9
112	2539	2	2537	8	2531	2	6	2531	0
116	2412	110	2302	112	2300	95	17	2285	15
118	2288	122	2166	108	2180	107	1	2165	15
122	2476	0	2476	3	2473	0	6	2470	0
200	2601	858	1743	878	1723	809	69	1674	49
201	2000	375	1625	381	1619	342	39	1586	33
202	2136	75	2061	82	2054	61	21	2040	14
203	2980	447	2533	449	2531	389	60	2473	58
205	2656	85	2571	82	2574	69	13	2558	16
209	3005	384	2621	403	2602	356	47	2574	28
213	3251	610	2641	655	2596	557	98	2543	53
214	2262	257	2005	276	1986	229	47	1958	28
217	2208	162	2046	151	2057	124	27	2019	38
219	2287	205	2082	178	2109	161	17	2065	44
233	3079	849	2230	858	2221	772	86	2144	77
Total	45122	4674	40448	4758	40364	4186	575	39873	488
Se = 90%		Sp = 0,98%		Err = 0,06		Acc = 0,94		P+ = 0,88	
								N+=0,987	

Figure 9.4. Evaluation of the developed Premature Beat Detection algorithm at the different selected thresholds, note that the best performance occurs at a selected threshold is about (-0.1).

Till now we don't know which are the individual misclassification costs actually (here, the cost of a false positive, C_{Fp} and the cost of a false negative, C_{Fn}) so system performance is often specified in terms of the required false positive and false negative rates, $P(Fp)$ and $P(Fn)$. It is equivalent to the Neyman-Pearson method¹⁴ where $P(Fn)$ is specified and $P(Fp)$ is minimized with that constraint, or vice versa. Often the only way to do the constraint minimization required by the Neyman-Pearson method is to plot $P(Tp)$ against $P(Fp)$. The division threshold is varied selecting the operating point (decision threshold) that most closely meets the requirements for $P(Fn)$ and $P(Fp)$. The varied plotted values of $P(Tp)$ and $P(Fp)$ as the decision threshold give rise to a Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve.

There is however a problem in specifying the performance in term of a signal operating point (usually a $P(Tp)$, $P(Tn)$ pair), as there is no indication of how these two measures vary according to the decision threshold variation. It may represent an operating point where sensitivity ($P(Tp)$) can be increased with little loss in specificity ($P(Tn)$), or it may not. It means that the comparison of two systems can become ambiguous. Therefore there is a need of a single measure of classifier performance (often termed accuracy, but not to be confused with $P(C)$) that is invariant to the decision criterion selected, prior probabilities, and is easily extended to include cost/ benefit analysis. In this section we describe the obtained results investigating the use of the area under the ROC curve (AUC) as a measure of classifier performance.

When the decision threshold is varied and a number of points on the ROC curve ($P(Fp) = \alpha$, $P(Tp) = 1 - \beta$) are obtained, the simplest way to calculate the area under the ROC curve is to use trapezoidal integration,

$$AUC = \sum_i ((1 - \beta_i) \cdot \Delta\alpha) + \frac{1}{2} (\Delta(1 - \beta) \cdot \Delta\alpha) \quad (9.3)$$

Where: $\Delta(1 - \beta) = (1 - \beta_i) - (1 - \beta_{i-1})$, $\Delta\alpha = \alpha_i - \alpha_{i-1}$

¹⁴ The Neyman-Pearson design criterion is to maximize the power of the test (probability of detection) subject to a chosen significance of the test (false alarm probability).

It is also possible to calculate the AUC by considering that the underlying probabilities of predicting negative or positive are Gaussian. The ROC curve will then have an exponential form which can be fitted either directly using an iterative maximum Likelihood (ML) estimation (D. D. Dorfmann, *et.*, 1969), giving the difference in means and ratio of the variances of the positive and negative distributions or, if the ROC curve is plotted on double probability paper, a straight line can be fitted to the points on the ROC curve (J. A. Swets 1979). The slope and intercept of this fitted line are then used to obtain an estimate of the AUC.

Figure 9.5. An evaluation method represented by ROC curve and its coefficients, note that ROC coefficients confirms the result of precedent evaluation method which is represented in Figure 9.4, the best performance occurs at the same selected ratio(-0,1).

Figure 9.6. Performance of the developed algorithm on different traces of ECG signal taken from MIT-BIH arrhythmia database.

9.3 Frequency Domain Methods

The RR interval time series is an irregularly time-sampled signal. This is not an issue in time domain, but in the frequency-domain it has to be taken into account. If the spectrum estimate is calculated from this irregularly time-sampled signal, implicitly assuming it to be evenly sampled, additional harmonic components are generated in the spectrum. Therefore, the RR interval signal is usually interpolated before the spectral analysis to recover an evenly sampled signal from the irregularly sampled event series. In the frequency-domain analysis power spectral density (PSD) of the RR series is calculated. Methods for calculating the PSD estimate may be divided into nonparametric [e.g. fast Fourier transform (FFT) based] and parametric [e.g. based on autoregressive (AR) models] methods [3]. The PSD is analyzed by calculating powers and peak frequencies for different frequency bands. The commonly used frequency bands are very low frequency (VLF, 0-0.04 Hz), low frequency (LF, 0.04-0.15 Hz), and high frequency (HF, 0.15-0.4 Hz). The most common frequency-domain parameters include the powers of VLF, LF, and HF bands in absolute and relative values, the normalized power of LF and HF bands, and the LF to HF ratio. VLF and LF represent the activity of sympathetic nervous system, where the HF represents the activity of parasympathetic system.

Also the peak frequencies are determined for each frequency band. For the FFT based spectrum powers are calculated by integrating the spectrum over the frequency bands. The parametric spectrum, on the other hand, can be divided into components and the band powers are obtained as powers of these components. A detailed description of this can be found e.g. in [4]. This property of parametric spectrum estimation has made it popular in HRV analysis. In this chapter, we represent the heart rate variability in the frequency plane by using the parametric autoregressive model.

9.3.1 Autoregressive model

An AR process of order p can be written as:

$$x_t = n_t + a_1 x_{t-1} + a_2 x_{t-2} + \dots + a_p x_{t-p} \quad (9.4)$$

Where n_t is the white noise driving signal, the innovation of the AR process, and p is the order of the AR model. To estimate the AR power spectrum density function, the parameters of the filter $\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_p\}$ and the variance that characterizes the white noise σ^2 must be found. The system of equations to find the AR parameters is linear and its solution is straightforward. Furthermore, it can be solved iteratively, using the Levinson–Durbin equations, thus reducing processing time (Kay and Marple 1981). The AR power spectrum density estimate is given by:

$$P_{AR}(f) = \frac{\sigma^2 \Delta t}{\left| 1 + \sum_{k=1}^p a_k e^{-j2\pi f k \Delta t} \right|^2} \quad (9.5)$$

Where σ^2 is the variance of the white noise driving function and Δt is the re-sampling interval.

Four criteria were used for the estimation of the optimum model order. The first was Akaike's final prediction error (FPE) criterion (Akaike 1969), described as:

$$EPE_p = \sigma_p^2 \left(\frac{N+p+1}{N-p-1} \right) \quad (9.6)$$

where N is the number of data samples and σ_p^2 is the estimate of prediction error power for model order p .

The second technique used for estimating the model order was Akaike's information criterion (AIC) (Akaike 1974):

$$AIC_p = \ln(\sigma_p^2) + \frac{2(p+1)}{N} \quad (9.7)$$

The third criterion was Parzen's criterion autoregressive transfer function (CAT) (Parzen 1974):

$$CAT_p = \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^p \frac{N-j}{N\sigma^2} \right) - \frac{1}{\sigma_p^2} \quad (9.8)$$

where σ_p^2 is the intermediate prediction error power for $j = 1$ to $j = p$.

The final technique was Rissanen's minimum description length method (RIS) (Rissanen 1984):

$$RIS_p = \sigma_p^2 \left(1 + \left(\frac{p+1}{N} \right) \ln(N) \right) \quad (9.9)$$

For all four techniques the mean square error and bias change for each model order used and the above-defined functions have a minimum point; the model order corresponding to this minimum point is said to be the optimum. The advantage of this method is that it is able to adapt to non-stationary behaviour of time series being analyzed by adaptively estimating autoregressive (AR) coefficients for each sample. The AR coefficients are updated on the basis of previous ones and a forgetting factor, λ . Changes of the signal spectra characteristics are tracked by weighting the performance index, ε of the RLS-based predictor:

$$\varepsilon = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda^{n-i} e(i)^2 \quad (9.10)$$

Where $0 < \lambda < 1$ is forgetting factor, n is the index of the last sample considered, and $e(i)$ is the estimation error:

$$e(i) = y(i) - \bar{y}(i) \quad (9.11)$$

The predicted signal $\bar{y}(i)$ can be estimated as:

$$\bar{y}(i) = \sum_{j=1}^p a_j(n) y(i-j) = (a(n))^T Y(i-1) \quad (9.12)$$

Where $a(n)$ are the prediction coefficients, p is the order of the model, and

$$Y(i-1) = \begin{pmatrix} y(i-1) \\ y(i-2) \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ y(i-p) \end{pmatrix} \quad (9.13)$$

The performance index must be minimized according to the adaptive prediction coefficients vector ($\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial a} = 0$), thus satisfying following expression:

$$a(n) = (R(n))^{-1} p(n) \quad (9.14)$$

Where $R(n)$ represents the autocorrelation matrix of $\{y(i)\}$ signal calculated on p samples over a window of n samples:

$$R(n) = \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda^{n-i} Y(i-1) Y(i-1)^T \quad (9.15)$$

$$p(n) = \sum_{i=0}^n \lambda^{n-i} y(i) Y(i-1) \quad (9.16)$$

From this equation the first vector of prediction coefficients, $a(n)$, is calculated. All other vectors are calculated, without minimizing the performance index, following the recursive formula:

$$a(n) = a(n-1) - e(n/n-1)g(n) \quad (9.17)$$

Where, $e(n/n-1) = y(n) - (a(n-1))^T y(n-1)$ represents the estimation error and $g(n)$ represents the Kalman gain vector:

$$g(n) = \frac{Q(n-1)y(n-1)}{\lambda + (y(n-1))^T Q(n-1)y(n-1)} \quad (9.18)$$

And $Q(n) = R(n)^{-1}$. For each sample the $Q(n)$ is recursively updated:

$$Q(n) = \frac{(I - g(n)(y(n-1))^T)Q(n-1)}{\lambda} \quad (9.19)$$

Where I is the unit matrix. The power spectral density then is calculated by using the equation (9.12)

9.3.2 Frequency domain parameters

In order to extract the parameters of the HRV or RR time series in the frequency domain, an autoregressive model was applied by using a scanning window of 400 samples on the time series. In the correspondent windows in the frequency domain we have represented the pdf function, on which we can observe the presence or the absence of two types of waves (LF, and HF). Then it may be calculated the fractions of LF and HF.

The ratio between low-frequency (LF) and high-frequency (HF) spectral power of heart rate has been used as an approximate index for determining the autonomic nervous system (ANS) balance.

Figure 9.7 illustrates the performance of the autoregressive model and the extracted parameters in the frequency domain.

We used HRV parameters, obtained in the frequency plane, together with an algorithm just created for ischemia episodes automatic classification. The main aim is to see graphically the change of the above-mentioned parameters with the rise of an ischemia. We noted that in some cases such parameters change or variability results meaningful on a trace representing an ischemia, on the contrary in other cases it does not.

We applied the algorithm on the traces of the European long term ST segment database available in [61] and we saved all the graphic outcomes. These outcomes confirm the ones in [32].

9.4 Classification of Ischemic Episodes

Cardiac Ischemic beat is usually presented in the classic electrocardiogram ECG as a ST-T segment depression. Transient myocardial ischemia is most frequently subendocardial. Episodes of subendocardial ischemia are usually diagnosed on H-ECG recording when horizontal or downsloping ST segment depression >1 mm at 0.06-0.08 sec from the J point, lasting at least 1 minute, is detected [Cohn, 1988].

After the early technical difficulties in the correct reproduction of low-frequency ECG signal [Bragg-Remschel et al., 1982], modern technology has allowed reliable reproduction of the ST segment by H-ECG devices [Deanfield et al., 1984a]. Furthermore the possibility to detect myocardial ischemia by H-ECG has been improved by monitoring two bipolar chest leads. Monitor leads should always include CM5, as it is the single lead with the highest sensitivity in relieving ST segment depression, independent of the location of myocardial ischemia [Quyyumi et al., 1986]. Recently H-ECG recorders able to monitor three leads, and also a system which

allows recording of 12 leads, have become available. Nevertheless, the usefulness of more than 2 bipolar leads for improving detection of subendocardial ischemia has been questioned [Shandling et al., 1992; Jiang et al., 1995]. In a study we found that the addition of a third H-ECG lead improved sensitivity for detecting subendocardial ischemia only from 94% to 96% [Lanza et al., 1994].

(A)

(B)

Figure 9. 7. The extracted parameters of a HRV time series represented in the frequency domain. Data was taken from the record 20031 of European long term database.

(A) The frequency parameters computed over a trace of 400 beats.

(B) Frequency parameters computed over all the H-ECG by using a scanning window of 400 beats.

According to Bayesian theorem the probability that transient ST segment depression on H-ECG actually represents myocardial ischemia varies according to the clinical features of the patient, being as greater as higher is the pre-test likelihood of CAD. In fact "ischemic" ST segment changes have been reported in 2% to 30% of asymptomatic apparently healthy subjects [Deanfield et al., 1984b; Armstrong et al., 1982; Quyyumi et al., 1983], but the vast majority of them will not have significant CAD. A greater severity of ST depression or the simultaneous presence of angina will increase the likelihood that the ECG alteration is actually caused by myocardial ischemia. The ischemic meaning of ST depression on H-ECG is usually established with reference to the presence or absence of hemodynamically significant epicardial coronary artery stenosis at angiography. However coronary angiography may not be the ideal "gold-standard" for the interpretation of ST segment depression, because myocardial ischemia can occur in the absence of coronary stenoses, as in microvascular angina or in subocclusive vasospastic angina.

Dynamic vectorcardiography has recently been proposed as an alternative to H-ECG for silent ischemia detection [Dellborg et al., 1995; Homvang et al. 1999]. Although this method is promising its actual sensitivity and specificity in ischemia detection are hitherto still poorly known. Furthermore clinical studies using dynamic vectorcardiography are limited and its advantages on H-ECG unclear.

In this chapter we propose an algorithm for the automatic identification of the ischemic episodes in the long term 2-leads H- ECG, proposed algorithm is based on the application of C-mean Fuzzy logic classification method which we have used in our developed QRS detection algorithm (*see chapter 5, section 5.5.3*).

9.4.1 Dataset

Our dataset is formed by the first two leads of thirty-five records taken from European Long -term ECG database. These ECG records are fundamental to detect and characterize episodes of myocardial ischemia in patients with suspected or documented Coronary Artery Disease (CAD). Indeed, 70% to 80% of transient ischemic episodes are not associated with anginal chest pain or any other symptom (silent ischemia) [Cohn, 1988], and this is independent of the mechanisms responsible for the induction of ischemia. In clinical practice long-term ECG monitoring is principally achieved by Holter ECG recordings (H-ECG), which is the method used in the vast majority of studies and trials on silent ischemia in the medical literature. Detection of spontaneous ischemic episodes during normal daily life by H-ECG has been found to have relevant prognostic implications and can assist in therapeutic decisions. Indeed, H-ECG can also provide findings contributing to define the pathophysiologic mechanisms responsible for transient ischemia in individual patients

9.4.2 Ischemic episodes detection algorithm:

Diagram 9. I illustrates schematically the three main steps of the proposed algorithm. First step dealing with the original ECG signal in order to extract the ST- segment from every cardiac beat, which is the most indicative feature to detect the Ischemic episodes, as we see in the block I, all the passages in this step are well known and well explained in the precedent chapters. Next step is to determine the deviations of the ST segments with respect to the ECG baseline, and to classify them into three different clusters. In this study we taken the zero volt as a referent line although that in some leads there are some normal ST segment shifts than the ECG baseline, because it was noted that these normal ST segment shifts are eliminated by using the first former step. We used the C-mean fuzzy algorithm (see chapter 5) in order to classify the ST deviations function in three clusters, we consider the cluster which corresponds to the greater centre, this selected cluster is then integrated by using an integration moving average window of twenty-five points to smooth the ST deviation function and reduce the deviation of

ST segments in the case in which the ST deviations occur in time minus than 30 seconds (so it is not considered as ischemic episode as it is reported in [32]).

The last step is to select a suitable threshold value THV, and identify the presence of an ischemic episode when the values of selected cluster is major or equal THV, vice versa, when the values is minus than the selected threshold there is not ischemic episode detected.

9.4.3 Results and discussion

We have done six experiments by using six different THVs $\{25, 32, 38, 42, 48, 52\}$, in order to stabilize the THV which realizes the best performance (in this case the sensitivity Se and positive predictive ratio P+), results are reported in the Tables 9. V, VI, VII, VIII, VIII, X where in the Figure 9. 8 we illustrate graphically the sensitivities and positive predictive ratios obtained at every threshold value for the two studied long term leads.

Diagram 9. I. The proposed algorithm of ischemic episodes detection represented schematically in three former steps.

Table 9. V. The classification of Ischemic episodes results that correspond to the critical value (25).

Record	Cp	Rp	Tp	Cp	Rp	Tp
20011	0	8	0	0	6	0
20021	20	24	20	26	29	26
20031	5	7	5	5	20	5
20041	26	29	26	30	33	30
20061	0	2	0	0	2	0
20081	33	37	33	0	5	0
20101	1	7	1	2	8	2
20121	9	9	9	0	5	0
20141	0	4	0	0	9	0
20161	59	60	59	10	15	10
20181	0	4	0	36	42	36
20201	0	3	0	0	1	0
20221	0	6	0	0	7	0
20241	0	3	0	0	6	0
20261	17	18	17	13	17	13
20281	14	12	12	2	7	2
20301	41	40	40	0	5	0
20341	8	7	7	0	8	0
20381	1	3	1	1	5	1
20401	9	12	9	7	13	7

20441	8	11	8	14	18	14
20461	4	5	4	4	7	4
20481	7	9	7	0	8	0
20501	0	5	0	0	9	0
20521	0	3	0	0	11	0
20541	0	2	0	0	6	0
20561	8	10	8	0	6	0
20601	1	3	1	3	5	3
20621	0	2		0	6	
20641	0	3	0	0	7	0
30661	21	24	21	19	25	19
30721	0	3	0	1	6	1
30741	17	18	17	11	15	11
30781	0	2	0	1	2	1
30801	0	1	0	4	5	4
	309	396	305	189	379	189
Total	Se		P+	Se		P+
	0,98		0,77	1		0,5

Table 9. VI. The classification of Ischemic episodes results that correspond to the critical value (32).

Record	Cp	Rp	Tp	Cp	Rp	Tp
20011	0	7	0	0	4	0
20021	20	23	20	26	27	26
20031	5	7	5	5	8	5
20041	26	28	26	30	32	30
20061	0	2	0	0	2	0
20081	33	35	33	0	5	0
20101	1	7	1	2	7	2
20121	9	9	9	0	4	0
20141	0	3	0	0	3	0
20161	59	60	59	10	12	10
20181	0	3	0	36	40	36
20201	0	2	0	0	1	0
20221	0	4	0	0	3	0
20241	0	3	0	0	6	0
20261	17	18	17	13	16	13
20281	14	11	11	2	3	2
20301	41	38	38	0	4	0
20341	8	7	7	0	4	0
20381	1	3	1	1	5	1
20401	9	12	9	7	11	7
20441	8	11	8	14	17	14
20461	4	5	4	4	5	4
20481	7	9	7	0	8	0
20501	0	3	0	0	9	0
20521	0	3	0	0	6	0
20541	0	2	0	0	4	0
20561	8	10	8	0	3	0
20601	1	2	1	3	5	3
20621	0	2	0	0	6	0
20641	0	2	0	0	7	0
30661	21	23	21	19	20	19
30721	0	3	0	1	5	1
30741	17	18	17	11	14	11
30781	0	2	0	1	2	1
30801	0	1	0	4	5	4
Total	309	378	302	189	313	189

Se	P+	Se	P+
0,977	0,80	1	0,6

Table 9. VII. The classification of Ischemic episodes results that correspond to the critical value (38).

Record	Cp	Rp	Tp	Cp	Rp	Tp
20011	0	4	0	0	2	0
20021	20	21	20	26	23	23
20031	5	5	5	5	5	5
20041	26	25	25	30	29	29
20061	0	2	0	0	2	0
20081	33	32	32	0	2	0
20101	1	3	1	2	4	2
20121	9	8	8	0	2	0
20141	0	3	0	0	3	0
20161	59	56	56	10	9	9
20181	0	3	0	36	35	35
20201	0	2	0	0	1	0
20221	0	4	0	0	1	0
20241	0	3	0	0	3	0
20261	17	16	16	13	13	13
20281	14	11	11	2	3	2
20301	41	37	37	0	2	0
20341	8	7	7	0	2	0
20381	1	3	1	1	3	1
20401	9	11	9	7	9	7
20441	8	10	8	14	15	14
20461	4	4	4	4	3	3
20481	7	8	7	0	5	0
20501	0	2	0	0	7	0
20521	0	2	0	0	5	0
20541	0	2	0	0	4	0
20561	8	9	8	0	3	0
20601	1	2	1	3	2	2
20621	0	0	0	0	4	0
20641	0	0	0	0	5	0
30661	21	20	20	19	18	18
30721	0	2	0	1	5	1
30741	17	16	16	11	13	11
30781	0	1	0	1	2	1
30801	0	1	0	4	3	3
	309	335	292	189	247	179
Total	Se	P+	Se	P+		
	0,94	0,87	0,947	0,72		

Table 9. VIII. The classification of Ischemic episodes results that correspond to the critical value (42).

Record	Cp	Rp	Tp	Cp	Rp	Tp
20011	0	3	0	0	1	0
20021	20	19	19	26	21	21
20031	5	5	5	5	4	4
20041	26	23	23	30	27	27
20061	0	2	0	0	2	0
20081	33	30	30	0	1	0
20101	1	2	1	2	2	2
20121	9	7	7	0	1	0
20141	0	2	0	0	2	0
20161	59	55	55	10	8	8
20181	0	3	0	36	33	33

20201	0	2	0	0	1	0
20221	0	4	0	0	1	0
20241	0	3	0	0	2	0
20261	17	15	15	13	12	12
20281	14	11	11	2	2	2
20301	41	37	37	0	1	0
20341	8	7	7	0	1	0
20381	1	3	1	1	2	1
20401	9	11	9	7	7	7
20441	8	9	8	14	13	13
20461	4	4	4	4	3	3
20481	7	8	7	0	4	0
20501	0	1	0	0	5	0
20521	0	1	0	0	4	0
20541	0	1	0	0	3	0
20561	8	7	7	0	3	0
20601	1	2	1	3	2	2
20621	0	0	0	0	3	0
20641	0	0	0	0	3	0
30661	21	19	19	19	17	17
30721	0	1	0	1	3	1
30741	17	16	16	11	9	9
30781	0	1	0	1	1	1
30801	0	1	0	4	3	3
	309	315	282	189	207	166
Total	Se		P+	Se		P+
	0,91		0,895	0,878		0,80

Table 9. VIII. The classification of Ischemic episodes results that correspond to the critical value (48).

Record	Cp	Rp	Tp	Cp	Rp	Tp
20011	0	1	0	0	1	0
20021	20	17	17	26	19	19
20031	5	3	3	5	4	4
20041	26	21	21	30	25	25
20061	0	1	0	0	1	0
20081	33	27	27	0	1	0
20101	1	1	1	2	1	1
20121	9	7	7	0	0	0
20141	0	1	0	0	0	0
20161	59	53	53	10	7	7
20181	0	2	0	36	31	31
20201	0	1	0	0	1	0
20221	0	1	0	0	1	0
20241	0	1	0	0	1	0
20261	17	14	14	13	11	11
20281	14	10	10	2	2	2
20301	41	35	35	0	1	0
20341	8	7	7	0	1	0
20381	1	2	1	1	1	1
20401	9	8	8	7	4	4
20441	8	7	7	14	11	11
20461	4	4	4	4	3	3
20481	7	6	6	0	2	0
20501	0	1	0	0	3	0
20521	0	1	0	0	2	0
20541	0	1	0	0	1	0
20561	8	7	7	0	1	0

20601	1	2	1	3	2	2
20621	0	0	0	0	1	0
20641	0	0	0	0	1	0
30661	21	18	18	19	16	16
30721	0	1	0	1	3	1
30741	17	16	16	11	9	9
30781	0	1	0	1	1	1
30801	0	1	0	4	3	3
	309	279	263	189	172	151
Total	Se	P+	Se	P+		
	0,85	0,94	0,80	0,88		

Table 9. X. The classification of Ischemic episodes results that correspond to the critical value (52).

Record	Cp	Rp	Tp	Cp	Rp	Tp
20011	0	0	0	0	0	0
20021	20	16	16	26	17	17
20031	5	2	2	5	3	3
20041	26	19	19	30	23	23
20061	0	0	0	0	0	0
20081	33	26	26	0	0	0
20101	1	0	0	2	1	1
20121	9	6	6	0	0	0
20141	0	0	0	0	0	0
20161	59	48	48	10	6	6
20181	0	2	0	36	26	26
20201	0	0	0	0	0	0
20221	0	0	0	0	0	0
20241	0	0	0	0	0	0
20261	17	14	14	13	11	11
20281	14	10	10	2	2	2
20301	41	31	31	0	0	0
20341	8	5	5	0	0	0
20381	1	2	1	1	1	1
20401	9	7	7	7	3	3
20441	8	5	5	14	10	10
20461	4	3	3	4	3	3
20481	7	5	5	0	0	0
20501	0	0	0	0	1	0
20521	0	0	0	0	0	0
20541	0	0	0	0	0	0
20561	8	5	5	0	0	0
20601	1	0	0	3	2	2
20621	0	0	0	0	1	0
20641	0	0	0	0	1	0
30661	21	15	15	19	16	16
30721	0	1	0	1	2	1
30741	17	14	14	11	9	9
30781	0	0	0	1	0	0
30801	0	0	0	4	3	3
	309	236	232	189	141	137
Total	Se	P+	Se	P+		
	0,75	0,983	0,725	0,972		

Figure 9. 8. The results of ischemic episodes detection algorithm reported graphically.

Note that the selected threshold (42) realizes the best performance, so we stabilized this threshold in our system. Figure 9. 9 illustrates graphically the performance of our algorithm over two different traces taken from Long Term ECG European database.

Our algorithm has based on the study of ST-T segment deviations and proceeds on two leads H-ECG to detect the episodes of ischemia. The relative positive predictive ratio and sensitivity are [%89, %91], [%80, %88] for the first and second leads respectively. In the other hand the configurations of the algorithm outcome reports the HRV's parameters which are important variables to consider to recognize the silent ischemia which may also disturb the heart's rhythm (Abnormal rhythms such as ventricular tachycardia or ventricular fibrillation can interfere with the heart pumping ability and can cause fainting or even sudden cardiac death).

(A)

Heart rate variability & Ischemic episodes detection

(B)

Heart rate variability & Ischemic episodes detection

Figure 9. 9. The ischemic episodes detection algorithm and The frequency parameters represented over a trace of 400 beats. Traces in A, and B, are taken from the records 20021, 20031 of European long term database respectively.

CHAPTER 10

CLASSIFIERS OF ARRHYTHMIA

Introduction

Each year, arrhythmia disease claims approximately 400.000 lives, and costs up to \$ 30 billion in combined health care spending in France, Germany, Italy, Spain, and in the United Kingdom [31].

In this work we consider five types of arrhythmic beats:

1-Premature Ventricular Conduction (PVC) is an ectopic cardiac pacemaker located in the ventricle. PVCs are characterized by the premature occurrence of bizarre shaped QRS complexes, usually greater than 120 ms. These complexes are not preceded by the P wave, and the T wave is usually large and opposite in direction to the major deflection of the QRS (*see section 2. 7. 1 in this thesis*).

2- Atrial Premature Conduction (APC) is an ectopic cardiac pacemaker located in the atrias; APCs are characterized by the premature occurrence of QRS (*see section 2.7.1 in this thesis*).

3 & 4- Blocks of the cardiac conduction system: they cause prolonged PR intervals, whose duration is more than 0.2sec. In this sense cardiac blocks were classified in three levels. The first one is caused by intra-atrial, AV node, or intra-ventricle slow conductions. The second level shows either the Wenckebach form (increasing PR interval until not connected P wave), or the Mobitz one (fixed PR interval and not connected P wave). The third level causes prolonged PR interval, but P wave and QRS complexes are dissociated.

Our classifier takes as object of study the slow conduction in the left and right ventricles, caused by a left or right bundle branch blocks (LBBB, or RBBB respectively). These types of arrhythmia show a prolonged PR interval and a wide abnormal QRS complex (*see section 2. 7. 3 in this thesis*).

5 -Paced Beats: a sequence of 3 or more junctional escapes. There may be AV dissociation, or the atria may be captured retrogradely by the junctional pacemaker (*see section 2. 7. 2 in this thesis*).

This chapter presents a robust classifier able to identify all the cited types of ectopic beats by using neural networks on a Bayesian framework. Data were obtained from 48 records of the MIT-BIH arrhythmia database[68], (only one lead). Five types of arrhythmic beats were classified using our method, Premature Ventricular Conduction beat (PVC), Atrial Premature Conduction beat (APC), Right Bundle Branch Block beat (RBBB), Left Bundle Branch Block beat(LBBB), and Paced Rhythm Beat (PRB), in addition to the Normal Beat (NB). The same method is tested using other two learning methods (Levenberg-Marquardt, and the classical backpropagation algorithms). Then a comparison based on a statistical analysis, between the developed Bayesian algorithm and the other two algorithms, will take place in this chapter in order to determine the best performance

10.1 Pre-Processing and ECG Waves Detection

10.1.1 ECG pre-processing

It means filtering and reducing the influence of noise superimposed on the ECG. Firstly we used a pass-band (0.05-40Hz) FIR filter to remove the continuous shift and draft baseline. Its coefficients were designed with Sptool. Secondly, we used a notch filter to reduce the 60Hz powerline interference (*Chapter 4, section 4. 1. 3 and section (4. 1. 4. I)*). Finally a signal was resampled to obtain a sampling frequency of 1000 s/s.

10.1.2 QRS detection algorithm

In order to enhance the desired signal features, the QRS detection represents the first step to have been executed. Many algorithms were proposed in the literature (Pan & Tompkins (1985), So. H. H and Chan K. L. (1997)) and guarantee a good performance level. In this chapter we develop a QRS detection algorithm based on a non linear operator which exploits the curve-length concept (M. Pauletti, C. Marchesi (2001)). Three fiducial points were determined, the QRS-on, the QRS-off, and the R-peak or amplitude (*chapter5, section 5. 5*).

10.1.3 P and T waves Detection

After the QRS complex has been detected, T and P waves were searched and detected using our developed algorithm (*chapter 6, Section 6. 3*). six fiducial points were determined using this algorithm, the P-on, P-off, P-amplitude, T-on, T-off, and T-amplitude.

10.2 Features Extraction

From the two former steps (Pre-filtering, ECG waves detection) we extract ten indicative parameters representing the features of each beat, these features were then normalized in order to use them to build the input vector of our neural network classifier, in the following section we cite these features and we explain how we have normalized them:

- 1) **P-amplitude:** if $P_amplitude < 0 \Rightarrow P_amplitude = -1$ else $P_amplitude = 1$.
- 2) **P-wide:** if $(P_wide \leq 0.08 \text{sec}) \Rightarrow (P_wide = -1)$
 elseif $(P_wide \leq 0.14 \text{sec}, \text{ and}, P_wide > 0.08 \text{sec}) \Rightarrow (P_wide = 0.5)$
 else $(P_wide = 1)$.
- 3) **R-amplitude:** if $R_amplitude < 0 \Rightarrow R_amplitude = -1$ else $R_amplitude = 1$.
- 4) **Q-amplitude:** if $Q_amplitude < 0 \Rightarrow Q_amplitude = 1$ else $Q_amplitude = -1$.
- 5) **S-amplitude:** if $S_amplitude < 0 \Rightarrow S_amplitude = 1$ else $S_amplitude = -1$.
- 6) **QRS-wide:** if $(QRS_wide \leq 0.08 \text{sec}) \Rightarrow (QRS_wide = -1)$
 elseif $(QRS_wide \leq 0.14 \text{sec}, \text{ and}, QRS_wide > 0.08 \text{sec}) \Rightarrow (QRS_wide = 0.5)$
 else $(QRS_wide = 1)$
- 7) **T-amplitude:** if $P_amplitude < 0 \Rightarrow P_amplitude = -1$ else $P_amplitude = 1$.
- 8) **T-wide:** if $(T_wide \leq 0.1 \text{sec}) \Rightarrow (T_wide = -1)$
 elseif $(T_wide \leq 0.5 \text{sec}, \text{ and}, T_wide > 0.1 \text{sec}) \Rightarrow (T_wide = 0.5)$
 else $(T_wide = 1)$
- 9) **PR-interval:** if $(PR_interval \leq 0.18 \text{sec}) \Rightarrow (PR_interval = -1)$
 elseif $(PR_interval \leq 0.25 \text{sec}, \text{ and}, PR_interval > 0.18 \text{sec}) \Rightarrow (PR_interval = 0.5)$
 else $(PR_interval = 1)$
- 10) **RR-interval:** if $(RR_interval \leq 0.5 \text{sec}) \Rightarrow (RR_interval = -1)$
 elseif $(RR_interval \leq 0.8 \text{sec}, \text{ and}, RR_interval > 0.18 \text{sec}) \Rightarrow (RR_interval = 0.5)$
 else $(RR_interval = 1)$

In this mode we have obtained the Normalized Features Matrix (NFM) which has $10 \times M$ elements, where M is the number of cardiac beats.

10.3 Technique of Arrhythmic Beat Classifiers

Our developed classifiers are based on the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) approach by using three different training algorithms: Bayesian, Backpropagation and Levenberg-Marquardt. All these algorithms are well explained in chapter 7 (section 7.6. sections 7.3 and 7.5 respectively). A configuration of the developed ANN is shown schematically in Figure 10. 1. The obtained NFM is applied on the ANN input, then the entered values passes through two consecutive hidden tangent sigmoid layers, and proceeds to a linear layer which represents the output of developed ANN. The number of nodes in the input layer corresponds to the number of features in the obtained NFM where the number of output nodes corresponds to the number of arrhythmia classes. As far as the number of nodes in the first and second hidden layers, many experiments were executed in order to determine the number of nodes which guarantees the best performance to our developed ANN.

Table (10. I) reports the best chosen numbers of nodes in the first and second hidden layers of the three upper indicated ANN classifiers.

Table 10. I. Chosen number of nodes in the hidden layers of studied classifiers.

ANN classifier	Number of nodes	Number of nodes
	(I layer)	(II layer)
Back-propagation	18	13
Levenberg-Marquardt	17	11
Bayesian	15	10

Figure 10. 1. Arrhythmic beat classifier's topology.

Figure 10. 2. populations of cardiac beats in MIT-BIH database.

ECG signals were obtained from MIT-BIH arrhythmia database, this database was formed from 48 ECG records, and it contains different kinds of ectopic beats and different kinds of noise that make it a typical database in order to test any method of ECG patterns recognition and automatic ectopic beats classification. Figure 10.2 illustrates the populations of normal and ectopic cardiac beats in the MIT database. Dataset was divided into two sets training dataset and tasting data set (55%, 45% respectively). Training dataset has been manually classified using MIT-BIH arrhythmia database directory and documentation, taking advantage of the professional

experience of a cardiologist, in order to create a suitable ANN target of binary values (-1 for positive and 1 for negative cases).

10.3.1 Training the Classifiers

A NFM was extracted from the learning dataset, then it was used as a classifier input. Where the normalized target file, which we have prepared manually, was used as classifier target. Then the neural net was learned in 100 epochs in the case of Bayesian and Backpropagation learning algorithms, and in 50 epochs in the case of Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm. Figure 10. 3 illustrates the convergence between the calculated mean square errors and the desired goal during the training epochs. Finally, neural net coefficients (weights and biases) were stored in order to test the three classifiers.

Figure 10. 3. The convergence of mean square error during the ANN training process:

- (A) Bayesian method , 100 epochs, mean square error= 0.093.
- (B) Backpropagation method, 100 epochs, mean square error=0.008.
- (C) Levenberg-Marquardt method, 50 epochs, mean square error= 0.078.

10.3.2 Testing and evaluating the classifiers:

In order to test the trained classifiers, we have extracted a NFM from the selected dataset, which was applied on the classifiers input. Figure 10. 4 illustrates populations of dataset.

The “row data” produced by a classification scheme during the test takes its value between -1 and 1. We counted the correct and incorrect classifications from the normal class (see Figure 10. 1), by using a certain criteria in the following mode:

If normal class (i) > criteria then normal class (i) is a normal beat.

else if normal class(i) ≤ criteria then normal class(i) is an ectopic beat .

where, $i=[1:N]$, where N: is the number of beats in the Testing dataset, criteria is between [-1 1].

Figure 10. 4. Datatest distribution.

Then this information was arranged in a *confusion matrix*¹⁵. The row totals, C_n and C_p are the numbers of truly negative and positive examples, the column totals R_n and R_p are the numbers of predicted negative and positive examples, N is the total number of examples ($N = C_n + C_p = R_n + R_p$). T_p and T_n are the numbers of true positive and true negative classified beats respectively, F_p and F_n are the numbers of false positive and false negative classified beats respectively. Although the confusion matrix shows all of the information about the classifier's performance, more meaningful measures can be extracted from it to illustrate certain performance criteria (i.e. (Accuracy (Acc), sensitivity (Se), specificity (Sp), positive predictive value (P^+), negative predictive value (N^+), see chapter 5, equations 5.20, 5.21, 5.22, 5.23 respectively).

To calculate the percentage error the normal and pathological cases must be equally distributed. In order to ensure this purpose we use the equation 9. 2.

In Figure 10. 5 we illustrate how the three classifiers behave to different values of criteria. A set of six critical values, $\{-0.4, -0.2, 0, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6\}$ was taken in consideration, then the pairs ($P(F_p)$, $P(T_p)$) of ROC curve and AUC were computed for every classifier. Note that the developed Bayesian classifier has the best performance in comparison to the other studied classifiers. The optimum criteria in the different studied objects is (0.2), so we have extracted the confusion matrices concerned to that criteria, in order to have another point of view in the comparison process between the performance of the three studied classifiers.

Tables II, III, IV illustrate the classification results at the selected criteria for Bayesian, Backpropagation, and Levenberg-Marquardt classifiers respectively, Figure 10. 6. reports a comparison between the performance of the three classifiers by using the set of computed values (sensitivity, specificity, error, accuracy, positive, and negative predictive values).

Table V reports the behaviour of Bayesian classifier in case of every singular class of arrhythmia at the selected criteria (0,2) where Figure 10. 7 illustrates a comparison between the computed values of confusion matrix.

¹⁵ A confusion matrix is a form of contingency table showing the differences between the true and predicted classes for a set of labelled (i.e. Table II)

Figure 9.5. A comparison between the training methods, represented by using ROC curve. (A), (B), and (C) illustrate the performance evaluation of Bayesian, Levenberg-Marquardt, and Backpropagation classifiers respectively.

Table II. Confusion matrix of Bayesian method.

Record	Cp	Cn	Rp	Rn	Tp	Fp	Fn	Tn
100	34	2239	31	2242	29	2	5	2237
102	2088	99	1860	327	1850	10	238	89
104	1382	847	1220	1009	1200	20	182	827
106	520	1507	441	1586	432	9	88	1498
107	2137	0	2121	16	2121	0	16	0
109	2532	0	2305	227	2305	0	227	0
111	2124	0	2069	55	2069	0	55	0
112	2	2537	703	1836	2	701	0	1836
113	6	1789	734	1061	6	728	0	1061
114	59	1820	856	1023	56	800	3	1020
115	0	1953	37	1916	0	37	0	1916
116	110	2302	1134	1278	110	1024	0	1278
117	1	1534	259	1276	1	258	0	1276
118	2288	0	2077	211	2077	0	211	0
119	444	1543	451	1536	444	7	0	1536
121	2	1861	4	1859	2	2	0	1859
124	1619	0	1588	31	1588	0	31	0
200	858	1743	1008	1593	858	150	0	1593
201	375	1625	575	1425	375	200	0	1425
202	75	2061	86	2050	75	11	0	2050
205	85	2571	114	2542	81	33	4	2538
228	365	1688	388	1665	360	28	5	1660
Total	17106	29719	20061	26764	16041	4020	1065	25699
	Acc = 90,3%		Se= 93,8%		Sp = 86,5%			
	Err =0,098		P⁺ =0,791		N⁺ =0,97			

Table 10. III. Confusion matrix of Backpropagation method.

Record	Cp	Cn	Rp	Rn	Tp	Fp	Fn	Tn
100	34	2239	29	2244	24	5	10	2234
102	2088	99	1860	327	1850	10	238	89
104	1382	847	1215	1014	1139	76	243	771
106	520	1507	441	1586	432	9	88	1498
107	2137	0	2088	49	2088	0	49	0
109	2532	0	2282	250	2282	0	250	0
111	2124	0	2038	86	2038	0	86	0
112	2	2537	721	1818	2	719	0	1818
113	6	1789	759	1036	6	753	0	1036
114	59	1820	860	1019	51	809	8	1011
115	0	1953	44	1909	0	44	0	1909
116	110	2302	1146	1266	110	1036	0	1266
117	1	1534	272	1263	1	271	0	1263
118	2288	0	2049	239	2049	0	239	0
119	444	1543	466	1521	444	22	0	1521
121	2	1861	13	1850	2	11	0	1850
124	1619	0	1568	51	1568	0	51	0
200	858	1743	1021	1580	858	163	0	1580
201	375	1625	590	1410	375	215	0	1410
202	75	2061	108	2028	75	33	0	2028
205	85	2571	114	2542	81	33	4	2538
228	365	1688	388	1665	360	28	5	1660
Total	17106	29719	20072	26753	15835	4237	1271	25482
	Acc = 89,1%		Se= 92,6%		Sp = 85,9%			
	Err = 0,108		P⁺ =0,789		N⁺ =0,95			

Table 10. IV. Confusion matrix of Levenberg-Marquardt method.

Record	Cp	Cn	Rp	Rn	Tp	Fp	Fn	Tn
100	34	2239	34	2239	27	7	7	2232
102	2088	99	1867	320	1859	8	229	91
104	1382	847	1215	1014	1144	71	238	776
106	520	1507	452	1575	444	8	76	1499
107	2137	0	2105	32	2105	0	32	0
109	2532	0	2315	217	2315	0	217	0
111	2124	0	2088	36	2088	0	36	0
112	2	2537	703	1836	2	701	0	1836
113	6	1789	749	1046	6	743	0	1046
114	59	1820	860	1019	53	807	6	1013
115	0	1953	39	1914	0	39	0	1914
116	110	2302	1143	1269	110	1033	0	1269
117	1	1534	266	1269	1	265	0	1269
118	2288	0	2033	255	2033	0	255	0
119	444	1543	471	1516	444	27	0	1516
121	2	1861	21	1842	2	19	0	1842
124	1619	0	1570	49	1570	0	49	0
200	858	1743	1015	1586	858	157	0	1586
201	375	1625	588	1412	375	213	0	1412
202	75	2061	106	2030	75	31	0	2030
205	85	2571	115	2541	79	36	6	2535
228	365	1688	384	1669	359	25	6	1663
Total	17106	29719	20139	26686	15949	4190	1157	25529
	Acc = 89,5%			Se= 93,2%			Sp = 85,9%	
	Err =0,104			P⁺ =0,791			N⁺ =0,957	

Figure 10. 6. The performance of studied classifiers, evaluated by using the computed parameters of the confusion matrices which were reported in Tables 10. I, II, III.

Figure 10. 7. The performance of Bayesian classifier in the different studied classes of arrhythmia, evaluated by using the computed parameters of the confusion matrix reported in Table V.

Table 10. V. Classification results of the studied types of arrhythmia.

Record	Total beat	APC	PVC	Paced rhythm	RBBB	LBBB	Normal + others
100	2273	33	1	0	0	0	2239
102	2187	56	4	2028	0	0	99
104	2229	0	2	1380	0	0	847
106	2027	0	520	0	0	0	1507
107	2137	0	59	2078	0	0	0
109	2532	0	40	0	0	2492	0
111	2124	0	1	0	0	2123	0
112	2539	2	0	0	0	0	2537
113	1795	6	0	0	0	0	1789
114	1879	10	49	0	0	0	1820
115	1953	0	0	0	0	0	1953
116	2412	1	109	0	0	0	2302
117	1535	1	0	0	0	0	1534
118	2288	106	16	0	2166	0	0
119	1987	0	444	0	0	0	1543
121	1863	1	1	0	0	0	1861
124	1619	2	86	0	1531	0	0
200	2601	30	828	0	0	0	1743
201	2000	164	211	0	0	0	1625
202	2136	55	20	0	0	0	2061
205	2656	3	82	0	0	0	2571
228	2053	3	362	0	0	0	1688
Total	46825	417	2788	5486	3697	4485	29719
Rp		4509	6888	7566	7197	8485	26764
Rn		42316	39937	39259	39628	37340	20061
Tp		377	2730	5311	3663	4350	25699
Fp		66	410	455	374	801	4020
Tn		45650	41207	39304	41644	40539	16041
Fn		732	2478	1755	1144	1135	1065
Sensitivity		0,9041	0,979	0,968	0,99	0,9699	0,8647
Specificity		0,9837	0,9357	0,95	0,965	0,9575	0,9377
error		0,88	0,45	0,165	0,159	0,136	0,099
Accuracy		0,12	0,55	0,83	0,84	0,864	0,90
P+		0,34	0,524	0,75	0,762	0,7931	0,96
N+		0,998	0,99	0,99	0,9911	0,9806	0,79
Average							
Sensitivity = 96,24%				Specificity = 95,86%			Error = 0,31
Accuracy = 0,69				P+ = 0,69			N+ = 0,96

10.4 Examples Represented on a Different ECG Traces:

In the following Figures we illustrate the performance of our developed Bayesian classifier on chosen traces of twenty-five seconds each, from the selected dataset.

Record 111/ MIT/BIH

Record 124/MIT-BIH

Record 107/MIT-BIH

Record 106/MIT-BIH

Record 100/MIT-BIH

Record 119/MIT-BIH

In this chapter, we have presented three classification systems of arrhythmia based on Bayesian, Backpropagation and Levenberg-Marquardt algorithms, and an excellent performance has been evaluated by representing the ROC curves of these systems and computing their corresponding AUC values. At the optimum criteria of ROC it has been noted that the three studied classifiers have approximately the same performance.

As far as the classification's performance for every class of arrhythmia it was noted that the level of pattern recognition is very good in cases of Paced rhythm, RBBB, LBBB, good in the case of PVC and unacceptable in the case of APC. This behaviour is interpretable, the main reason regards the population of APC in the selecting dataset. Table IV illustrates clearly the minority of APC population respect to the others, so we are working now to enrich the selecting dataset by adding more APC cases in order to overcome this problem.

CONCLUSION

This doctoral thesis presented several algorithms to improve the automatic ECG analysis and put forward solutions to certain problems encountered in the ECG processing and classification through six new developed algorithms:

1. QRS detection algorithm.
2. T & P waves detection algorithm.
3. A new adaptive ECG filter method.
4. Premature beat detection algorithm.
5. Arrhythmia (five ectopic beats) classifiers.
6. Ischemic episodes classifier.

The prospective work is to develop an automatic ECG analysis system in order to interpret and classify more cardiac pathological cases and realize a wider automatic diagnosis system.

References

1. A. Smrdel and F. Jager (2006): "Diurnal Changes of Heart Rate and Sympatho-Vagal Activity for Temporal Patterns of Transient Ischemic Episodes in 24-Hour Electrocardiograms", press Aleš Smrdel, Faculty of Computer and Information Science, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia.
2. A. Taddei, G. Costantino, R. Silipo, M. Emdin, C. Marchesi (1995): "A System for the Detection of Ischemic Episodes in Ambulatory ECG", IEEE, Vol.0276-6547, pp. 705-708.
3. Ader C (1897): Sur un nouvel appareil enregistreur pour cables sousmarins. *Compt. rend. Acad. Sci. (Paris)* 124: 1440-2.
4. Akaike H(1969): "Fitting autoregressive models for prediction" *Ann. Inst. Stat. Math.* 21, pp. 243-7.
5. Akaike H(1974): "A new look at the statistical model identification", *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control*, 19, pp. 716-23.
6. Anna M. Bianchi, Luca Mainardi, Ettore Petrucci, Maria. G. Signorini, Mauro Mainardi, and Sergio Cerutti (1993): "Time-Variant Power Spectrum Analysis for the Detection of Transient Episodes in HRV signal, *IEEE Transaction on Biomedical Engineering*, Vol. 40, No. 2, pp. 136-144.
7. Antti Ruha, Sami Sallinen, Seppo Nissilä.(1997), " A Real Time Microprocessor QRS detector System with a 1ms Timing Accuracy for the Measurement of Ambulatory HRV", *IEEE Transaction on biomedical engineering*, Volume 44, No. 3, pp.159-167.
8. Armstrong WF, Jordan JW, Morris SN, McHenry PL (1982): "Prevalence and magnitude of S-T segment and T wave abnormalities in normal men during continuous ambulatory electrocardiography", *Am J Cardiol*, vol. 49, pp.1638-1642.
9. Behzad Mozaffary Mohammad A. Tinati "ECG Baseline Wander Elimination using Wavelet Packets", *ENFORMATIKA V3 2004* ISSN 1305-5313.
10. Bragg-Renschel, D, Angus JA, Anderson C, Winkle RA(1982): "Frequency response characteristics of ambulatory ECG monitoring systems and their implications for ST-segment analysis", *Am Heart J*, vol. 103, pp. 20-31.
11. Brody DA (1956): A theoretical analysis of intracavitary blood mass influence on the heart-lead relationship. *Circ. Res.* 4:(Nov.) 731-8.
12. C. S. Burrus, R. A. Gopinath, H. Guo, "Introduction to Wavelets and Wavelet Transforms, a primer" Prentice Hall New jersey, 1998.
13. C. Stein, "Estimation of the mean of a multivariate normal distribution," *Ann. Stat.*, vol. 9, pp. 1135-1151, 1981.
14. Charalambous, C. (1992): "Conjugate Gradient Algorithm for Efficient Training of Artificial Neural Networks" *IEEE Proceedings*, vol. 139, no. 3, pp. 301-310.
15. Clifford G, McSharry P. A (2004): "realistic coupled non linear artificial ECG, BP, and respiratory signal generator for assessing noise performance of biomedical signal processing algorithms", *Proc of SPIE International Symposium on Fluctuations and Noise* Vol. 5467, no. 34, pp 290-301.
16. Cohn PF (1988): " Silent myocardial ischemia", *Ann Intern Med*, vol. 109, pp. 312-317.
17. D. D. Dorfmann " E. Alf. (1969): "Maximum Likelihood Estimation of Parameters of Signal Detection Theory and Determination of Confidence Intervals Rating Method Data," *Journal of Mathematical Psychology* 6, pp.487-496.
18. D. Gao, Y. Kinouchi, K. Ito, X. Zhao (2003): "Time Series Identifying and Modeling with Neural Networks". In: *Proc. IEEE Int. Joint Conference on Neural Networks*, Portland, USA, pp. 2454-59.
19. D. Gao, Y. Kinouchi, K. Ito, X. Zhao, (2005): " Neural Networks For event Extraction from Time Series A Back Propagation Algorithm Approach", *Future Generation Computer Systems (FGC)*, Volume 21, No 7, pp1096- 1105.
20. DASKALOV, I. K., and CHRISTOV, I. I. (1999): "Electrocardiogram signal preprocessing for automatic detection of QRS boundaries", *Med. Eng. Phys.*, 21, pp. 37-44.
21. Deanfield JE, Ribeiro P, Oakley K, Krikler S, Selwyn AP (1984b): "Analysis of ST-segment changes in normal subjects: implications for ambulatory monitoring in angina pectoris", *Am J Cardiol*, vol. 54, pp. 1321-1325.
22. Deanfield JE, Selwyn AP, Chierchia S (1983): "Myocardial ischemia during daily life in patients with stable angina: its relation to symptoms and heart rate changes", *Lancet*, vol.2, pp. 753-758.
23. Deanfield JE, Shea M, Ribeiro P (1984a): "Transient ST-segment depression as a marker of myocardial ischemia during daily life". *Am J Cardiol*, vol. 54, pp. 1195-1200.
24. Dellborg M, Malmberg K, Rydén L, Svensson A, Swedberg K. (1995): "Dynamic on-line vectorcardiography improves and simplifies in-hospital ischemia monitoring of patients with unstable angina". *J Am Coll Cardiol*, vol. 26, pp. 1501-1507.
25. Donoho, D.L. (1995), "De-noising by soft-thresholding," *IEEE Trans. on Inf. Theory*, 41, 3, pp. 613-627.
26. Durrer D, van Dam RT, Freud GE, Janse MJ, Meijler FL, Arzbaecher RC (1970): Total excitation of the isolated human heart. *Circulation* 41:(6) 899-912.

27. Durrer D, van Dam RT, Freud GE, Janse MJ, Meijler FL, Arzbaeher RC (1970): Total excitation of the isolated human heart. *Circulation* 41:(6) 899-912.
28. Einthoven W (1908): Weiteres über das Elektrokardiogram. *Pflüger Arch. ges. Physiol.* 122: 517-48.
29. Einthoven W, Fahr G, de Waart A (1913): -ber die Richtung und die Manifeste Gr.sse der Potentialschwankungen im menschlichen Herzen und über den Einfluss der Herzlage auf die form des Elektrokardiogramms. *Pflüger Arch. ges. Physiol.* 150: 275-315.
30. Einthoven W, Fahr G, de Waart A (1950): On the direction and manifest size of the variations of potential in the human heart and on the influence of the position of the heart on the form of the electrocardiogram. *Am. Heart J.* 40:(2) 163-211. (Reprint 1913, translated by HE Hoff, P Sekelj).
31. European Markets for Arrhythmia Management Products, 278 Pages Report # RP-481420, February 2001.
32. F. Jager, A. Taddei, G. B. Moody, M. Emdin, G. Antolic, R. Dorn, A. Smardel, C. Marchesi, R. G. Mark (2003): "Long-term ST database: a reference for the development and evaluation of automated ischemia detectors and for the study of the dynamics of myocardial ischemia", *Med. Biol. Eng. Comput.*, Vol. 41, pp. 172-182.
33. Fozzard HA, Haber E, Jennings RB, Katz AM, Morgan HI (eds.) (1991): *The Heart and Cardiovascular System*, 2193 pp. Raven Press, New York.
34. G. Clifford (2000), Matlab software, <http://www.gnu.org/>.
35. G. Karraz, G. Magenes (2006) "Automatic Classification of Heartbeats using Neural Network Classifier based on a Bayesian Framework", *Proceeding of the 28th IEEE EMBS Annual international Conference*, New York City, USA, FrEp8.10, pp 4016-4019.
36. Geselowitz DB (1964): Dipole theory in electrocardiography. *Am. J. Cardiol.* 14:(9) 301-6.
37. Goldberger E (1942a): The aVL, aVR, and aVF leads; A simplification of standard lead electrocardiography. *Am. Heart J.* 24: 378-96.
38. Goldberger E (1942b): A simple indifferent electrocardiographic electrode of zero potential and a technique of obtaining augmented, unipolar extremity leads. *Am. Heart J.* 23: 483-92.
39. Goldman MJ (1986): *Principles of Clinical Electrocardiography*, 12th ed., 460 pp. Lange Medical Publications, Los Altos, Cal.
40. Gritzali, F. (1988): "Towards a generalized scheme for QRS detection in ECG waveforms", *Signal Process.*, 15, pp. 183-192.
41. Gulrajani RM, Mailloux GE (1983): A simulation study of the effects of torso inhomogeneities on electrocardiographic potentials using realistic heart and torso models. *Circ. Res.* 52: 45-56.
42. Gulrajani RM, Roberge FA, Mailloux GE (1989): The forward problem of electrocardiography. In *Comprehensive Electrocardiology: Theory and Practice in Health and Disease*, 1st ed. Vol. 1, ed. PW Macfarlane, TDV Lawrie, pp. 237-88.
43. H.K. Joeng, K.-K Kim, S.C. Hwang, and M.-H. Lee(1989) "A new Algorithm for P-Wave detection in the ECG Signal" *Proceedings of the Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*, Vol. 1, pp. 42-43.
44. Hagan, M. T., and M. Menhaj (1994): "Training Feedforward Networks with the Marquardt Algorithm" *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 989-993.
45. Hodgkin AL, Rushton WA (1946): The electrical constants of a crustacean nerve fiber. *Proc. R. Soc. (Biol.)* B133: 444-79.
46. Homvang L, Andersen K, Dellborg M, Clemmensen P, Wagner G, Grande P, Abrahamsson P (1999): "Relative contributions of a single-admission 12-lead electrocardiogram and early 24-hour continuous electrocardiographic monitoring for early risk stratification in patients with unstable coronary artery disease", *Am J Cardiol*, vol. 83, pp. 667-674.
47. Hurst JW, Schlant RC, Rackley CE, Sonnenblick EH, Wenger NK (eds.) (1990): *The Heart: Arteries and Veins*, 7th ed., 2274 pp. McGraw-Hill, New York.
48. Hyttinen J (1989): *Development of aimed ECG-leads*. Tampere Univ. Tech., Tampere, Finland, Thesis, pp. 138. (Lic. Tech. thesis).
49. J. A. Hanley " B. J. McNeil (1982): "The Meaning and Use of the Area under a Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve," *Radiology* VOL. 143, pp. 29-36.
50. J. A. Swets, *ROC Analysis Applied to the Evaluation of Medical Imaging Techniques*," *Investigative Radiology* 14(1979),109-121.
51. J. Pan and W. J. Tompkins, A real-time QRS detection algorithm. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, BME-32(3):230-236, 1985.
52. Ju-won Lee and Gun-Ki Lee, "Design of an Adaptive Filter with Dynamic Structure For ECG signal Processing", *International Journal of Control, Automation, and System*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 137-142, March 2005.
53. Ju-Won Lee, Gun-Ki Lee (2005): "A design of an adaptive filter with a dynamic structure for ECG signal processing", *International Journal of Control, Automation, and systems*, vol.3, no.1, pp. 137-142.

54. Kadambe, S., Murray, R., and Boudreaux-Bartels, F. (1999): "Wavelet transform-based QRS complex detector", *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, 46, pp. 838–848.
55. Kay S M and Marple S L (1981): "Spectrum analysis- a Modern perspective" *Proc. IEEE*, Vol. 69, pp. 1380–1419.
56. Kléber AG, Riegger CB (1986): Electrical constants of arterially perfused rabbit papillary muscle. *J. Physiol. (Lond.)* 385: 307-24.
57. Lanza GA, Manzoli A, Pasceri V, et al. Ischemic-like ST-segment changes during Holter monitoring in patients with angina pectoris and normal coronary arteries but negative exercise testing. *Am J Cardiol*, vol. 79, pp.1- 6.
58. Lanza GA, Mascellanti M, Placentino M, Crea F, Lucente M, Maseri A (1994): "Usefulness of a third Holter lead in the detection of myocardial ischemia". *Am J Cardiol*, vol. 74, pp.1216-1219.
59. Lanza GA, Pedrotti P, Pasceri V, Lucente M, Crea F, Maseri A (1996): "Autonomic changes associated with spontaneous coronary spasm in patients with variant angina". *J Am Coll Cardiol*, vol. 28, pp. 1249-1256.
60. Lippman, R. P. (1987): "An Introduction to Computing with Neural Nets" *IEEE ASSP Magazine*, pp. 4-22.
61. Long Term H-ECG database, 35 records available: <http://www.Physionet.com>.
62. Lynch, R.M., Rayner, P.J., and Holden, S.B (1991): "Removal of degeneracy in adaptive Volterra networks by dynamic structuring". *Proceedings of IEEE international conference on Acoustics, speech, and signalprocessing*, , pp. 2069-2072.
63. M. Pauletti, C. Marchesi (2001): "Model Based Signal Characterisation for Long Term Personal Monitoring", *IEEE Computer in Cardiology*; 28: pp.413- 416.
64. M. Sabry-Rizk, W. Zgallai, C. Morgan, S. El-Khafif, E.R. Carson and K.T.V. Grattan (2000): "Novel decision strategy for P wave detection utilising nonlinearly synthesised ECG components and their enhanced pseudo spectral resonances", *IEEE proc.-sci. Meas. Technol.*, Vol. 147, No. 6, pp 389-393.
65. Macfarlane PW, Lawrie TDV (eds.) (1989): *Comprehensive Electrocardiology: Theory and Practice in Health and Disease*, 1st ed., Vols. 1, 2, and 3, 1785 pp. Pergamon Press, New York.
66. Macfarlane PW, Lawrie TDV (eds.) (1989): *Comprehensive Electrocardiology: Theory and Practice in Health and Disease*, 1st ed., Vols. 1, 2, and 3, 1785 pp. Pergamon Press, New York.
67. MacKay, D. J. C. (1992): "Bayesian Interpolation", *Neural Computation*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 415-447.
68. MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database Directory (Records), Boston's Beth Israel Hospital (now the Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center). Available: <http://www.Physionet.com>.
69. Mason R, Likar L (1966): A new system of multiple leads exercise electrocardiography. *Am. Heart J.* 71:(2) 196-205.
70. Nelson CV, and Geselowitz DB (1976): *The Theoretical Basis of Electrocardiology*, 544 pp. Oxford University.
71. Nelson CV, Rand PW, Angelakos TE, Hugenholtz PG (1972): Effect of intracardiac blood on the spatial vectorcardiogram. *Circ. Res.* 31:(7) 95-104.
72. Netter FH (1971): *Heart*, Vol. 5, 293 pp. The Ciba Collection of Medical Illustrations, Ciba Pharmaceutical Company, Summit, N.J.
73. Netter FH (1971): *Heart*, Vol. 5, 293 pp. The Ciba Collection of Medical Illustrations, Ciba Pharmaceutical Company, Summit, N.J.
74. P. Laguna, et. , (1990): "New Algorithm for QT Interval Analysis in 24-hour Holter ECG: Performance and Applications", *Med. & Biol. Eng. & Comput.*, Vol. 28, pp. 67-73.
75. Pablo Lugana, Raimon Jane, Oliver Meste, Peter W. Poon, Pere Caminal and Natish V. Thakor, Adaptive Filter for Event Related Bio-Electrical Signals Using an Impulse Correlated Reference Input: Comparison with Signal Averaging Techniques. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* Vol. 39, October 1992.
76. Parzen E (1974): "Some Recent Advances in Time Series Modelling", *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, AC-19, pp. 723-730.
77. Paul JS, Reddy MR, Kumar VJ. A (2000): "transform domain SVD filter for suppression of muscle noise artefact in exercise ECG's", *IEEE Trans. Biomed.Eng*; vol. 3, pp. 654-663.
78. Pilkington TC, and Plonsey R (1982): *Engineering Contributions to Biophysical Electrocardiology*, 248 pp. IEEE New York.
79. POLI, R., CAGNONI, S., and VALLI, G. (1995): "Genetic design of optimum linear and nonlinear QRS detectors", *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, 42, pp. 1137-1141.
80. Quyyumi AA, Crake T, Mockus LJ, Wright CA, Rickards AF, Fox K. (1986): "Value of the bipolar lead CM5 in electrocardiography", *Br Heart J*, vol. 56, pp. 372-376.
81. Quyyumi AA, Wright C, Fox K. (1983): Ambulatory electrocardiographic ST-segment changes in healthy volunteers. *Br Heart J*, vol. 50, pp.460-464.
82. RH. Clayton, SW. Lord, JM. McComb, A. Murray (1997): "Comparison of Autoregressive and Fourier Transform Based Techniques for Estimating RR Interval Spectra", *IEEE*, Vol.0276-6547, pp 379-382.

83. Rissanen J (1984): "Universal coding, information prediction and estimation", IEEE Trans. Inf. Theory 30, pp. 629-30.
84. Robert S.H. Istepanian, Leontios J. Hadjileontiadis, and Stavros M. Panas (2001): "ECG data compression using wavelets and higher order statistics method", IEEE vol. 5, no. 2, pp 108-115.
85. Ruch TC, Patton HD (eds.) (1982): Physiology and Biophysics, 20th ed., 1242 pp. W. B. Saunders, Philadelphia.
86. Rudy Y, Plonsey R, Liebman J (1979): The effects of variations in conductivity and geometrical parameters on the electrocardiogram, using an eccentric spheres model. *Circ. Res.* 44: 104-11.
87. Rumelhart, D. E., G. E. Hinton, and R. J. Williams (1986): "Learning Representations by Back-propagating Errors" *Nature*, vol. 323, pp. 533-536.
88. Rush S (1975): *An Atlas of Heart-Lead Transfer Coefficients*, 211 pp. University Press of New England, Hanover, New Hampshire.
89. Ruttkay-Nedeck I (1971): Respiratory changes of instantaneous spatial cardiac vectors. In *Vectorcardiography 2. Proc. XIth Internat. Symp. Vectorcardiography*, New York 1970, ed. I Hoffman, RI Hamby, E Glassman, pp. 115-8, North-Holland Publishing, Amsterdam.
90. S. Osowski, and Tran Hoai Linh(2000) " Fuzzy clustering neural network for classification of ECG beats", IEEE INNS-ENNS International Joint Conference on Neural Networks, (IJCNN'00)-Volume 5.
91. SABRY-RIZK, M., ZGALLAI, W., EL-KHAFIF, S., CARSON, E.R., and GRATTAN, K.T.V. (1998) : "Higher-order ambulatory electrocardiogram identification and motion artifact suppression with adaptive second- and third-order Volterra filters" , *Proc. SPIE - Int. Soc. Opt. Eng.*, 3461, pp. 417-431.
92. Scheidt S (1983): *Basic Electrocardiography: Leads, Axes, Arrhythmias*, Vol. 2/35, 32 pp. Ciba Pharmaceutical Company, Summit, N. J.
93. Scheidt S (1984): *Basic Electrocardiography: Abnormalities of Electrocardiographic Patterns*, Vol. 6/36, 32 pp. Ciba Pharmaceutical Company, Summit, N.J.
94. Scher AM, Young AC (1957): Ventricular depolarization and the genesis of the QRS. *Ann. N.Y. Acad. Sci.* 65: 768-78.
95. Shandling AH, Bernstein SB, Kennedy HL, Ellestad MH (1992): "Efficacy of three-channel electrocardiographic monitoring for the detection of myocardial ischemia", *Am Heart J*, vol.123, pp.310-316.
96. Simonson E, Horibe H, Okamoto N, Schmitt OH (1966): Effect of electrode displacement on orthogonal leads. In *Proc. Long Island Jewish Hosp. Symposium, Vectorcardiography*, ed. I Hoffman, p. 424, North-Holland Publishing, Amsterdam.
97. So. H. H and Chan K. L.(1997) " Development of QRS Detection Method for Real Time Ambulatory Cardiac Monitor", *Proc 19 Annu Int Conf IEEE EMBS*, Chicago, USA, pp. 289-292.
98. Steven W. Smith *The Scientist and Engineer's Guide to Digital Signal Processing Second Edition* California Technical Publishing 1997-1999 P.P 319-327.
99. Suppappola S, Sun Y. A.(1991): "Comparison of three QRS Detection Algorithms using the AHA ECG Database", *IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society*:13, 586-587.
100. Van Oosterom A, Plonsey R (1991): The Brody effect revisited. *J. Electrocardiol.* 24:(4) 339-48.
101. Vogl, T. P., J. K. Mangis, A. K. Rigler, W. T. Zink, and D. L. Alkon (1988):"Accelerating the Convergence of the Backpropagation Method", *Biological Cybernetics*, vol. 59, pp. 256-264.
102. Voukydis PC (1974): Effect of intracardiac blood on the electrocardiogram. *N. Engl. J. Med.* 9: 612-6.
103. Waller AD (1887): A demonstration on man of electromotive changes accompanying the heart's beat. *J. Physiol. (Lond.)* 8: 229-34.
104. Waller AD (1889): On the electromotive changes connected with the beat of the mammalian heart, and on the human heart in particular. *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. (Lond.)* 180: 169-94.
105. WIEBEN, O., AFONSO, V. X., and TOMPKINS, W. J. (1999): "Classification of premature ventricular complexes using filter bank features induction of decision trees and a fuzzy rule-based system", *Med. Biol. Eng. Compute.*, 37, pp. 560-565.
106. Williams PL, Warwick R (eds.) (1989): *Gray's Anatomy*, 37th ed., 1598 pp. Churchill Livingstone, Edinburgh.
107. Wilson FN, Johnston FD, Macleod AG, Barker PS (1934): Electrocardiograms that represent the potential variations of a single electrode. *Am. Heart J.* 9: 447-71.
108. Wilson FN, Johnston FD, Rosenbaum FF, Erlanger H, Kossmann CE, Hecht H, Cotrim N, Menezes de Oliveira R, Scarsi R, Barker PS (1944): The precordial electrocardiogram. *Am. Heart J.* 27: 19-85.
109. Wilson FN, Macleod AG, Barker PS (1931): Potential variations produced by the heart beat at the apices of Einthoven's triangle. *Am. Heart J.* 7: 207-11.
110. ZGALLAI, W. (2000): "The application of higher-order statistics to non-invasive fetal electrocardiogram (ECG) detection". PhD Thesis, City University, London, UK,